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The *Global Research Journal of Business Management (GRJBM)* is a publication of the Association of Management and Social Sciences Researchers of Nigeria (AMSSRN). It is a peer-reviewed journal published real-time online and two times annually in hardcopy, focusing on cutting-edge research and practical solutions in business management and related disciplines.

Scope

GRJBM invites research articles from a broad spectrum of topics, including but not limited to organizational behavior, strategic management, financial management, human resource management, entrepreneurship, and the impact of technology on business processes.

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To be a global leader in fostering scholarly debates and disseminating high-quality, timely, and impactful research on contemporary business management issues.

Mission

To continuously provide an intellectually stimulating platform for academics, practitioners, and policymakers to share insights, drive innovation, and contribute to the advancement of business management practices worldwide.

EDITORIAL PREFACE

We are pleased to present Volume 2, Issue 2 of the *Global Research Journal of Business Management (GRJBM)*, a publication of the Association of Management and Social Sciences Researchers of Nigeria (AMSSRN). As a trusted platform for the dissemination of impactful research, GRJBM continues to deliver high-quality, peer-reviewed articles that address contemporary challenges and opportunities in the realm of business management.

This issue features an engaging collection of articles that examine critical themes. Together, these studies reflect the journal's commitment to advancing knowledge and informing practice within Nigeria and beyond.

We are deeply grateful to our contributors for their insightful work and to our reviewers and editorial team for their dedication to maintaining the high standards of GRJBM. The unwavering support of AMSSRN has also been instrumental in the continued success of this journal.

We trust that the articles in this issue will stimulate meaningful discussions and provide actionable insights for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers.

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Synergy between Entrepreneurship and Poverty Reduction Among the IDPs in Gerei local government Area of Adamawa State.

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Abstract

Research Purpose: This paper examines the synergy between entrepreneurship and poverty reduction among internally displaced persons in Gerei LGA. Abject poverty and worsening unemployment partly due to the activities of insurgency, cattle rustling, natural disasters and illiteracy were evident among internally displaced persons in Gerei LGA.

Design/ Methodology/ Approach: A sample of fifty (50) respondents including young and old were randomly selected from the IDP camps in Gerei LGA for the study. Data was collected and analyzed using mean and standard deviation for the research questions. The results of the Analysis in table 4.1, has a mean and standard deviation of 3.41 and 1.49 shows that entrepreneurship have significant contribution to the internally displaced persons, the result of the analysis further indicates that there challenges faced among the IDPs because the calculated grand mean and standard deviation of 3.87 and 1.20, the result also outlines and indicates the possible solutions to mitigates those challenges because the calculated grand mean and standard deviation of 4.98 and 0.90.

Findings: The study reveals that there are significant synergy and possible significance of entrepreneurship among the IDPs. It also reveals that significant challenges exist; it further buttressed the possible solutions to some of the identified challenges.

Originality/Value Added: Based on the findings, it is therefore recommended that; Government should assist the emerging IDP entrepreneurs with soft loans to develop their trade so as to reduce the incessant poverty among them.

Keywords: *Entrepreneurship, Poverty reduction and Internally Displaced Persons*

Introduction

As a result of situations of armed conflicts (or the threat thereof) and mass violations of human rights, as well as floods, earthquakes and other natural disasters, the number of people fleeing their homes has increased dramatically over recent years. There are also deeper-seated factors underlying this phenomenon of mass displacement. Imasuen, (2015) asserts that, under -development, poverty, unequal distribution of wealth, unemployment, ethnic tensions, subjugation of minorities, intolerance, absence of democratic procedures, and many other factors have been cited as causes. Under the following working definition of “Internally Displaced Persons” (IDPs), which was developed by the Special Rapporteur on IDPs Ocha, (2004) defines internally displaced persons, as persons or groups of persons who have been forced to flee their homes or places of habitual residence suddenly or unexpectedly as a result of armed conflict, internal strife, systematic violations of human rights or natural or manmade disasters, and who have not crossed an internationally recognized state border.

Displaced persons under international law are persons or groups of persons who have been forced or obligated to flee or to leave their homes or places of habitual residence, in particular, as a result of or in order to avoid the effects of armed conflict, situations of generalized violence, violations of human rights or natural or human-made disasters, and they must have either remain within their own national borders (as Internally Displaced Persons) or they must have crossed an internationally recognized state border as Refugees Ladan, (2004).

The United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD 2012: 24) defines entrepreneurship as the “capacity to and willingness to undertake conception, organization and management of a productive new venture, accepting all attendant risks and seeking profit as a reward”. Entrepreneurship is an essential tool for poverty reduction in every society. It is globally considered as an alternative way to tackle most of the socioeconomic problems confronting nations. This is because entrepreneurship has the capacity to create jobs and thereby cushion the effects of the humanitarian crisis among the IDPs in Adamawa state.

It is seen as a key contributing factor to sustainable economic development and poverty reduction in every nation Dialoke et al (2017). Entrepreneurship is therefore a panacea to sustainable wealth creation among the IDPs who have virtually lost all the means of their livelihood to Boko-Haram crisis. Augustine (2019) noted that the effects of the crisis has brought an unimaginable misery and hardship to the IDPs who have virtually lost all their means of livelihood.

The UN Secretary General (1992) described the IDPs as people or individuals that have been forced to flee their homes as a result of or in order to avoid the effects of conflicts situation of a generalized violence, violations of human rights or disaster and who have not gone outside the border of their own country. The International Organization for migration and NEMA in Augustine (2019) that there were estimated 2,152,000 and 2,155,618 IDPs by the year 2015 and 2016 respectively due to the activities of the Boko-Haram Insurgence. The kampala Convention Declaration on IDPs even though has not yet been domesticated in Nigeria is very clear about the roles of government in empowering the IDPs to be self employed. Entrepreneurship development is therefore key in the management of the IDPs. It has the capacity to reduce poverty among them through the start up of businesses among.

Entrepreneurship

The term entrepreneurship is derived from a French word entrepreneur meaning the one who under takes. In line with this, Entrepreneurship is the ability to envisage and chart a course for a new business venture by combining information from the functional discipline and from the external environment in the context of extraordinary uncertainty and ambiguity which direct attention on the new business venture. It revolves around substantial resources acquisition and development which leads to providing, sustaining, communicating and coordination. Hoit (2006) defines entrepreneurship as the process of bringing together creative and innovative ideas and exploring management and organization skills to combine people, money and resources to meet an identified need and thereby create wealth. Thus, Ekong (2008) calls it education provided to develop the individual in the skills, altitudes, competencies, belief and the perspective of conceiving, planning, starting and managing enterprise for sustained benefits. This definition seems to be too bogus and so Oguegbune and Ugbe (2008) narrowed it down to a process of exposing learners to the essential skills for effective development and management of an enterprise at any level. This definition seems to be adequate enough.

Entrepreneurship is the dynamic process of creating incremental wealth. This wealth is created by individuals who assume the major risks in terms of equity, time, and or career commitment of providing value for some product or service. The product or service itself may or may not be new or unique but value must somehow be infused by the entrepreneur by securing and allocating the necessary skills and resources.

Timmons (1994) defines entrepreneurship as the ability to create and practically build something out of nothing. Adegoh and Daugara cited in Augustine (2014) maintains that entrepreneurship is the function of seeking investment, production, production opportunity and organizing an enterprise to undertake new production process, raising capability, hiring labour, arranging resources and introducing new organizations. In the same vein,

Augustine (2014:154) maintains that:

Entrepreneurship is the ability of the entrepreneur to make something tangible out of nothing. She adds that entrepreneurship is much more about the ability of the entrepreneur to make use his/her Imaginations to make something happen. It is about the ability of the entrepreneur to become flexible, initiative and willing to thing and take risk of mobilizing resources to produce something meaningful and useful. Entrepreneurship is about the skills to create wealth by an individual who takes the risks in term of resources, time and the commitment or dedication to make something or create value out of nothing.

Entrepreneur

Dangana (2014) defines entrepreneur as one who sees opportunity and maximizes the opportunity for wealth creation. Frank Carney (n.d) defined entrepreneurs as ‘risk takers’ in new venture creation –are uniquely optimistic, hard-driving, committed individuals who derive great satisfaction from being independent. He is of the view that successful entrepreneurs are are never afraid of taking risk they are eager and committed to their business because they anxious to be independent. The IDPs have lost all their livelihood and are disparate to recover their losses through entrepreneurship startup. Joseph Alios Schumpeter (1883-1950) “entrepreneurs are not necessarily motivated by profit but regard it as a standard for measuring achievement or success”.

The Role of Entrepreneurship education

Economic development means growth plus change in the living standards of the people. It goes with upward improvement where the real per capita income of the citizenry improves over time. Entrepreneurship has a significant role to perform in the overall development of a nation. It remains one of the important ingredients of economic development of a nation. It has been accepted worldwide that entrepreneurship is a catalyst to economic advancement. Therefore the significant role played by entrepreneurs in the economic development of any nation cannot be over emphasized. Dhaliwal et al (2016:4263) explains that:

The crucial role played the entrepreneurs in the development of the Western countries has made the people of the underdeveloped countries too much conscious of the significance of entrepreneurship for economic development now. People have begun to realize that for achieving the goal of economic development, it is necessary to increase entrepreneurship both qualitatively and quantatively in the country. It is only active and enthusiastic entrepreneurs who fully explore the potentialities of the country’s available resources- labour, technology and capital

They are of the view that there is no alternative to entrepreneurial development in a developing nation like Nigeria which is blessed with abundant human and material resources. Nigeria is blessed with potential entrepreneurs who are capable of exploiting the abundant and laying material resources. Dreher & Gassebner; Dutta; and Sobel in Doran et al (2018) also attested to the fact that entrepreneurship plays a critical role in the overall development of a nation. He further noted that impact of entrepreneurship on economic growth also differ according to the level of development. It was as a result of this that Schumpeter (1934), Smelser (1956) and Harbison (1965) viewed the entrepreneurs as key figures in economic development of a nation because of their ability to be innovative. This means then that development does not arise overnight but undergo process using some agents or catalyst like an entrepreneur who sees opportunities where others are seeing problems. Entrepreneurship therefore has the following specific in the development of any nation.

Poverty

Poverty has been defined differently by different scholars. For example, some conceive the conceive poverty to mean lack of access to basic needs, productive resources, inefficient common resources; as well as a result of exclusion mechanism, Ifeoma et al (2018). The World Bank states that poverty is categorized as both absolute and relative. When poverty is conceived as absolute; it means lack of

resources to meet the basic needs for survival such as lack of security; the absence of one or more factors that enable individuals or families to take responsibilities and enjoy the fundamental human rights n Ali and Ali in Ifeoma (2018) Tadaro and Smith (2003), Oladunmi (1999) and Haruna (2002). Poverty like explained by Savadogo et al (2015) who made a community based definition reveals that poverty means much more than lack of access to basic needs of life to include; vulnerability, powerlessness, voicelessness, indecent living conditions, absence of social capital and community net-works among others. Poverty is conceived as a multi-dimensional phenomenon. Poverty is a situation that occurs as a result of several factors. Poverty is multidimensional in its symptoms, multivariate in its causes, dynamic in its trajectory, and quite complex in its relation to health M.Mowafi, and M.Khawaja (2005:1)

In Nigeria, the concept of poverty is much more captured when is concerned with what Cobbinah et al (2013) referred to “social exclusion and inequality in the distribution of the national resources”. Poverty even though a global phenomenon should be tackled locally using the available local resources. Nigeria no doubt is a country blessed with abundant human natural resources capable of leveraging her to the expected level of growth and development. The major problem of the country like Claude Ake would say is the fact that development has never been on the agenda of the leaders of the leaders. The major motivating factor for aspiring into leadership position has always been for self aggrandizim to the detriment of the teaming masses that has continued to wallow in abject poverty for years.

Poverty Alleviation Strategies in Nigeria.

In order to check the rising unemployment, surging crime rate and incidence of poverty, different government administrations introduced diverse poverty reduction policies (PRPs) to redress the problems and challenges highlighted above (Eriki and Okafor, 2005) thereby making Nigerians creative, innovative and resourceful to create more wealth and improve their general wellbeing. Some of the poverty reduction policies (PRPs) initiated by different regimes in Nigeria include: (a) General Yakubu Gowon’s National Accelerated Food Production Programme (NAFPP) and Nigerian Agricultural Cooperative Bank (NACB); (b) General Olusegun Obasanjo’s Operation Feed the Nation (OFN); (c) Alhaji Shehu Shagari’s Green Revolution Programme (GRP); (d) General Ibrahim Badamosi Babangida created the Directorate of Food, Roads and Rural Infrastructure (DFRRI), National Agricultural Land Development Authority (NALDA); (e) General Sani Abacha’s Family Economic Advancement Programme (FEAP) and his wife’s Family Support Programme (FSP); (f) President Olusegun Obasanjo’s National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS); (g) Alhaji Umaru Musa Yar’adua’s “Seven-Point Agenda; (h) President Goodluck Jonathan’s Economic Transformation Agenda including the Vision 20:2020 presently under implementation (Raimi et al, 2011).

It has consistently been argued that for developing nations (Nigeria inclusive) to grow and catch up with other developing nations, there is the urgent need for a viable entrepreneurship model that would help tackle hydra-headed poverty, unemployment, illiteracy, chronic diseases, maternal mortality, infant mortality, crimes, conflict, terrorism/insurgency, while at the same time promote growth of SMEs, wealth creation, enhance value reorientation, preserve the ecosystem from abuse and in the final analysis achieve sustainable economic development (National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy, 2004, DFID, 2009). Viewed from the same angle, Roy (2010) describes Africa’s socio-economic travails as:

“Widespread poverty, corruption, inadequate resources, poorly trained labour supplies, wars and other forms of civil strife such as ethnic cleansing, pandemic diseases such as HIV/AIDS and malaria, tribal tensions, and ruinous economic policies have led to problems of such scope and dimension that it is only governments, African and international, that can mobilize the necessary capital to begin to make headway on these enormous issues.”

Entrepreneurship has been defined differently by different scholars. Robert C.Ronstadt is of the view that:

Relevance of Entrepreneurial Skills to the internally displaced persons

Ifeoma *et al* (2018) is of the view that “entrepreneurship is an alternative way to tackle some of the socio-economic problems that bedevil most countries of the world currently, especially problem of high unemployment and poverty. They maintained that entrepreneurship action undertaken by government to reduce the level of poverty in the economy. The IDPs are among the vulnerable individuals of Nigeria who suffer from unemployment and abject poverty, the government need to put in place and enhance entrepreneurial skills and knowledge through structured training and programmes targeted on the IDPs who are in their numbers. Osuagu in Ifeoma *et al* (2018) noted that entrepreneurship is catalyst to increase the rate of economic growth, creating job opportunities as well as reducing dependence on import of manufactured goods. This has become necessary for Nigeria as a nation to look inward to identify and develop who are capable of creative. This will go a long way to salvage the nation from over dependence on foreign products. The singular outbreak of the Corona Virus 2019 in Wuhan China that has put the world on stand still is enough a lesson for the Nigerian government to invest in entrepreneurship development.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study site and design

A descriptive cross-sectional survey was carried out in the Sangere-marghi IDP camp in Girei LGA between March 2014 and November 2022. The Sangere-marghi IDP camp is located in the geographical centre of Girei. The study was undertaken in Girei, one of the local government units in Adamawa state. The research region is located between 90 11' and 90 39' north latitude and 120 21' and 120 49' east longitude of the Greenwich Meridian (Adebayo, 2012). The climate is tropical wet and dry, and the region is part of the Northern Guinea Savannah Zone. The dry season lasts at least five months (November-March), while the rainy season lasts from April to October. The average yearly rainfall is 700mm. The Study area is bordered on the north by Song Local Government Area, on the east by Fufore, and on the south and west by Yola and Demsa. The entire land mass of the area is approximately 2,186 square kilometers.

3.0 Methodology

A structured questionnaire was used as instrument for the data collection which was adopted by the researcher. The researcher considered questionnaire as the most appropriate way to generate the required data. The questionnaire was addressed to the IDPs and their stakeholders. The questionnaire will provide the data from the respondents which are required for the study.

The Purposive sampling was used to sample Girei IDP camp and environs in that the IDPs lives there. This is because most the IDPs from Michika and Madagali the two worst heat local government resides there for business purposes. Simple random sampling was additionally used to select 50 respondents for the study. Means and Standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. SPSS version 26 was used to compute the analysis and results.

4.0 RESULT

SECTION A: RESULT

TABLE 1; SIGNIFICANCE OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP
--

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	SD	D	UD	A	SA	\bar{X}	SD	DECISION
1	IDP's based entrepreneurship programmes are available in Gerei community.	5	10	2	18	15	3.56	1.37	Agreed
2	Social welfare programmes are ad-hoc in nature.	7	8	1	21	13	3.50	1.40	Agree
3	Girei IDP's been provided with foods and none food relief materials from time to time.	9	4	3	20	14	3.52	1.45	Agreed
4	I am comfortable with the distribution pattern of the relief materials in the Gerei host community.	16	8	1	8	17	3.04	1.74	Undecided
Grand Mean							3.41	1.49	Agreed
TABLE 2; IDENTIFIED CHALLENGES									
5	Provision of social welfare programmes to IDP is limited in scope.	1	2	2	28	17	4.16	0.84	Agreed
6	None availability of IDP's based entrepreneurship training empowerment affect their livelihood in the host community.	4	4	2	17	23	4.02	1.25	Agreed
7	The training and empowerment of the IDP's in the Gerei host community is fraught with human right abuses.	1 2	6	3	19	10	3.18	1.51	Undecided
8	Non provision of IDPs based training and empowerment to engage in small scale business has impoverished many	4	4	0	22	20	4.0	1.21	Agreed
9	Lack of entrepreneurship skills have impoverished the IDPs	5	2	1	22	20	4.0	1.23	Agreed
Grand Mean							3.87	1.20	Agreed
Table 3; POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS									
10	IDPs should be trained in skills acquisition to enable self employed	2	0	1	24	23	4.32	0.87	Strongly Agreed
11	IDPs should have access to micro-credit facilities	2	1	1	28	18	4.18	0.89	Agreed
12	Compulsory saving scheme should be taught among the IDPs	0	1	1	28	20	4.34	0.63	Strong Agreed
13	The small scale should be supervised and monitored from time to time	0	0	0	22	28	4.56	0.50	Strongly Agreed
14	Successful entrepreneurs among the IDPs should be trained to assist the weak ones	0	0	0	31	19	4.38	0.49	Strongly Agreed
15	Successful IDP entrepreneur should be given further assistance to increase their business	3	1	0	29	17	4.12	0.98	Agreed
Grand Mean							4.31	0.98	Agreed

Research question one: What is significance of entrepreneurship to IDPS in Gerei LGA?

From the result in table 4.1, on whether the respondents agreed on the significance of entrepreneurship to internally displaced persons. The respondents response has grand mean score of 3.41 with standard

deviation of 1.49, which indicates that it is agreed that entrepreneurship plays a significant role among the IDPs in the study area. As given in the chart below.

Research question two: What are the challenges of entrepreneurship among IDPS in Gerei LGA?

From the result in table 4.1, From the result in table 4.1, on whether the entrepreneurship activities faced some challenges among the IDPs in Gerei. The respondent's response has grand mean score of 3.87 with standard deviation of 1.20. Thus, indicates that they agreed that entrepreneurship faces challenges among

the IDPs in the study area. As given in the chart below.

Research question three: What are possible solutions to challenges of entrepreneurship among IDPS in Girei LGA?

From the result in table 4.1, the possible solutions to challenges of entrepreneurship among IDPS in Girei LGA has grand mean score of 4.31 with standard deviation of 0.99. Therefore, from the above descriptive statistics results, we can say there are enough plausible solutions to mitigate the challenges so as to reduce poverty among the study participant as given in the chart on the next page.

4. DISCUSSION

5. Conclusion

The core objective of this paper is to examine the synergy that exist between entrepreneurship education/skill as mechanism for empowerment of internally displaced persons in Girei local government area. Based on the objective, exhaustive review of literature was carried out to provide more insight into the subject matter being discussed. On the strength of the literature reviewed, it was discovered that entrepreneurship development could be an effective tool for poverty reduction, stimulating employment as well as resettlement of IDPs and promoting gender equality. Despite the prospect of entrepreneurship education and skill development, it is faced with the challenges of paucity of funds, and lack of experienced skill trainers and host of other factors.

Recommendations

Consequent upon the above the following recommendations were made;

1. Governmentes at all levels and nongovernmental organization should provide certain basic facilities in the IDP camps to facilitate skill acquisition
1. Teacher education trainers should also be trained and retrained for effective integration of entrepreneurship education in teacher training institution
2. International donor agencies should partner with government to provide trained IDPs with starter packs after their training

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

REFERENCES

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1. Dhaliwal A. (2016) Role of Entrepreneurship in Economic Development in International Journal of Scientific Research and Management (IJSRM) Vol. (4) Issue (06) 4262-4269 (2916) www.ijsrm.in ISSN (e):2321-3418
2. Doran J. McCarthy N.& O'Connor (2018) The role of entrepreneurship in stimulating economic growth in developed and developing countries, Cogent Economic & Finance, 6:1, 14442093, DOI:10.1080/23322039.2018.144209
3. Rufus B .A.(2010) Towards a definition of Poverty: poor people' perspective and implications for poverty reduction. In Journal of Developing Societies. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0169796x0902500201>.
4. M.Mowafi and M. Khawaja (2005) Poverty in the Journal of Epidemiology and Community Health. Volume 59 Issue 4.<http://dx.doi.org./10.1136/jech.2004.022822>.

Singh PK, Chaudasama H 2020 "Evaluating Poverty Alleviation Strategies in a Developing Country. PloS ONE 15 (1): e0227176. Doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0227176.

EMPIRICAL TEST OF BID- ASK SPREAD AND MARKET MICROSTRUCTURE: EVIDENCE FROM NIGERIA STOCK EXCHANGE

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Abstract

Research Purpose: *This study seeks to empirically review the test of Bid- Ask Spread and Market Microstructure in Nigeria stock Exchange. Investors and traders buying and selling shares in Nigeria Stock Exchange usually carry out this test with appropriate models such as Glosten and migrom (1985) information asymmetry model, model of inventory control. Market maker model, among others.*

Design/Methodology/Approach: *This study adopts Glosten Milgroom (1985) model, who opined that the determination of the bid-ask spread can be demonstrated by assuming that an asset could take two possible values, high and low values with an equal probability for the two values. The stock prices of thirty quoted companies for the month of August, 2022, specifically 30th and 31st of August, 2022 were used.*

Findings: *The findings revealed that the model predicted accurately the prices of shares of eighteen listed companies, which is 60% of the sample of the study, while for the remaining twelve companies, the model showed how actual stock prices can be a bit high or low of the forecast for the day. This study has thus revealed how uninformed investor could be educated and be informed in having knowledge of forecasting the next day's stock prices with sometimes minor differences from the actual, using the prior day's prices.*

Originality/Value Added: *The study therefore recommends that adequate awareness and education should be embarked on, for stock market players, most of whom are uninformed to be informed.*

Key words: *Asymmetry information,.Bid-Ask Spread, market Micro structure, share prices*

1.0: Introduction:

Market micro-structure is the study of financial markets and how they operate. Market micro-structure research primarily focuses on the structure of exchanges and trading venues, the price discovery process, determinants of spreads and quotes, intraday trading behavior, and transaction costs (Kissell, 2018). Most of the academic research in period past has focused on valuation techniques to uncover the fair market price of an instrument, expected return forecasts, dividend yield approach and risk modeling techniques.

Analysts may determine the fair value price of a company by examining the company's balance sheet and profit and loss account fundamentals, such as sales figures, year-over-year growth, and revenue forecasts. Analysts may also determine which factors, sectors, or other subgroups will likely under- or over perform.

Additionally, analysts may utilize a quantitative process, such as the capital asset pricing model (CAPM) or arbitrage pricing theory (APT) to perform asset allocation and determine optimal portfolio mixes (Kissell, 2018).

While the above techniques provide valuable insight into the market's assessment of fair value and appropriate stocks to hold in the portfolio, these techniques do not provide insight into how to measure and incorporate investors' subjective assessment and preference of the securities or how markets will react to the arrival of "new" information, thus creating a gap for this study. Without taking into account these preferences, portfolio managers could transact at unfavorable prices, causing a setback in performance; a common reason why funds underperform their peers.

Market microstructure continues to be one of the fastest growing fields of financial research due to the rapid development of electronic trading. Interest in market microstructure stems also from rapid structural, technological and regulatory changes which has affected the security trading industry all over the world. Stock market crash of 1987 and increased availability of high frequency data since 1990's also increased the interest in this area (Andersen and Bondarenco, 2014). O'Hara (1995) provided a ground breaking research on financial market studies and how it operates. Since then, varying researches have been done to advance this study.

Microstructure challenges the theory that share prices reveals all information by investigating the process that prices could diverge away (or converge close to) information ally efficient equilibrium prices because rational participants are acting strategically (Biais, Glosten, & Spatt, 2005). A bid-ask spread is the amount by which the ask price exceeds the bid price for an asset in the market. The bid-ask spread is essentially the difference between the highest price that a buyer is willing to pay for an asset and the lowest price that a seller is willing to accept.

An individual looking to sell will receive the bid price while one looking to buy will pay the ask price. The bid-ask spread, along with commissions or other fees, represents the basic transaction cost of trading. The size of the spread commonly varies in accordance with the trading liquidity of the asset.

The bid-ask spread is a reflection of the supply and demand for a particular asset. The bid represents demand and the ask represents supply for an asset. The depth of the "bids" and the "asks" can have a significant impact on the bid-ask spread, making it widen significantly if one outweighs the other or if both are not robust.

If the bid price for a stock is ₦19 and the ask price for the same stock is ₦20, then the bid-ask spread for the stock in question is ₦1. The bid-ask spread can also be stated in percentage terms; it is customarily calculated as a percentage of the lowest sell price or ask price.

For the stock in the example above, the bid-ask spread in percentage terms would be calculated as ₦1 divided by ₦20 (the bid-ask spread divided by the lowest ask price) to yield a bid-ask spread of 5% ($\frac{₦1}{₦20} \times 100$). This spread would close if a potential buyer offered to purchase the stock at a higher price or if a potential seller offered to sell the stock at a lower price.

Bid-Ask Spread and Market microstructure has continued to be an area of rising interest for academics over twenty years now, as the existence of this phenomenon has been examined by researchers in most advanced capital markets of the world.

This paper seeks to empirically test information asymmetry modeling framework provided by Glosten and Milgrom (1985), which could help uninformed investors to predict daily movement of prices of securities relating to capital markets in Nigeria..

Furthermore, this research will improve on the previous studies carried out in Nigeria by providing statistical evidence to ascertain whether or not, there is significant change between the actual price and forecast price.

1.1 Objectives of the Study:

The research objective is to determine how uninformed investors/traders in the Nigeria stock market could be assisted to forecast next day's stock price with data for previous day stock price, and profiting thereby from it.

2.0: Review of Relevant Literature

2.1: Design and Structure of Nigerian Capital Market

Nigerian Capital Market is the pillar of national economy responsible for capital formation and investments. Incorporated in 1960 initially as the Lagos Stock Exchange and thereafter became the Nigerian Security Exchange (NSE) in 1977, the security market's vision to play a key and essential role in capital formation and advancement of the private (real and nominal) sector through deposit mobilization and medium and long-term investment capital.

Before its automation in 1999 a lot of structural, legal/regulatory, technological and institutional reforms has taken place from its inception to 2006, the market was known for low trade as the effect of the market was insignificant in the economy. However, the emergence in 1999 of the automated trading system and other structural, legal and economic reforms arising there from targeted at resolving this problem. The reforms facilitated in the stock market a microstructure change (osagie and okuwhere, 2019). The goal of the microstructure change was for advancement in rate and volume of trade and liquidity, as well as instilling confidence in market participants through transparency and acts that could prevent violation of ethics and other misconduct. Osamwonyi, Igbinosa and Aigboduwa (2011), opine that the stock exchange in Nigeria has exhibited significant but weak level of inventory effect and spread in the price of transactions in January 2009.

2.2: Market Microstructure Model/Theory: A Review

There are three main models to explain the behavior and setting of prices based on the theory of market microstructure. These are the inventory model, asymmetric information-based models and market maker model.

2.2.1: Inventory models deals with the problems associated with order movement and inventory risk as well as liquidity providers' optimization issues within reasonable risk aversion level, Inventory-based Models focus on inventory difficulty of a dealer who meets buyers and sellers arriving at different time. The models postulate the primary role of market-makers as liquidity providers and display exactly how the bid-ask spread rewards market-makers for price risk on inventory.

2.2.2: Asymmetric information-based model, deals with the underlying forces of market and change procedures of prices, utilizing perceptions based on the model of asymmetric information and adverse selection. These models focus on explaining market behavior that does not rely only on transaction costs, but also relies on asymmetric information. The essential feature of information-based models is that the

trading process involves decisions made by traders who have superior information compared to others. These traders who have superior information (informed traders) purchase when stock price is very low, and they sell when the price of stock rises. From the point of view of the market-maker, he always loses with informed traders and bears the costs of these trades.

2.2.3: Market-Marker Model

Garman (1976) explained the attitude of market markers, by considering those of them that possesses monopoly power and faced with many autonomous buy and sell orders. In guiding against lapses, these market markers will diverse the prices of buy and sell orders.

Hence, market microstructure focuses on how good or bad an exchange's rules facilitate effective trading. According to Easley & O'Hara (1987), market microstructure theory evolves to explain the process through which prices of assets are determined and it is an aspect of finance that deals with the information of how exchange happens in markets.

2.3: Types of Market: These include Market for dealers; Market for Limit order and Hybrid market

a. Market for dealers

This is a platform for trading, consisting of dealers who agree to sell whenever investors wishes to buy stock or agree to buy whenever investors wishes to sell.

b. Market for Limit Order

This is a market consisting of buyers and sellers who jointly accepts to provide liquidity through enlisting limit orders or desires liquidity through market orders placement.

c. Hybrid Market

This is a market that combines the attributes of the above two markets. An example of this market is New York Stock Exchange, due to the volume of business transactions that passes through the book kept for limit orders, however, setting of prices are the responsibility of the dealers.

2.4: Benefits of Market Micro-structure

i. Openness

This consists of the quantum of information made available to operators or dealers in the market. Previous Studies such as Chowdhry & Nanda (1991), Forster & George (1992) reveal that pure openness facilitates more liquidity and reduces costs of transaction to the barest minimum.

ii. Dealer's Role

Most stock exchanges are still dealers dependent, because it is costly to get providers of limit orders for the market sustenance. In addition costs of information in the market are minimized by dealers. (Benveniste et al., 1992).

iii. Market Segments

There are many segments in the market, the benefits of which include increased price signals quality. However, these segments have the demerit of low liquidity and high velocity in each market segment (Mendelson, 1987)/

2.5: Empirical Literature

Hasbrouck (1991) studies the connection between bid-ask quotes and security trades revisions for listed stock on the New York Stock Exchange (NYSE), result indicates the benefits of the content of trade information.

Chan, Christie & Schultz (1995) studies the impact of the stock exchange activities on prices of daily open and closure and resultant spread, emphasizing on specialist behaviour for listed stock on the National Association of specialist dealers automated quotations exchange. Results indicate tendency of substantial variances amid a stock market with a major specialist and competing market marker exchange. Biais, Glosten & Spatt (2005). examined the macro foundation of market micro structure, the study exposed the benefits of inventory, handling cost, and adverse selection. The results indicate how market power impact on prices, while full efficient allocation of stock was unattainable.

Yacine & Dacheng (2017) examines the possibility of how data sample with high frequency can be treated as being free from noise emanating from market micro structure at a given sampling frequency, with the aim of high frequency volatility implementation. The findings show an appreciable progress in capital market liquidity over a decade; this has culminated in enhanced frequency of safely utilization of simple, uncorrected volatility estimators.

Methodology:

This study used exploratory and ex-post facto research designs. Data about the daily share price of thirty publicly quoted companies in Nigeria were extracted from the website of cash craft Nigeria limited for 30th and 31st August, 2022 for empirical testing.

This study adopted the model of Glosten and Miligrom (1985),, who believed that the spread from bid – ask quote can be determined by assuming the possibility of an asset having two possible values, i.e. a value that is high V^H and a value that is low, V^L with probability that is homogeneous to the two possible values. Probability π .are given to Informed investors. There is a risk neutrality assumption for all informed investors at $a = (V^H + V^L/2)$. The ask price “A” is then the expected value of the asset.

Model specification:

The ask price

$$A = V^H \pi + a (1 - \pi) \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

The bid price

$$B = V^L \pi + a (1 - \pi) \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

The bid –ask spread

$$A - B = \pi (V^H - V^L) \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Where

V^H = An asset high value

V^L = An asset low value

π = value of probability

Population: All publicly quoted securities in Nigeria represents the population.

Sample: Randomly selected 30 publicly quoted and traded securities, whose high and low price values are published in Nigerian Exchange Group as at 30th and 31st of August, 2022.

Data Source:: The data was extracted from the Nigerian Exchange Group’s Report through the web site of Cash Craft Management Company for 30th and 31st August, 2022.

Data Presentation and Analysis:

Here, the data generated are analyzed with the Glosten and Milgroom information asymmetry model as specified above. This analysis assist investors and simple traders in the market on how they can be informed about securities prices in the stock exchange market and reduce the adverse effects of information asymmetry in the transaction process.

The companies used and the prices at which the stock were traded in the Nigerian Exchange Group for the period are presented in appendix A of this study. The extensive analyses from the table below clearly show that the company's stock price exhibit a random walk movement. For example, for zenith bank, union bank, stanbic, sterling bank, FCMB and host of other companies, the forecasted stock price though priced low compared with the actual day's price (31st August, 2022), however approximate it.

Randomly as it is, the forecast ed stock price of unilever was priced higher than the actual, 13.15 forecasted against the actual of 12.20, a difference of 0.95, this happens occasionally to few stock prices.

In most cases, the forecasted prices are either accurate or almost accurate or approximate.

The implication of these findings is that the Glostten Milgroom model of information asymmetry could be used to reveal to uninformed investors and traders, how companies' stock prices could be forecasted and so allows them to have a little foreknowledge about subsequent day's actual stock price in the Nigerian Stock market without precisions, but very near precisions.

The model accurately forecasted the stock prices of eighteen companies which are union bank, conoil, ABC Transport, Cadbury, Dangcem, mansard, etranzact, flourmill, fincocoa, Intbrew, Japaul Gol, Nem, Nestle, NGX Group, NPFMCRFBK, UAC, UPDC and Vitaform.

The model obviously reflects random walk movement as well as significantly demonstrated the probability of achieving accurate forecast; it does minimize the cost effect of asymmetric information in the stock market.

COMPUTATION OF FORCASTED STOCK PRICES

FOR 31ST AUGUST, 2022 AND COMPARISON WITH ACTUAL PRICES FOR THE DAY.

S/N	COMPANIES	$\pi (VH - VL)$	$VL-\pi (VH - VL)$	FORCAST	ACTUAL	DIFFERENCES
1	ZENITH BANK	$.50(22 - 21.90) = 0.05$	$21.90 - 0.05$	21.85	21.90	0.05 approx.
2	UNION BANK	$0.50(5.60 - 5.60) = 0$	$5.60 - 0$	5.60	5.60	0
3	STERLING BANK	$0.50 (1.55 - 1.52) = 0.015$	$1.52 - 0.015$	1.505	1.55	0.045 Approx.
4	STANBIC	$0.50(31 - 30.85) = 0.075$	$30.85 - 0.075$	30.775	31	0.227 Approx.
5	JAIZ BANK	$0.50(0.90-0.86)=0.02$	$0.86 - 0.02$	0.84	0.86	0.02 Approx.
6	CADBURY	$0.50(13 - 13) = 0$	$13 - 0$	13	13	0
7	CHIPLC	$0.50(0.65-0.62)=0.015$	$0.62 - 0.015$	0.605	0.60	0.005 Approx.
8	CONOIL	$0.50(26.5 - 26.5) = 0$	$26.5 - 0$	26.50	26.50	0
9	DANGCEM	$0.50 (245-245) = 0$	$245 - 0$	245	245	0
10	ETRANZACT	$0.50 (2.50-2.50) = 0$	$2.50 - 0$	2.50	2.50	0
11	FCMB	$0.50 (3.07 - 3.07)= 0$	$3.07 - 0$	3.07	3.05	0.02 Approx.
12	FLOURMILL	$0.50 (27.3-27.3)= 0$	$27.3 - 0$	27.3	27.3	0
13	FINCOCOA	$0.50 (0.30- 0.30) = 0$	$0.30 - 0$	0.30	0.30	0
14	GTCO	$0.50 (19.90 - 19.80) = 0.05$	$19.80 - 0.05$	19.75	19.85	0.10 Approx.
15	INT BREWERIES	$0.50 (5 - 5 = 0$	$5 - 0$	5	5	0
16	ABC TRANSPORT	$0.50 (0.31 - 0.31) = 0$	$0.31 - 0$	0.31	0.31	0
17	JAPAUOL GOL	$0.50 (0.33 - 0.33) = 0$	$0.33 - 0$	0.33	0.33	0

18	MANSARD	$0.50 (1.81 - 1.80) = 0.005$	$1.80 - 0.005$	1.795	1.80	0.005 Approx.
19	NEM	$0.50 (5 - 5) = 0$	$5 - 0$	5	5	0
20	NESTLE	$0.50 (1350 - 1350) = 0$	$1350 - 0$	1350	1350	0
21	NAX GROUP	$0.50 (21 - 21) = 0$	$21 - 0$	21	21	0
22	NPFMCRFBK	$0.50 (1.54 - 1.54) = 0$	$1.54 - 0$	1.54	1.54	0
23	SOURININS	$0.50 (0.28 - 0.26) = 0.01$	$0.26 - 0.01$	0.25	0.26	0.01 Approx.
24	UACN	$0.50(11 - 11) = 0$	$11 - 0$	11	11	0
25	UCAP	$0.50 (12 - 11.95) = 0.025$	$11.95 - 0.025$	11.925	12	0.075 Approx.
26	UPDC	$0.50 (1.02 - 1.02) = 0$	$1.02 - 0$	1.02	1.00	0.02 forecasted price higher
27	VITAFORM	$0.50(23.60 - 23.60) = 0$	$23.60 - 0$	23.60	23.60	0
28	NAHCO	$0.50 (5.90-5.69) = 0.105$	$5.69 - 0.105$	5.585	5.70	0.115 Approx.
29	MTNN	$0.50(200-199) = 0.50$	$199 - 0.50$	198.50	199	0.50 Approx.
30	UNILEVER	$0.50 (13.15 - 13.15) = 0$	$13.15 - 0$	13.15	12.20	0.95 Forecasted price higher than Actual

Source: Researcher’s Computation, 1st September, 2022.

The importance of the analyses in the above table clearly indicates how uninformed investors could be informed or have a satisfactory knowledge of what the following day’s stock price will likely be in the stock market. It should be emphasized that the model is not a bench mark for investors to beat the market as the stock market at all times exhibit a random walk movement.

The model is not a source of market prophecy to investors. The model only helps investors to get an estimated stock price, which could be higher, lower or accurate occasionally. The market is still subject to trade manipulations and insider knowledge influence, though could be easily detected for restoration of investors’ confidence. The model helps to promote efficiency in the market and meaningfully educate uninformed investors.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This article assessed bid-ask spread and micro structure of the market, which is an integral part of finance that believes in the transformation of the hidden demands of stockholders into dealings. The study established the practical and experimental demonstration of the applicability of market micro structure model in Nigerian capital market..

The adopted model of Glosten and Miligrom (1985) predicted stock prices of eighteen securities with reasonable precision, this supports the usage of the model creditably in Nigerian stock market.

Information asymmetries are important in theory but difficult to identify and quantitatively captured in practice, especially in developing economies like Nigeria.

This article therefore recommends regular education of the investors and would be investors that hugely patronizes the capital market without the needed skills about the dynamics of stock price changes.

Adequate information and training of stakeholders, on the dynamics of capital market that will equip uninformed investors on what it takes to succeed in the market, should be conducted by regulatory organizations.

Enforcement unit should be created to enforce the rules of procedures and penalize offenders in cases of price manipulations, insider trading and other market malfeasance. This will ultimately help in restoring investors’ confidence in the market.

References

- Andersen. T.G., & Bondarenco.O (2014). VPIN and the flash crash. *Journal of financial market*, 17, 1-46.
- Benveniste, L., Marcus, A., & Wilhelm, W. (1992). What's special about the specialist? *Journal of Financial Economics*, 32(1), 61-86.
- Biais, B., Glisten, L., & Spatt, C. (2005). Market microstructure: A survey of micro foundations empirical result and policy implications. *Journal of Financial Markets*, 8(2), 217-264.
- Chan, K.C., Christie, W. G., and Schultz, P. H. (1995). Market Structure and the Intra day pattern of bid-ask spreads for NASDAQ Securities' *Journal of Business*, 1995, 68'1, 35-60.
- Chowdry, B., & Nanda, V. (1991). Multimarket trading and market liquidity. *Review of Financial Studies*, 4(3), 483-511.
- Forster, M., & George, T. (1992). Anonymity in securities markets. *Journal of Financial Intermediation*, 2(2), 168-206.
- Garman, M. (1976). Market microstructure. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 3(3), 257-275.
- Glosten, L. & Milgrom, P. (1985). Bid, ask and transaction prices in a specialist market with heterogeneously informed traders. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 14(1), 71-100.
- Mendelson, H. (1987). Consolidation, fragmentation and market performance. *Journal of Financial and Quantitative Analysis*, 22(2), 189-207.
- Hasbrouck, J. (1991). Measuring the information content of stock trades. *Journal of Finance*, 46(1), 179-207.
- O'Hara, M. (1995). *Market Microstructure Theory*. Cambridge, MA : Basil Blackwell.
- Easley, D. & O'Hara, M. (1987). Price, Trade Size, and Information in securities markets. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 19, 6990.
- Osagie, O., & Okuwhere, M. (2019). 'A Test of Market Microstructure: Evidence from Nigerian Bourse. *Amity- Journal of Finance*, Volume 3, issue 2, pg 66-76.
- Osamwonyi. I.O., Igbiosa, S. O., and Aigbodua, J. E. (2011). Operations Research Models and Market Microstructure. *Asian-Africa Journal of Economics*, 11(2); 511-531.
- Robert Kissell, (2018). *The Science of Algorithmic Trading and Portfolio Management from Financial Trading and Investment* (second Edition).
- Yacine, A., & Dacheng, X. (2017). A Hausman test for the presence of market microstructure noise in high frequency data. *Journal of Econometrics*, 211(1), 176-205.

APPENDIX

PRICELIST AS AT WEDNESDAY, AUGUST 31, 2022, FROM CASH CRAFT SITE

Security	Price	Change	PClose	Open	High	Low	Volume	Value
ABBEYBDS	1.70	0	1.70	1.70	0.00	0.00	10,811	16,540.83
ABCTRANS	0.31	0	0.31	0.31	0.00	0.00	21,650	6,711.50
ACADEMY	2.10	0	2.10	2.10	0.00	0.00	131,288	277,095.30
ACCESSCORP	8.30	0.15	8.15	8.15	8.40	8.20	27,700,910	228,032,997.80
AFRIPRUD	5.60	0	5.60	5.60	5.60	5.60	378,523	2,100,665.60
AIICO	0.55	0.02	0.53	0.53	0.55	0.53	8,475,840	4,539,448.70
AIRTELAFRI	2,040.00	0	2,040.00	2,040.00	0.00	0.00	183,550	348,747,271.90

Security	Price	Change	PClose	Open	High	Low	Volume	Value
ARDOVA	12.60	0.5	12.10	12.10	12.60	12.60	222,049	2,803,683.85
BERGER	6.60	0	6.60	6.60	0.00	0.00	2,500	15,250.00
BETAGLAS	51.20	0	51.20	51.20	0.00	0.00	50	2,365.00
BUACEMENT	52.00	0	52.00	52.00	0.00	0.00	66,431	3,387,296.75
BUAFOODS	58.30	2.5	55.80	55.80	58.30	53.50	1,713,774	93,315,867.75
CADBURY	13.00	0	13.00	13.00	0.00	0.00	110,189	1,448,613.10
CAP	16.50	0	16.50	16.50	0.00	0.00	44,196	767,494.95
CAVERTON	1.14	0.1	1.04	1.04	1.14	1.14	611,719	695,970.28
CHAMPION	3.85	0	3.85	3.85	0.00	0.00	51,337	184,013.20
CHAMS	0.27	0.01	0.26	0.26	0.27	0.27	2,930,080	791,121.60
CHIPLC	0.60	-0.05	0.65	0.65	0.60	0.60	206,000	123,840.00
CILEASING	3.20	0	3.20	3.20	0.00	0.00	47,500	149,150.00
CONOIL	26.50	0	26.50	26.50	0.00	0.00	25,324	654,439.40
CORNERST	0.69	-0.01	0.70	0.70	0.69	0.65	1,862,000	1,241,720.81
COURTVILLE	0.48	0	0.48	0.48	0.48	0.48	2,377,228	1,141,704.00
CUSTODIAN	6.50	0	6.50	6.50	6.50	6.50	1,512,734	9,832,771.00
CUTIX	2.12	0	2.12	2.12	0.00	0.00	488,492	1,019,762.94
CWG	0.99	0	0.99	0.99	0.00	0.00	100	99.00
DANGCEM	245.00	0	245.00	245.00	0.00	0.00	27,406	6,730,562.50
DANGSUGAR	16.40	0.4	16.00	16.00	16.40	16.00	3,195,964	51,191,710.65
DEAPCAP	0.20	0	0.20	0.20	0.00	0.00	200	40.00
ELLAHLAKES	3.60	0	3.60	3.60	0.00	0.00	20,630	81,694.80
ETERNA	6.05	0	6.05	6.05	0.00	0.00	5,224	31,919.76
ETI	11.00	0.2	10.80	10.80	11.00	11.00	8,039,015	88,432,848.60
ETRANZACT	2.50	0	2.50	2.50	0.00	0.00	38,665	106,078.75
FBNH	11.15	0.25	10.90	10.90	11.15	10.85	22,425,620	244,668,800.10
FCMB	3.05	-0.02	3.07	3.07	3.07	3.04	2,570,334	7,856,596.12
FIDELITYBK	3.19	0.15	3.04	3.10	3.20	3.10	20,166,210	63,769,516.97
FIDSON	9.40	0.2	9.20	9.20	9.40	9.40	865,839	8,207,172.01
FLOURMILL	27.30	0	27.30	27.30	0.00	0.00	266,851	7,545,396.90
FTNCOCOA	0.30	0	0.30	0.30	0.00	0.00	69,680	20,434.00
GLAXOSMITH	6.00	0	6.00	6.00	0.00	0.00	269,366	1,562,015.45
GTCO	19.85	0	19.85	19.85	19.90	19.80	5,545,544	110,129,328.05
GUINNESS	87.90	7.9	80.00	80.00	87.90	87.90	973,667	80,805,030.70
HONYFLOUR	2.65	-0.05	2.70	2.70	2.70	2.65	809,005	2,173,408.10

Security	Price	Change	PClose	Open	High	Low	Volume	Value
IKEJAHOTEL	1.20	0	1.20	1.20	0.00	0.00	1,200	1,332.00
IMG	7.45	0	7.45	7.45	0.00	0.00	16,908	130,362.20
INTBREW	5.00	0	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	758,197	3,800,193.05
JAIZBANK	0.86	-0.04	0.90	0.90	0.86	0.86	814,938	701,747.26
JAPAUFGOLD	0.33	0	0.33	0.33	0.33	0.33	325,439	105,220.96
JBERGER	25.90	0	25.90	25.90	0.00	0.00	136,441	3,584,190.70
JOHNHOLT	0.81	0	0.81	0.81	0.00	0.00	500	400.00
LASACO	1.03	0.05	0.98	0.98	1.03	0.95	1,196,717	1,167,803.91
LEARNAFRCA	2.47	0	2.47	2.47	0.00	0.00	35,349	85,280.91
LINKASSURE	0.52	0	0.52	0.52	0.00	0.00	12,000	5,760.00
LIVESTOCK	1.24	0	1.24	1.24	0.00	0.00	242,579	302,620.80
MANSARD	1.80	0	1.80	1.80	0.00	0.00	120,726	217,335.84
MAYBAKER	3.88	0	3.88	3.88	0.00	0.00	272,787	963,293.71
MBENEFIT	0.32	0	0.32	0.32	0.33	0.32	19,193,970	6,147,152.22
MCNICHOLS	0.74	0	0.74	0.74	0.00	0.00	300,000	201,084.93
MEYER	2.27	0	2.27	2.27	0.00	0.00	6,600	13,530.00
MORISON	2.19	0	2.19	2.19	0.00	0.00	600	1,260.00
MRS	14.35	0	14.35	14.35	0.00	0.00	439	5,769.45
MTNN	199.00	0	199.00	199.00	199.80	199.00	4,371,649	873,285,981.00
MULTIVERSE	2.62	0	2.62	2.62	0.00	0.00	40,791	100,555.70
NAHCO	5.70	0	5.70	5.70	5.70	5.70	527,789	3,016,911.85
NASCON	11.00	0	11.00	11.00	0.00	0.00	140,964	1,564,316.90
NB	45.50	-0.3	45.80	45.80	45.50	43.10	801,382	35,373,339.75
NCR	3.60	0	3.60	3.60	0.00	0.00	20,000	70,831.73
NEIMETH	1.56	-0.01	1.57	1.57	1.56	1.56	251,558	392,819.02
NEM	5.00	0	5.00	5.00	5.25	5.00	1,083,480	5,586,535.29
NESTLE	1,350.00	0	1,350.00	1,350.00	0.00	0.00	29,741	40,184,760.00
NGXGROUP	22.35	1.35	21.00	21.00	22.35	21.60	2,275,514	49,808,151.70
NPFMCRFBK	1.54	0	1.54	1.54	1.54	1.54	155,150	239,031.00
OANDO	5.10	0.05	5.05	5.05	5.10	4.81	2,913,486	14,542,650.14
OKOMUOIL	188.30	0	188.30	188.30	0.00	0.00	94,927	16,184,008.70
PHARMDEKO	1.75	0	1.75	1.75	0.00	0.00	149,500	252,670.00
PRESCO	142.60	0	142.60	142.60	0.00	0.00	111,232	14,522,255.10
PZ	8.20	0.15	8.05	8.05	8.20	8.20	447,028	3,670,483.70
REDSTAREX	2.70	0	2.70	2.70	0.00	0.00	48,040	129,331.00

Security	Price	Change	PClose	Open	High	Low	Volume	Value
REGALINS	0.26	0	0.26	0.26	0.26	0.26	275,000	71,500.00
RTBRISCOE	0.35	0	0.35	0.35	0.00	0.00	91,100	29,152.00
SEPLAT	1,300.00	0	1,300.00	1,300.00	0.00	0.00	39,230	50,764,874.30
SOVRENINS	0.26	-0.02	0.28	0.28	0.26	0.26	1,312,945	342,795.05
STANBIC	31.00	0	31.00	31.00	31.00	31.00	864,561	26,796,785.80
STERLNBANK	1.55	0.03	1.52	1.52	1.55	1.47	162,446,700	238,936,889.92
TOTAL	234.50	0	234.50	234.50	0.00	0.00	7,058	1,489,943.80
TRANSCORP	1.13	0.09	1.04	1.04	1.13	1.05	6,901,182	7,521,713.16
TRANSEXPR	0.69	0	0.69	0.69	0.00	0.00	100	75.00
TRIPPLEG	0.87	0	0.87	0.87	0.00	0.00	53,100	44,425.00
UACN	11.00	0	11.00	11.00	11.00	11.00	310,304	3,401,703.90
UBA	7.20	0	7.20	7.20	7.25	7.15	26,577,600	191,273,360.85
UBN	5.60	0	5.60	5.60	5.65	5.60	428,008	2,419,255.00

MANAGEMENT INFORMATION SYSTEMS AND EFFECTIVE BUSINESS DECISIONS: AN EVALUATION OF PENSION FUND ADMINISTRATORS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Research Purpose: Management Information Systems (MIS) is a strategic and critical tool that is required in taking decision at all levels in organizations. Pension industry is a critical sector that affects every adult who contributes to pension scheme. The study identified the important role of MIS in business decision of PFAs from onboarding of clients, contribution remittance, contribution processing, investment of contribution, and contribution alert to clients, handling of clients' complaints up to retirement process for RSA holders and analysis of various information for business decision making. Decision making process differentiates a company in the industry.

Design/Methodology/Approach: The methodology adopted was survey design that employed distribution of questionnaire to some senior officers of PFAs in Nigeria.

Findings: The findings revealed hypothesis one that calculated $Z=5.6 > \text{critical value}=1.96$ showing that MIS has a significant effect on decision process of PFAs; Hypothesis two showed that calculated $Z=7.2 > \text{critical value}=1.96$ revealing that MIS has significant effect on work delivery among PFAs in Nigeria; Hypothesis three revealed calculated $Z=2 > \text{critical value}=1.96$, MIS had a significant effect on collaborative efforts of all departments in an organization. Hypothesis four showed a calculated value $=2.4 > \text{critical value}=1.96$, MIS has a significant effect on decision quality in the decision-making process of PFAs in Nigeria.

Originality/Value Added: Some recommendations were made which included proper planning is very important in any information system; PFAs are encouraged to invest more in MIS for competitive edge; and MIS is yardstick through which decisions are made in organizations.

Keywords: Decision making, Management, Management Information Systems, National Pension Commission, Pension Fund Administrators

1.0 Introduction

Management information systems combine hardware, software, and network products in an integrated solution that provides managers with data in a format suitable for analysis, monitoring, decision-making and reporting (Adebisi, 2016). The system collects data (input), stores in a database (storage), processes it (processing) and produces output to users (output) over a secure network. According to Kumar and Sharma (2017), in order to define MIS, it must be principally divided into the three facets that constitute it which are: management, information, and systems. In furthering his ideas, Kumar simply defines management as the process through which managers plan, organize, initiate, and control operations within their businesses.

Kumar and Sharma (2017) further states that information generally refers to analyzed data. Kumar also mentioned that system refers to “A set of elements joined together for a common objective.” More often than not, business systems normally consist of smaller systems known as subsystems which all work towards ensuring effectiveness of the larger systems. It should be noted that no two organizations run the same system. In other words, information (with regards to business) results from data that is analyzed using business statutes, principles and theories advanced by various macroeconomists. Information systems have been most helpful to managers by providing support for their functions in disseminating information required for allocation of resources. However, information systems have not been fully accepted by informal sector which accounts for why most of their activities are still manually operated. Complexity in businesses had led to technological development across the globe.

The business requirement in our time has called for adoption of Management information system to provide information that will aid organizations in taking appropriate decision faster than before. Managers need rapid access to information to make decisions about strategic, financial, marketing and operational issues (Adebisi, 2016). The volume of information required these days by PFAs cannot be manually provided to meet up with the speed of actions required considering the number of clients handled by PFAs. Such information includes PIN generation from client registration, contribution processing, RSA statement generation, profit figures, financial ratios, forecasts, budgets and variance analysis, cost volume profit analysis, transfer pricing, divisional performance evaluation, make or buy decision, capital budgeting decision and sensitivity analysis, capital rationing, departmental or product viability and linear programming technique.

Pension Fund Administrators deal with high volume of information of their clients that manual operation could not handle. This accounted for the reason why the former body (NSITF) handling pension for Nigerian workers could not provide necessary information to its teeming clients due to manual operation they were using at that time. Nigerian workers were not properly serviced at that time before the introduction of contributory pension scheme regulated by the National Pension Commission (Pencom). The contribution made by workers could not be properly invested to provide returns to them. As at the time they asked NSITF to return contributors' fund, they were only asked to return principal contributions, no return was added, due to improper management of the fund and lack of effective management information system.

Pension helps former employees to acclimate themselves back into the society upon retirement (Fapohunda, 2013). A pension fund management information system is an automated tool that is used by organizations to manage, organize and evaluate pension funds and information as regards this area. It focuses on providing an organization with a tool that will aid their day-to-day activity by providing them with a computer-based tool that will be fully implemented to perform their specific tasks and functions to achieve client satisfaction.

Decision making is an important aspect of any business because any decision taken has an impact on its sustainability. Such decisions are based on the information provided to the management. In this technological era, there is no company that wants to make progress that will remain doing things in traditional way. Taking appropriate and right decisions will help a company achieve its objectives.

Therefore, most businesses are turning into the automated process of decision-making capabilities in order to ensure the reliability and suitability of the decisions with company goals (Aina, Hu & Mohammed, 2016).

Management information system is not limited to a section of an organization, it is a company wide information system that provides information about every aspect of the company (Accounting, Operations, Marketing, HR & Admin, ICT, etc). Companies collect vast amounts of information including customer records, contributions, investment, sales data, market research, financial records, manufacturing and inventory data and human resource records. However, much of that information is held in separate departmental databases, making it difficult for decision makers to access data quickly (Adebisi, 2016). At a glance the management can see the position of the company and which area they need to put their focus on. Management information systems are believed to foster the process of decision-making capabilities (Aina, Hu & Mohammed, 2016). This topic has been directed to some industries but not enough has been done in pension industry hence the interest of the researcher directed to this area.

Despite the oversight function by Pencom, some PFAs are still not able to take advantage of management information system to keep proper records and render appropriate returns to the Commission. They have necessary gadgets to provide the information but they are beset with one challenge or the other that prevents them from meeting up with Pencom periodic requirements. This shortcoming has led to administrative sanction imposed by Pencom on some erring PFAs. The contributory pension scheme (CPS) started in 2004 about sixteen years ago. There has not been sufficient coverage of this topic in this area. This has created gap in the body of knowledge that this study sets out to fill.

The general objective of this study is to evaluate the effect of management information system on business decisions of PFAs in Nigeria. The annual consolidated report of Pencom shows the importance of management information system on business decisions of PFAs, if any PFA fails to provide necessary information to the Commission, it will affect its performance in providing correct information to the public. Pencom consolidates information from various PFAs to take some decisions, the volume of information required from PFAs cannot be provided manually.

The complex information required in pension industry can only be handled by management information system. Based on information provided by PFAs and consolidated by Pencom, we can see total registrations, contributions, investment, branch network etc. Pencom has been able to supervise 22 PFAs effectively with the help of management information system technique. Management information system also provides clients with information to take a decision in the forthcoming transfer window. With the help of Management information system, clients receive contribution alert, RSA statement every quarter which was not achievable under old system.

2.0 Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

De Lone and McLean (1992) identified some factors influencing the success of Management information system on business decisions including decision making process, work turnaround, employees'

collaborative efforts and quality of information. Management information systems are said to have some advantages in relation to the support provided for enhancing business decisions. The main role of management information systems begins from the statement of the problem to which actions are based on. Mintzberg, Raisinghani, Theoret (1976) mentioned two important areas in problem definition phase. The first is known as “decision recognition” which is thought to start the process of decision making process by revealing relevant problems, threats and etc. As regards the second phase, known as “diagnosis”, is mainly concerned with the analysis and reviews of the previously defined problem and threat in “decision recognition” sphere. This is a crucial aspect of operation in management information systems.

The role of management information systems is vital in capturing and storing information for decision-making purposes. In this case, information may be obtained from different sources including internal and external. Therefore, available information is crucial for identifying problems and threats and further opportunities as well. To be more precise, the information may be defined and analyzed in relation to political, legal, economic, technological and social factors which are considered to be crucial in analyzing changing consumer behavior and market environment. Information is considered to play an important role in every organization. The use and application of information are significantly related to its value.

Most of the past researches showed a positive link between quality of information and firm success. Information is found to be important for making necessary decisions which may impact the company’s performance. Therefore, the role of the information can be regarded as the raw material for making a decision. The management information system is considered to be essential when there is a great deal of information available for managers to take decision. There are various definitions of Management Information System by some writers. Kenneth and Jane Laudon (2020); Dos Santos, Peffer and Mauer (1993), define Management information system as a planned system of collecting, processing, storing, disseminating data in the form of information needed to carry out the functions of management. Ngima and Kyongo, 2013; Weihrich and Koontz [2001] defined Management Information system as a functional system of gathering, comparing, analyzing, and dispersing internal and external information to the enterprise in a timely, effective, and efficient manner.

In the days when businesses recorded all transactions in a bound ledger, tallying and tracking what was going on, took a lot of time and work (manually). In the late 1800s, process automation began to appear in the form of punch cards. Associated machines tabulated the punch card data and printed results, which made it easier to capture transactions. The company that came to eventually be known as IBM was founded in the early 1900s and became the leader in business machines and punch cards. These cards evolved from a solution to automate pattern creation in weaving machines. The company adapted the idea to store and input data for applications from as simple as time for payroll to very complicated uses like recording census data. When general-purpose computers became available after WWII (originally developed for codebreaking, calculating shell trajectories, and other war-related needs), the punch card became an input method as well as a way to store outputs (though it required readers to decode and print the data so people could read it).

Later, magnetic media (such as tapes and floppy disks) took over the storage of input and output, and computers could read and write directly to their own memory. This eliminated the need for the specialized

machines. Next, optical media (like CDs and DVDs) that could store much more data on a single disc came along. Today, we are transitioning to flash memory (which also goes by solid state, as in a solid state drive or SSD). Flash memory has a higher capacity, is less volatile, and you can reuse it thousands of times with little degradation in quality.

Each of these periods has improved storage capacity at a lower cost. In relation with the increased speed in computing power, more powerful software, universal connectivity via wifi, mobile devices, and ever-expanding networking that advanced into the internet, work that used to take longer hours like preparing a company's payroll over a period or GDP increases in a country over a period now takes little time or human effort.

On the software side, the functions that paper ledgers performed was taken over by spreadsheet programs (the term spreadsheet came from the large sheets of paper spread out on tables). Microsoft Excel is the best-known example, but it wasn't the first to become popular. VisiCalc, which was created for the Apple II in the late 1970s by Dan Bricklin and Bob Frankston, was the first to gain popularity. There were spreadsheet programs available for mainframes and minicomputers before VisiCalc, but they didn't offer the ability to see results in real time.

Spreadsheets became more powerful in the '70s and '80s. They gave users the ability to easily and quickly access and manipulate data when connected with databases. As users' requirements changed, customized programs were developed for different user groups, allowing innovative ways to use data.

Information technology and MIS used to be synonymous. Task automation (such as report creation) led to an expansion of the work that fell under MIS. Simultaneously, the definition of IT expanded even more, and it now includes areas beyond MIS, such as cyber security and network administration.

Theoretical Framework

Some theoretical frameworks were reviewed to form basis for this study:

Attribution Theory

The word "attribution" literally means the grant of responsibility and tries to explain the behavior attributed to a person or situation. Heider (1958) advances the theory concerned with how people perceived the behavior of themselves and other people. Heider (1958) initiated the theory, later Weiner and colleagues (e.g., Jones et al., 1972; Weiner, 1974) developed a theoretical framework that has become a major research paradigm of social psychology. Heider divided the behavior attribute into internal and external factors. Internal attribution describes the behavior within a person and attributes like character, attitude, aptitude and personality. In the case of external attribution, the situation gets assigned to cause of a particular behavior e.g. the assignment of environment or weather to causality.

Weiner (1974) advances a three-stage process that underlies an attribution. (i) The person must perceive or observe the behavior. (ii) the person must believe that the behavior was intentionally performed, and (iii) the person must determine if they believe the other person was forced to perform the behavior (in

which case the cause is attributed to the situation) or not (in which case the cause is attributed to the other person). Weiner confined the theory on the most important factors affecting the attribution for achievement such as ability, effort, task difficulty, and luck. Omarli, 2017 inferred that a manager is the last decision maker in the process. When managers make decision, they have to consider the purpose of business, so it has a high impact on all the company's plans of activities and results.

Weiner also classified attribution along three causal dimensions: locus of control, stability, and controllability. The locus of control further differentiates into either internal or external. The stability dimension analyses whether there are changes over time attributed to causes. For example, we can have ability that is stable and internal; or an effort that is unstable and internal. Controllability is in reference to the causes one is able to control (e.g. skill/efficacy), and from causes one cannot control (e.g. aptitude, mood, other's actions, and luck) Ahmed, Bwisa, Otieno, & Karanja (2014).

Game Theory

It is a mathematical study of strategic decision making. It is considered to be an interactive decision theory as it takes into consideration the conflict and cooperation between intelligent rational decision makers. A lot of executives are today utilizing the science of game theory to help them make high risk/high reward strategic decisions in highly competitive markets and situations (Buchanan, 2006). Modern game theory has been around for over fifty years, and has demonstrated the ability to generate the ideal strategic choice in a variety of situations and problems.

Colleague-Role Approach to Executive Decision Making

Executive decision making in organizations, the making of decisions which has consequences for subsequent organizational activities. It is seldom done by individual members of the organization acting alone. People work together in project-teams or task-forces, coordinate their efforts with broader purposes of the organization and exchange support with their colleagues. Despite the obvious importance of such interactions between people in organizations in the process of making executive decisions, they have surprisingly received little direct study. Reference is usually made of the existence of "informal organization" and its importance, but they offer little insight (by way of making systematic statements) as to how these interactions work to aid decision making (Hammond, 2006).

Empirical Studies

The use and application of information are significantly related to its value. Most of the past researches show a positive link between quality of information and firm success. Information is found to be important for making a necessary decision which may impact future objectives of the company. Therefore, the role of the information can be regarded as the raw material for making a decision. The use of management information system is considered to be essential when there is a great deal of information available for managers.

Yadeta (2016) posits that management information system is an important part of the business organizations which provides timely and accurate information to the business managers and helps them in taking appropriate decisions.

Management information system can help managers to find a necessary solution for the given problems since problem identification and decision-making analysis is important to function of decision support systems (Mohammed A, and Hu, W, 2015; Ghazi A and Hu, W, 2015).

MIS provides accurate and timely information necessary to facilitate the decision-making process and enable the organizations planning, control, and operational functions to be carried out effectively. He further said that MIS also plays the crucial role of providing a wide range of streamlined options from which decision-makers are able to make their preferred choices and this ensures that whatever choices are made by decision makers, the outcome, more often than not, becomes positive (Sukru & Mohsen, 2015).

Nowduri (2011) in his study of Management Information Systems and business decision making: review, analysis, and recommendations said a good number of MIS used today can perform multiple tasks all at the same time. This potential to multitask increases efficiency in a company since several business operations can be conducted simultaneously. With special regards to decision making, the capacity to multitask ensures that decisions are made speedily when compared to those systems which can only handle one task at a time.

Rhodes (2010) also adds that: Management information systems give managers quick access to information. This can include interaction with other decision support systems, information inquiries, cross referencing of external information and potential data mining techniques. These systems can also compare strategic goals with practical decisions, giving managers a sense of how their decisions fit organizational strategy. In summary, Rhodes simply believes that management information systems are a huge contributing factor in the getting of viable information from organization.

Allen, Heurtebise, and Turnbull (2010) in their study said that by routinely programming a Management Information System, the business is bound to make positive progress since time and resources can be easily channeled into rightful business paths.

The positive relationship has been found between high quality of information and decision makers' satisfaction (Landrum, Prybutok, Strutton, & Zhang, 2008)). Another study by Wu and Wang (2006) provided evidence for supporting the positive relationship between information quality and user satisfaction.

Jahangir (2005) says that some MIS allow multiple users to access the same content all at the same time without any discrepancies. This potentiality boosts accountability from the business operators since multiple people can access a particular content and verify whether they are consistent or whether they are not. As a matter of fact, most organizations tend to suffer due to poor accountability from those charged with the mandate to manage certain details.

Marchland, Kettinger and Rollins (2003) mentioned the positive correlation between the management information system and speed of problem identification mentioning that role of MIS is significant in forecasting marketing trends, shifts, competition and changes in both internal and external environmental forces.

Management information system is reported to predict user satisfaction given high quality of information (Livari, 2005). Many studies also found a positive relationship between information quality and user satisfaction (Halawi et al, 2008).

H₀₁: The adoption of MIS does not significantly influence the decision making process in my organization.

H₀₂: The use of MIS does not significantly influence the speed of work delivery in my organization.

H₀₃: The use of MIS has no significant influence on collaborative efforts to achieve organizational objectives

H₀₄: The use of MIS has no significant influence on decision quality in the decision making process of PFAs

3.0 Methodology

Research Design and Sample Size

The study used a survey design to evaluate the impact of management information system on the business decision of PFAs in Nigeria. The design was adopted because of its appropriateness in describing the current situation of phenomenon (Kothari, 2004). The population of the study is the Pension Fund Administrators in Nigeria. Nwankwo (2011) stated that the population of any research work is the universe of such group; of people or object which a researcher is interested. In obtaining the sample size of the population, Senior Managers such as Investment Manager, Financial Controller, HR Manager, Head of Contributions Processing, Head of Benefits Payment and Head of Pension Service Centre from the 22 Pension Fund Administrators in Nigeria were selected through random sampling. A sample element of 132 respondents which also means 6 respondents from each selected PFA through a probabilistic sampling technique. The primary source of data collection was through the use of questionnaire, personal observation and interview.

Research Instrument and Technique

The data collected were presented in tables and analyzed using non-parametric simple percentages and Z – test statistical technique was used in order to confirm the stated hypotheses.

Research and Reliability of Research Instrument

The validity of an instrument refers to the extent to which it measures what was intended to measure. The validity of the scales utilized in this study was assessed for content and construct validity. After the survey had been completed the reliability of the scales was further examined by computing their coefficient alpha (Crombach Alpha). All scales were found to exceed a minimum threshold of 0.7 suggested by Nunnally (1978).

4.0 Result and Findings

In the course of this study 132 questionnaire were distributed to PFAs in order to critically evaluate the impact of MIS in their business decisions. A total of 125 questionnaire were returned out of which 110 were found to be valid and useful for this study. This represents 88% which is good enough, as it is reliable and generalizable.

The hypothesized statements were tested using the Z –test statistical tool as earlier stated. The tests conducted at 95% confidence interval and 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule was that if the calculated Z value is less than the critical value (1.96), we accept otherwise we reject null hypothesis.

The following were the results of the tested hypotheses:

H₀₁: The adoption of MIS does not significantly influence the decision making process in my organization.

As shown in Table 1 (Appendix I), the calculated $Z = 5.6$ is greater than the critical value $Z = 1.96$ i.e the null hypothesis is rejected. The result shows that MIS has a significant influence on the decision making process in PFAs. This is supported by the work of Mohammed A, and Hu, W, 2015; Ghazi A and Hu, W, 2015), they said that Management information system can help managers to find a necessary solution for the given problems since problem identification and decision-making analysis is important to function of decision support systems. Information is the basis of any decision making i.e without information made available there will be nothing to work with and base the decision on. PFAs deal with a lot of clients' information that form the basis for their decision on what steps to take on staff recruitment, investment placement, clients' registration, ICT equipment acquisition, addressing clients' complaints etc. In the annual routine examination carried out by Pencom on PFAs in 2019, the major issues identified were inadequate staffing, poor record keeping, lack of staff training, inadequate ICT facilities, and poor service delivery. It can be inferred that some of the PFAs are yet to fully imbibe MIS in all of their operations.

H₀₂: The use of MIS does not significantly influence the speed of work delivery in my organization.

As shown in Table 2 (Appendix I), the calculated $Z = 7.2$ is greater than the critical value $Z = 1.96$ i.e the null hypothesis is rejected. This informs that MIS has significant influence on the work delivery among PFAs in Nigeria. This is supported by Nowduri (2011) in his study of Management Information Systems and business decision making: review, analysis, and recommendations said a good number of MIS used today can perform multiple tasks all at the same time. This potential to multitask increases efficiency in a company since several business operations can be conducted simultaneously. With special regards to decision making, the capacity to multitask ensures that decisions are made speedily when compared to those systems which can only handle one task at a time. Returns provided to Pencom are from different departments with tight timelines. Various departments that provide information to Pencom are Contributions processing, Benefits Payment, Fund Account, Risk Management, Compliance etc.

It should be noted that PFAs are mandated to provide some returns to Pencom on daily, monthly, quarterly and annual basis and failure to do so attracts some administrative sanctions against any erring PFA as contained in the Framework for Regime of Sanctions and Penalties by Pencom.. This shows that an effective PFA needs to take business decision on investing in ICT equipment to deliver to Pencom as demanded. This return rendition is a key area and it requires MIS to deliver them on timely basis. The volume of data dealt with by PFAs is huge and large. Pencom in their third quarter 2019 report, said that "Licensed Pension Operators continued to render the returns for the Funds under their management/custody as well as that of the Company to the Commission via the Risk Management & Analysis System (RMAS) for the quarter ended 30 September, 2019". Pencom has been relating with PFAs with the help of Management information system. This has really singled out Pencom as an

outstanding regulator in Nigeria. As at 30th September, 2019, the total membership of RSA was 8,838,835; membership of Closed PFA (CPFA) was 17,548 while membership Approved existing scheme (AES) was 40,951. As at the same period, the total pension fund assets on unaudited valuation reports was N9.583 trillion. This analysis was made possible by Pencom through the help of MIS employed PFAs. No manual system could have been able to handle this volume of data for the contributions by the contributors. It should also be noted that the number of offices managed by PFAs could only be achieved with the help of MIS otherwise there would be unbearable delay in service delivery in pension industry. According to Pencom third quarter 2019 report the total contributions received from contributors from both the public and private sectors to date was N5.6 trillion. The use of MIS has really made it possible for PFAs to render this information for the use of Pencom. Pencom issued this report in November 2019.

H₀₃: The use of MIS has no significant influence on collaborative efforts to achieve organizational objectives.

As shown in Table 3 (Appendix I), the calculated $Z = 2$ is greater than the critical value $Z = 1.96$ i.e the null hypothesis is rejected. This informs that MIS has significant influence on collaborative efforts of all departments in an organization. It shows that no department can work in isolation. The current Enterprise resource program by many organizations today can be shared by as many as are connected to it to fetch information for their use. Same information may be required by different departments for certain decisions. Same information on number of staff may be required by Business development department and HR for different purposes and they can fetch it from the same source at the same time without waiting for each other. This is supported by the work of Jahangir (2005) who said that some MIS allow multiple users to access the same content all at the same time without any discrepancies. This potentiality boosts accountability from the business operators since multiple people can access a particular content and verify whether they are consistent or whether they are not. As a matter of fact, most organizations tend to suffer due to poor accountability from those charged with the mandate to manage certain details.

There is interconnectivity among departments working in PFAs through MIS. Without MIS, it would have been difficult to provide information required for certain decisions in the company. Pencom report provided through MIS is a valuable document through which PFAs share information to take some decisions. PFAs can determine their market share in the pension industry through this industry information from Pencom. Without MIS, it would not have possible to amass such information and provide an industry report within a very short time. This hypothesis is also supported by the work of Nowduri (2011) in his study of Management Information Systems and business decision making: review, analysis, and recommendations said a good number of MIS used today can perform multiple tasks all at the same time. This potential to multitask increases efficiency in a company since several business operations can be conducted simultaneously. With special regards to decision making, the capacity to multitask ensures that decisions are made speedily when compared to those systems which can only handle one task at a time.

H₀₄: The use of MIS has no significant influence on decision quality in the decision making process of PFAs.

As shown in Table 4 (Appendix I), the calculated $Z = 2.4$ is greater than the critical value $Z = 1.96$ i.e the null hypothesis is rejected. This informs that MIS has significant influence on decision quality in the decision making process of PFAs. This goes to show that every information is scrutinized properly before a final decision is arrived at. Any decision taken based on information provided has an implication for the company. The repercussion can be from clients' reaction or sanction from the regulator. At times reaction can come from employees through resignation or appointment. It is important to provide correct and

accurate information that will guide informed decision. Incorrect or inaccurate information will affect the decision quality of decision makers. This hypothesis is supported by Rhodes (2010) who added that: Management information systems give managers quick access to information. This can include interaction with other decision support systems, information inquiries, cross referencing of external information and potential data mining techniques. These systems can also compare strategic goals with practical decisions, giving managers a sense of how their decisions fit organizational strategy. In summary, Rhodes simply believes that management information systems are a huge contributing factor in the getting of viable information from organization.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Management Information systems play the crucial role of providing a wide range of streamlined options from which decision-makers are able to make their preferred choices (Vittal & Shivraj, 2008). Absolutely, this ensures that whatever choices are made by decision makers, the outcome, more often than not, becomes positive. This, as a matter of fact, is the reason why many decision makers tend to prefer using MIS tools when making tough business choices. It can be concluded that management information system is an important aspect of the business organizations which provides timely and accurate information to the business managers and helps them in taking appropriate decisions. With the change of technology management, new software is being used in information systems which leads to the fast and timely supply of the information. It should be noted that information systems have their challenges like implementation costs, power issue, cybersecurity issue, employees' sabotage and resistance to change, server crash problems and learning of new system problems, recruiting the right staff, and up-to-date information etc.

For the success of information system, it is recommended that proper planning is very important in any information system because without planning nothing is possible. Project harmony is necessary and uniformity in the organization is also required which corroborates collaborative efforts provided by this study.

Essentially, it is inherent to note that in spite of the fact that this paper is expressively analytical, more research needs to be done in order to bring more information into public domain as the industry is a nascent one with 22 PFAs, 4 Custodians and one regulator.

Moreover, the industry commenced transfer window in November 2020 which will pose intense competition among PFAs. Any PFA that is not strong in management information system may not be able to cope with the ensuing competition.

Business managers must learn to cope with the ever changing trends in MIS and decision making, without which it will be very challenging to make positive progress in decision making. More focus should be paid to MIS as it is the main tool for drawing information to take decisions in the organization.

PFAs use MIS to take decision on investment placement, branch set up, budgeting, business development and client registration, branding and handling of clients' complaints. MIS has improved the way business is carried out. MIS has become the yardstick through which customer satisfaction can be obtained and assessed. PFAs need to invest more in this area to deliver to their clients especially now that they are entering competition phase through transfer window that is about to open in the last quarter of 2020.

Finally, it is vital to remember that improvement in decision making is fundamentally meant to ensure customer satisfaction while businesses continue to flourish in success. All MIS strategies should therefore be tailored in a way that the above business goals are achieved. As an industry, some operations can be streamlined to reduce cost among PFAs just as ATM is being operated in banks. A depository can be

created where contribution operators can operate all contributions in the industry since they have PINs as the main identifier. Schedules are sent by different employers, these schedules contain date of payment, contribution month being paid for, the name of employer, staff names who are clients, PINs, the month being paid for, employee contribution, employer contribution, Additional voluntary contribution and total contribution, name of PFA, name of account officer. Further studies can be carried out on using MIS to take advantage of competition in the ensuing transfer window for PFAs. Pencom can collaborate with higher institutions to encourage more studies in researches to improve pension industry.

References

- Adebisi, A. A. (2016). The role of management information system and factors influencing strategic decision making processes in an organization. *Texila International Journal of Management*, 2(2), 1-8.
- Aina, A. A. M, Hu, W. & Mohammed, A. N A. M. (2016). Use of management information systems impact on decision support capabilities: A conceptual model. *Journal of International Business Research Mark*, 1(4), 27-31
- Allen, B., Heurtebise, A., & Turnbull, J. (2010). Improving Information Access. *Business Management US*. Retrieved October 2, 2010 from <http://www.busmanagement.com/article/Improving-information-access/>
- Bardhan I.R. & Whitaker, J.W. (2006). Information technology, production process outsourcing, and manufacturing plant performance. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 23(2), 13-40.
- Certo, S, C. (1997). *Modern Management, diversity, quality, ethics and the global environment*, 7th Ed, New Jersey, Prentice-Hall Inc.
- Dos Santos, B.L., Peffers, K., & Mauer, (1993). The impact of information technology investment announcements on the market value of the firm. *Information Systems Research*, 4(1), 1-29
- Fapohunda, T. M. (2013). The pension system and retirement planning in Nigeria. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*. 4(2), 1-10
- Ghazi, A & Hu, W. (2015). Impact of individual decision-making styles on marketing information system based decision-making. *International Journal of Innovation and Economic Development*, 1(2), 40-49
- Gordon, J. (1993). *A diagnostic approach to organizational behavior*, 4th Ed, New York, Prentice-Hall Inc, Englewood Cliffs, NJ.
- Gorry, G.A. & Michael, M.M.S. (1971). A framework for management information system. *Sloan Management Review*, 13(Fall), 55-70
- Gorry, A & Morton, S. M.A. (1971). A framework for management information systems. *Sloan Management Review*, 14, 55-70
- Halawi, A., Mccarthy, P. L., & Aronson, E. J. (2008). An Empirical Investigation of Knowledge Management System's Success. *Journal of Computer Information Systems*, 48 (2), 121-135
- Hammond, J. (2006). The Hidden Traps in Decision-Making. *Harvard Business Review*, January.
- Huber, G. P. (1980). *Managerial decision making*. Glenview, IL: Scott, Foresman and Co.

- Jahangir, K. (2005). Improving organizational best practice with information systems. Knowledge Management Review. Retrieved on October 15, 2021 from <http://www.findarticles.com/p/articles/mi>
- Jawadekar. (2006). Management information systems: Texts and cases. New York, NY: McGraw Hill. Kothari, 1990
- Kumar, V. & Sharma, R. R. K. (2017). Relatinf management problem solving strles of leadersto TQM focus: An empirical study. TQM Journal, 29(2_, 218-239
- Landrum, H. T., Prybutok, V. R., Strutton, D., & Zhang, X. (2008). Examining the Merits of usefulness versus use in an information service Quality and information system success Web-based Model. Information Resources Management Journal, 21 (2)
- Laudon, K & Laudon, J. (2020). Management information systems: Managing the Digital Firm. 16th Ed, Pearson
- Livari, J. (2005). An empirical test of the DeLoneMcLean model of information system success. ACM SIGMIS Database, 36 (2), 8-27.
- Marchland, D., Kettinger, J., & Rollins, D. (2003). Information orientation: people, technology, and the bottomline. Sloan Management Review, 41(4), 69-80
- Mintzberg, H. & Raisinghani, A. (1976). The structure of "unstructured" decision processes, Administrative Science Quarterly, (1976) 246-275.
- Mohammed A. & Hu, W. (2015) Using Management Information Systems (MIS) to Boost Corporate Performance International Journal of Management Science and Business Administration , 11(1), 55 – 61
- Ngima, W.M. & Kyongo, J. (2013). Contribution of motivational management to employee performance. International Journal of Humanities and Social Science. Vol 3(14), 219-239
- Nowduri, S. (2011). Management information systems and business decision making: review, analysis, and recommendations. Journal of Management and Marketing Research. Retrieved from: <http://www.aabri.com/manuscripts/1> on Oct. 22, 2020.
- Nwankwo, O.C. (2011). A Practical guide to Research Writing for students of research enterprise (revised fourth edition. PortHarcourt; Pam Unique Publishers,
- Nunnally, J. C. (1978). Psychometric theory (2nd Ed.). NewYork: McGraw-Hill.
- Omarli. (2017) Which Factors have an Impact on Managerial Decision-Making Process? An Integrated Framework. *Essays in Economics and Business Studies*, ISBN 978-80-89691 42-5
- Pension Reform Act, 2014. www.pencom.gov.ng
- Power, D. J. (2002). Decision support system: concepts and resources for managers. Westport Conn., Quorum Books.
- Raymond, M, Jr. (1990). Raymond, Information Systems. New York, Macmillan Publishing Company.

Rhodes, J. (2010): the role of Management information Systems in Decision- Making. eHow. Retrieved October 2, 2010 from <http://www.eHow.com/facts/7147006/role-information-systems-Decision-making.html>.

Simon, H. (1997). Administrative Behavior: A Study of Decision-Making Processes in Administrative Organizations, 4th Ed. The Free Press.

Sukru, A. & Mohsen, G. (2015). Decision making based on management information system and decision support system. International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management, 3(4)

Vittal, A and Shivraj, K. (2008): Role of Information Technology and Knowledge Management in improving project management.

Vitez, O. (2020). Characteristics of a good management information system. Retrieved from techwalla.com on Oct. 22m 2020

Wallick, D. W., Julieann, S., Christos, T., & Joanne, Y. (2012). The global case for strategic asset allocation. Valley Forge, Pa.: The Vanguard Group.

Weihrich, H. & Koontz, H. (2001). Management: A Global Perspective. 10th Edition. New Delhi: Tata McGraw-Hill Publishing Company Limited

Weiner, B. (1974). Achievement, motivation and attribution theory. Morristown, NJ: General Learning Press

Wu, J. & Wang, Y. (2006). Measuring KMS success: A re-specification of the DeLone and McLean's model. Information & Management, 43 (6), 728- 739

Yadeta, G.D. (2016). Role of management information system in business organizations. Proceedings of Academics World 18th International Conference, Boston, USA

Yusuf, M., Sanni, I.M. & Kazeem, A.O. (2014). The impact of management information system on the performance of business organization in Nigeria. International Journal of Humanities Social Sciences and Education (IJHSSE). Vol 1(2), 76-86.

APPENDIX I

H₀₁: The adoption of MIS does not significantly influence the decision making process in my organization.

Table 1

Factors	Frequency	%
I consider Management Information System important for my function	13	11.82
Everyone in my department operates computer for their daily activities	17	15.46
I am aware of Management Information System in my	10	9.09

organization		
Business decision making process is improved through Management information system	70	63.63
Total	110	100

From the table 1 above

$$P = 63.63 \quad 63.63\% = 0.64 \quad P_1 = 0.5 \quad N = 110$$

$$Z = \frac{0.64 - 0.5}{\sqrt{0.5(1-0.5)/110}} = 0.14/0.25/10$$

$$Z = 0.14/0.025 = 5.6$$

H₀₂: The use of MIS does not significantly influence the speed of work delivery in my organization.

Table 2

Factors	Frequency	%
I consider management information system much better and faster than the previous manual system being operated earlier.	75	68.18
All operations in my department are automated	10	9.09
Management information system makes it easier to take decision without physical meeting.	12	10.91
I do generate reports for management and board meeting through computer	13	11.82
Total	110	100

From the table 2 above

$$P = 68.18 \quad 68.18\% = 0.68 \quad P_1 = 0.5 \quad N = 100$$

$$Z = \frac{0.68 - 0.5}{\sqrt{0.5(1-0.5)/100}} = 0.18/0.25/10$$

$$Z = 0.18/0.025 = 7.2$$

H₀₃: The use of MIS has no significant influence on collaborative efforts to achieve organizational objectives

Table 3

Factors	Frequency	%
There is a dedicated and fully fledged ICT department in my organization	17	15.45
I consider Management	20	18.18

Information System important for my function		
There is effective collaboration among departments as a result of adoption of management information system	61	55.46
All operations in my department are automated	12	10.91
Total	110	100

From the table 3 above

$$P = 55.46 \quad 55.46\% = 0.55 \quad P_1 = 0.5 \quad N = 100$$

$$Z = 0.55 - 0.5 / 0.5(1-0.5) / \sqrt{100} = 0.05 / 0.25 / 10$$

$$Z = 0.05 / 0.025 = 2$$

H₀₄: The use of MIS has no significant influence on decision quality in the decision making process of PFAs.

Table 4

Factors	Frequency	%
Management information system assists in management function of planning, organizing, directing, staffing, budgeting and controlling.	62	56.36
I do generate reports for management and board meeting through computer	20	18.18
Our daily, monthly and quarterly returns are done though management information system to Pencom	15	13.64
I consider Management Information System important for business decision	13	11.82
Total	110	100

From the table 4 above

$$P = 56.36 \quad 56.36\% = 0.56 \quad P_1 = 0.5 \quad N = 100$$

$$Z = 0.56 - 0.5 / 0.5(1-0.5) / \sqrt{100} = 0.06 / 0.25 / 10$$

$$Z = 0.06 / 0.025 = 2.4$$

APPLICATION OF DIGITAL TOOLS FOR DESTINATION MARKETING OPTIMIZATION IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Research Purpose: The continuous increase in tourists' arrivals in different destinations and tourism contribution to the country's economy have influenced destinations competing to be the choice destination. Meanwhile, there are many factors that lead to tourism development and destination competitiveness. One of such factors is ICT readiness and use of digital tools to optimize destination marketing. Therefore, the aim of the study is to explore the effect of Nigeria's ICT readiness and digital optimization for destination marketing.

Design/Methodology/Approach: The study made use of secondary data from various publications of the World Bank, World Economic Forum and United Nations World Tourism Organisation and contents from the social media pages and websites of the Nigerian Tourism Development Corporation. The content analysis was applied to determine the effect of the digital tools for marketing optimization and tourists' engagements. Longitudinal analysis of the trend data was presented to examine the trends in the ICT readiness and effectiveness of marketing and branding to attract tourists from 2008-2019.

Findings: The results show that the country's ICT readiness was below average over the years and has negatively influenced the effectiveness of marketing and branding to attract tourists into the country. Actual and potential tourists should be able to have access to digital platforms of the choice destination to enable them plan and share tourism experiences. The results of this study hope to contribute literature in tourism destination marketing and management.

Keywords: Destination Marketing; ICT Readiness; Digital Optimization; Tourism Development.

Introduction

The tourism sector has been praised for its capacity to stimulate economic growth through job creations, and by attracting investments and fostering entrepreneurship, while also contributing, if properly harnessed, to preservation of ecosystems and biodiversity, protection of cultural heritage and promotion of empowerment of local communities [United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD), 2017]. It is a significant driver of economic and social development. It stimulates economic growth and development by generating income, employment, investment and exports. It also generates valuable spin-off benefits, including preservation of cultural heritage, improved infrastructure and local community facilities [World Travel & Travel Council (WTTC), 2013].

Tourism's potential has been recognized by policymakers at the national and international levels, and is increasingly reflected in national and international frameworks. At the global level, Sustainable Development Goals 8, 12 and 14 highlight the central role of tourism in job creation, local promotion of culture and economic development. However, as tourism covers several sectors and is a cross-cutting issue, the development of tourism has an impact on many Sustainable Development Goals, for example, poverty,

decent work, gender and infrastructure development (UNCTAD, 2017). Tourism benefits the country as a whole, as well as the local economy through its multiplier effects. These are some of the reasons why tourism has been variously advocated as a valued tool for driving development includes, a means of advancing wider international integration within areas such as the European Union (EU), or as a catalyst for modernization, economic development and prosperity in emerging nations especially in developing countries like Nigeria (Ajake, 2015).

The tourism potentials of Nigeria are very enormous and there is no gainsaying that if properly developed and promoted, will herald huge revenues into our country. Nigeria offers a wide variety of tourist attractions such as extended and roomy river and ocean beaches ideal for swimming and other water sports, unique wild life, vast tracts of unspoiled nature ranging from tropical forest, magnificent waterfalls, some new rapidly growing cities and climatic conditions in some parts particularly conducive for holidaying. Other attractions include traditional ways of life preserved in local customs, rich and varied handicrafts and other colorful products depicting or illustrative of native arts and lifestyle, and the authentic unsophisticated but friendly attitude of many in the Nigerian population (Aiyamenkhue, 2010). Meanwhile, in this smart tourism era, digital and mobile technologies are becoming inevitable in destination marketing and promotion as many destination marketing organisations use digital tools to promote tourism potentials of the destination to both potential and actual visitors. Besides, it enable tourists to conduct searches for potential destinations to visit, read reviews from those that visited already and also help the tourists to instantly share their memorable tourism experiences on social media during the timespan of a trip (Munar & Jacobsen, 2014). These memorable tourism experiences are selectively constructed, not least because they can be recalled after a trip (Zhang, Wu, & Buhalis, 2018). People enjoy sharing positive travel experiences throughout the pre-trip, during-trip, and post-trip stages (Jung & Cho, 2015), and the sharing behaviour of tourists brings changes to destinations and tourism businesses (Li, Hu, Huang, & Duan, 2016).

Nigeria is one of the destinations of the world with abundant tourism resources ranging from waterfalls, cultural festivals, and heritage, religious festivals, beaches, lakes, sporting events, etc. but has not been able to compete favourably with other destinations in Africa and the world in general. The country's inability to develop and promote her tourism resources to compete with other nations was described by WTTC Report of 2015 as a missed opportunity for economic growth and development. Despite the abundance of tourism resources and Government's effort in establishing Nigeria Tourism Development Corporation and State Tourism Boards to promote the tourism industry in Nigeria, the country's position among the competing nations is worrisome. The World Tourism Organization's master plan for tourism in Nigeria conducted in 2006, reported that marketing approach and activities towards tourism development are underfunded, inadequate and ineffective, the tourist products are not organized and well-packaged for the market place; Nigeria's tourist attractions are unknown to the international travel trade and the image of Nigeria abroad is very negative and not being addressed. In the same vein, Travel and Tourism Competitiveness Index (TTCI) of 2019 by World Economic Forum shows that Nigeria ranks 129th out of 140 countries surveyed. Besides, out of the 140 countries surveyed all over the world in the competitive index, Nigeria ranks 134th in effectiveness of marketing and branding to attract tourists and 128th in Information Communication Technology readiness, with an index of 2.9/7.0 (WEF, 2019). These show that Nigeria is not performing well in the area of destination marketing and the use of digital tools for destination marketing.

Meanwhile, since tourism development and marketing lead to national development, and many tourists now use digital tools to search for tourist destinations, tourism products, compare prices, trace locations, read reviews, plan trips and also share their experiences during the visit, it is vital for destination marketing organisations to adopt the application of digital tools in their marketing programmes in order to attract more

tourists and improve in their competitiveness. Therefore, it is on this background that this study is based to explore the application of digital tools for destination marketing optimization and destination competitiveness in Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature Conceptualization of Tourism

Tourism is a word that is so often used in everyday language. Surprisingly, there is no universally accepted definition of tourism rather there have been almost as many different definitions as there are researchers. It has been suggested that defining tourism is almost conceptually impossible. Complications are from the disciplinary nature of tourism research, the ambiguity of what constitutes a “tourism” and “tourism business” and overlaps with the concepts of travel, hospitality and leisure (Ispas 2014). The World Tourism Organization (WTO) defines tourism as “the activities of persons travelling to and staying in places outside their usual environment for not more than one consecutive year for leisure, business and other purposes not related to the exercises of an activity remunerated from within the place visited (WTO, 2004). It is a social, cultural and economic phenomenon which entails the movement of people to countries or places outside their usual environment for personal or business/professional purpose. These people are called visitors (which may be tourists or excursionists, residents or nonresidents) and tourism has to do with their activities, some of which imply tourism expenditure (WTO, 2014).

Modupe (1987) cited in Omole, Amodu, Olanubi and Emmanuel (2013) defines tourism as the temporary movement of people away from their usual place of abode to another location for relaxation and leisure purposes. Improvements in the transport system and the development of tourism centers have encouraged the movement of tourists to areas where opportunities for leisure, recreation and adventures are available. Omole, et al (2013) gave more reasons for such movement to include, the desire for the change and relaxation, the desire to treat them to a higher standard of comfort that they are normally accustomed to and the desire to participate in the promotion of business enterprises conferences, political meetings, religious and significant activities and interest born out of intellectual curiosity to see other cultures and physical attractions from which further knowledge could be acquired.

Tourism is widely acknowledged as an effective tool for socio-economic development, because of the positive backward and forward linkages with the rest sectors of the economy which allows it to facilitate employment opportunities, income, and economic development and enhance the quality of life (Ayeni & Ebohon, 2012). It also plays significant roles in alleviating the major political, social and economic problems that characterize the rural areas and help in developing the urban centers (Ojo, 2014). In the same view, Jiboku and Jiboku (2010) opined that tourism, if well-developed will enhance youth development, stern youth restiveness and foster unity and social cohesion among the numerous ethnic groups in Nigeria.

Tourism Destination and Destination Marketing

Various definitions of destinations are found in literature, which address destinations in a different manner. Buhalis (2000) defines destination as complex networks involving a large number of coproducing agencies supplying a wide range of products and services. He opines that destinations are an amalgamation of tourist products, offering consumers with an integrated experience. Similarly, Pike and Page (2014) describe a destination as an amalgam of a diverse and eclectic range of business and people who input have a vested interest in the prosperity of their destination. Okocha, et. al., (2021), opined that in an increasing globalized and competitive market for tourism, destination marketing is acknowledged as a pillar of the future growth and sustainability of tourism destination. Keyser (2009) as cited in Balkaran and Maharaj (2013) describes a destination as a defined spatial area made up of a mix of tourism resources, created facilities and support services and infrastructure, that are managed, marketed and consumed under a single brand identity..

Destination Marketing

According to UNWTO (cited in Pike & Page, 2014), Destination marketing is now acknowledged as a pillar of the future growth and sustainability of tourism destination in an increasing globalized and competitive market for tourists. Published research related to destination marketing represents an important growth area in tourism that has evolved for a distinct paradigm and its significance according to Pike & Page (2014) is reinforced by four key propositions that are associated with global tourism: first, most aspects of tourism take place at destinations. Second, the United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) proposed that destinations were “the fundamental unit of analysis in tourism”. Third, destinations have emerged as the biggest brands in the travel industry and lastly, a large number of nations, states and cities are now funding a Destination Marketing Organization (DMO) as the main vehicle to compete and attract visitors to their distinctive place or visitor space.

According to the UNWTO (2004), destination marketing “covers all the activities and processes to bring buyers and sellers together, focuses on responding to consumer demands and competitive positioning, is a continuous coordinated set of activities associated with efficient distribution of products to high potential markets; involves making decisions about the product, branding, the price, market segmentation, promotion and distribution. Kotler, Bowen and Makeus (2006) as cited in Agina et.al. (2017) opined “destination marketing as an integral part of developing and retaining a particular location’s popularity”. Destination Marketing is a proactive, strategic, visitor centered approach to the economic and cultural development of a location, which balances and integrates the interests of visitors, service providers, and the community (DMAI, 2009). It is also the process of communicating with potential visitors to influence their destinations preference, intention to travel and ultimately their final destination and product choices (Sustainable Tourism Organisation, 2014).

Destination Marketing Organisation (DMO)

A destination marketing organisation promotes a town, city, region or country in order to increase the number of visitors. It promotes the development and marketing of destination, focusing on convention sales, tourism marketing and services (Ford & Peeper, 2008). Ispas (2016) as cited in Okocha. et. al., (2021) sees destination marketing organisation “as any organization at any level, which is responsible for the marketing of identifiable destination. Such organization promotes economic development of a destination by increasing visits from tourists and business travelers, which generates overnight lodging for a destination, visits to restaurants and shopping revenues”. They are directly responsible for marketing the destination brand through travel and tourism “product awareness” to visitor. Destination Marketing Organisations produce billions of dollars in direct and indirect revenue and taxes for their destinations economies with their marketing and sales expertise (Destination Marketing Association International, 2009).

According to Ispas (2014), the core purpose of DMOs is enhancing sustained destination competitiveness. A major element in striving for competitive advantage in the crowded tourism markets is the development and implementation of tourism strategies, since destinations endowed with natural attractions have been forced into competition with places that have developed attractive built environments. To achieve competitiveness, the four main goals for DMOs are enhancing destination image, increasing industry profitability, reducing seasonally and ensuring long-term funding. The DMOs provides information along a destination lodging, attractions and events, museum, and culture, history and recreation, some even provide services, inside tips, blogs, photos, forum etc.

In Nigeria, organized tourism dates back to 1962 to project the country's tourism potential and encourage domestic and international tourism activities. The Nigeria Government appreciated the role and prospects of tourism by promulgating Decree 54 of 1976, which created the Nigeria Tourism Board and state Tourism Committee as government agencies charged with matters relating to Tourism development. These bodies in 1992, through Decree No. 81 were upgraded to Nigeria Tourism Development Corporation and State Tourism Boards. These agencies were expected to develop comprehensive Tourism programmes for both national and states, train staff for the sector, package tourism products in Nigeria and market them for both domestic and foreign consumption.

Effective destination marketing requires, among other factors, innovation, and creativity. More to that, the ability to connect with potential customers and their changing preferences is essential.

The destination marketing trends in the 2020s are as follows:

- a. **Focus on sustainability:** industrialization across the world has brought about development. Unfortunately, it has also resulted in the deterioration of the environment. Because of this, many travellers consider what is right for the planet in order to preserve the environment for future generations. This move to sustainability has quickly found its way into the travel industry. The sustainability travel report of 2019 points out that over 70% of travellers are of the opinion that travel companies should offer more sustainable travel choices. This emphasis on sustainability means a number of travellers are making decisions based on how eco-friendly a place is. Destination Marketing Organisations can, therefore, evaluate their success by being more green-minded. They should let the potential visitors see the actions they are taking to protect nature and secure the future of their region.
- b. **Increased use of virtual reality technology:** Destination Marketing Organisations can entice travellers to their destinations by giving them a taste of what they will experience using VR technology. And by having a virtual experience, the consumers are more likely to make a booking in order to experience the place in person.
- c. **Enhanced mobile experience:** According to Google report of 2018, the percentage of smartphone users who are comfortable researching, booking, and planning their trip to a new travel destination using only a mobile device keep increasing. According to the report, Germany (27%), France (44%), Australia (45%), U.K (43%), U.S (48%), South Korea (53%), Japan (59%), Brazil (67%), and India (87%). They also use mobile phones researching for hotels, airfares, and to seek directions. Therefore, it is crucial for destination marketers to optimize mobile experiences for their customers. It can build a strong competitive advantage.
- d. **More micro-influencer marketing:** Influencer marketing has proven to be quite effective in fact, data from Musfind reveals that 92% of consumers trust an influencer more than a traditional advertisement or a celebrity endorsement. Micro influencers marketing is deemed to be more authentic than using big-time influencers. These 'smaller' influencers tend to have more engagement with their audience and are also more relatable.
- e. **Consolidation of DMOs and Cross-Industry partnerships:** DMOs can no longer solely rely on governments to keep afloat because of declining financial support. This has resulted in destination marketers looking for other ways to fill that gap, hence an increase in consolidations and partnerships. Tourism organisations can also partner with companies and organisations in other industries that benefit from having more visitors coming to a particular location.

- f. **Preference for live stream videos:** according to Hubspot, about 54% of consumers want to see videos more than other types of content from brands in general. Videos are engaging and can result in higher conversions and more bookings.

Digital Marketing Tools

Travelers of all age groups increasingly use digital technologies to explore, research, confirm and ultimately share their travel experiences. Mobile technologies, in particular the smartphone and tablet devices revolutionize the way we access and consume information and intensifies the shift towards customer empowerment. Besides, the increasing proliferation of mobile technologies has a big impact on destination managers' strategic decisions. In particular the large variety of choices regarding mobile solutions (for example, apps, mobile sites, responsive designs, etc.). Meanwhile, social media has grown for DMOs into an established customer touch point. Majority of the DMOs consider social media either as the key ingredient of their strategy-mix, or at least as one of their main tools.

Social media has significantly changed the way people interact and communicate with each other (Ngai, Tao, & Moon, 2015). It is defined as a group of Internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0, and allow the creation and exchange of user generated content (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). There are studies conducted recently on social media influences in tourism marketing and development (Leung et al., 2013; Zeng & Gerritsen, 2014). These studies include the applications of social media for destination marketing (Hays, Page, & Buhalis, 2013) and tourism development (Usui, Wei, & Funck, 2017). They also cover the applications of social media by tourists, which include collecting planning information, sharing travel information, and interacting with others on social media platforms (Chan & Guillet, 2011; Zeng & Gerritsen, 2014).

Meanwhile, in order to minimise the risk of making faulty travel decisions, tourists use social media to search information when making travel plans in the pre-trip stage (Chung & Koo, 2015; Xiang & Gretzel, 2010). Tourists usually find information about different destinations based on electronic word-of-mouth communication (eWOM) on social media (Burgess, Sellitto, Cox, & Buultjens, 2011). They consider eWOM a credible source of information (Murphy, Benckendorff, & Moscardo, 2007) and believe eWOM from friends and family over and above all forms of advertising (Casaló, Flavián, & Guinalú, 2011; Litvin, Goldsmith, & Pan, 2008). Therefore, the credibility of shared experience on social media hugely influences future travel intentions and choices (Bae et al., 2017). These travel experiences are shared through many different media, including text, image, audio, and video (Thevenot, 2007). It would appear that tourists enjoy partaking of social interaction with friends on social media (Pan, MacLaurin, & Crotts, 2007) as well as generating insightful online reviews and recommendations to increase their utilitarian beliefs (Kim & Fesenmaier, 2015; Sotiriadis, 2017). Thus, the quality of tourists' experiences influence their sharing behaviour decisions (Bae et al., 2017).

The era of smart tourism involves smart technologies and mobile-based social media applications (e.g. WhatsApp and Facebook), combined with gradually easier and cheaper online access to smart destinations, enabling tourists to easily share their memorable experiences while on a trip.

Methodology

This study adopted the panel data qualitative and content analysis in obtaining analysis and interpreting data relating to the ICT readiness, Effectiveness of marketing and branding to attract tourists, and international tourist arrivals in Nigeria. Trend studies are concerned with the study of changes over time within some general population. The most important advantage of this form of study is that it permits companions of

data or observation over time within some general population. Other advantages include the generally better quality and enhanced comprehensiveness of data may usually be more accurate (Ezejelue et al., 2008). Therefore the data on ICT readiness, Effectiveness of marketing and branding to attract tourists, and International Tourist Arrivals from 2008-2019 were collected from World Bank, WTTC, UNWTO, and World Economic Forum.

Data Presentation and Analysis/Discussion

Data on the variables are presented and studied (2008-2019). The values of effectiveness of marketing and branding to attract tourists were compiled by the World Economic Forum in a 7-points Scale (I = Extremely Inefficient: 7 = extremely efficient), while ICT readiness were rated in the 7-point scale (I = very poor; 7 = Excellent).

Table I: ICT Readiness, Effectiveness of Marketing and Branding to attract Tourists, and International Tourist Arrivals for Nigeria from 2008-2019.

Years	ICT Readiness (1-7)	Effectiveness of Marketing & Branding (1-7)	International Tourist Arrivals
2019	2.9	2.4	1,889,000
2018	2.9	2.4	1,276, 000
2017	3.2	2.4	1,964,000
2016	3.4	2.4	1,889,000
2015	3.2	3.3	1,255,000
2014	2.8	4.3	854,000
2013	2.2	4.3	600,000
2012	2.2	4.0	486,000
2011	3.0	4.0	715,000
2010	3.0	3.3	1,555,000
2009	1.9	3.3	1,414,000
2008	1.8	3.1	1.313,000

Source: WEF & World Bank databases

Table 1 shows the performance of the variables from 2008 – 2019. From the table it reveals that the performance of Nigeria in ICT Readiness over the surveyed period was below the average of 3.5. Top performing countries in ICT Readiness in Africa are: Seychelles (5.0), Mauritius (4.9), and South Africa (4.6). These countries have utilized the available digital tools such as social media, mobile applications, websites, etc., to promote and communicate with actual and potential tourists to their destinations. Nigeria’s inability to effectively apply digital tools in destination marketing has resulted to ineffectiveness of marketing and branding to attract tourists to Nigeria as shown in Table 1. The lack of optimizing destination marketing through the use of digital tools has really affected the Nigeria’s marketing activities and has resulted to low and fluctuated international tourists’ arrivals.

From the content analysis, the websites and social media pages of Nigerian Tourism Development Corporation (NTDC), for example, the Facebook page ‘Tour Nigeria’ is updated frequently but lack engagement with the potential and actual tourists visiting Nigeria. The website of the Corporation is not also updated frequently with festivals with dates and tourist sites. This has made it difficult for tourists to

have much to talk about in terms of expectations. Observations from other countries in Africa with high index on ICT readiness such as Seychelles, Mauritius, and South Africa are not just using social media to engage with stakeholders in the industry, but have gone ahead to leverage mobile applications integrated with their websites in order to provide seamless interaction and experience for the tourists. Online communities are also created where tourists can share their traveling experiences.

Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations

The findings from this particular study have theoretical and practical implications. Theoretically, the study is the first study to apply content analysis in an exploratory study to examine the effect of digital optimization in destination marketing in Nigeria. The study also contributes to the body of knowledge in destination marketing and digital optimization by using qualitative data and content analysis to show the importance of using digital tools for destination marketing and tourists' engagement.

Practically, this results exposed the importance of adopting digital tools for destination marketing in Nigeria's tourism industry. Understanding this, enables the management of NTDC, State Tourism Boards, and other stakeholders in the tourism industry to plan their marketing programmes using digital tools for tourists engagement and promotion. As many destinations all over the world are developing and implementing post covid-19 recovery strategies, digital tools play important roles in destination marketing. The digital tools such as mobile applications, social media platforms, email, SOE tools, use of cookies, live streaming, etc. are being applied to get to the target markets. In using these tools, there is need for synergies and collaborative efforts by the industry stakeholders in designing and implementing the marketing strategies for better destination competitiveness. **References**

Aaker, D. A. (1991). *Managing brand equity: Capitalizing on the value of a brand name*. NY: The Free Press.

Adebayo, A. K., & Iweka, A. C. O. (2014). Optimizing the sustainability of tourism infrastructure in Nigeria through design for deconstruction framework. *American Journal of Tourism Management*, 3 (1). 13-19.

Adebayo, W.O., Jegede, A.O., & Eniafe, D.F. (2014). The economic impact of tourism development in Ile-Ife, Osun State, Nigeria. *Journal of Tourism, Hospitality and Sports*. 2, 28 – 33.

Adora, C.U. (2010). Managing tourism in Nigeria: The security option. *Management Science and Engineering*, 4(1), 14 – 25.

Agina E.K., Anyasor, O.M, Okocha, E.R., & Nwankwo N.L. (2017). Destination marketing and tourists' choice: a comparative study of Nigeria and selected African countries. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development*. Vol. 4(12): 178-186

Aiyamenkhue, E. (2010). *Tourism in Nigeria: Challenges and prospects*. Lecture delivered at the 6th Benin National Merit Award. 27th December.

Ajake, A.O. (2015). Influence of marketing strategies on Tourists' choice of destination area in Cross River State, Nigeria. *American Journal of Tourism Management*, 4(5) 61 – 76.

Ajake, A.O. & Amalu, T.E. (2012). The relevance of tourism on the economic development of Cross River State, Nigeria. *Journal of Geography and Regional planning*, 5(1), 14 – 20.

- Alexander, B. (2020). The top destination marketing trends in 2020. www.pro.regiondo.com/destinationmarketing
- Amalu, T.E. & Ajake, A.O. (2012). An assessment of the influence of Calabar Carnival on the economy of residents of Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State, Nigeria. *Global Journal of Human Social Sciences (13): Geography and Environmental Geosciences*, 12, (10). 65 – 75.
- Awodele, O.A. & Ayeni, D.A. (2011). Managing risks in tourism development projects: A case study of Nigeria. *Journal of Construction Project Management and Innovation 1* (2), 105 – 129.
- Ayeni, D. & Ebohon, O. (2013). Exploring sustainable tourism in Nigeria for developmental growth. *European Scientific Journal*, 8 (20) 126 – 140.
- Bae, S. J., Lee, H., Suh, E. K., & Suh, K. S. (2017). Shared experience in pretrip and experience sharing in posttrip: A survey of Airbnb users. *Information and Management*, 54(6), 714– 727.
- Baker, D., & Crompton, J. (2000). Quality, satisfaction and behavioural intentions. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 27. 785-804.
- Balkaran, R. & Maharaj, S. (2013). The Application of the theory of visitor attractions and its impact on the Competitive advantage of the Tourism Sector in Durban, South Africa. *Journal of Economics and Behavioural Studies*, 5, (8), 546 – 552.
- Barnhart, B. (2021). 20 must have digital marketing tools to help you grow. www.sproutsocial.com/insights/digital-marketing
- Bogan, E. (2014). Communication and promoting policy in tourism marketing. *International Journal of Academic Research in Environment and Geography 1* (1). 1-6.
- Bowen, J., Kotler P. & Markens J. (2006). *Marketing for hospitality & tourism*. Pearson: Prentice Hall.
- Buhalis, D. (2000). Marketing the competitive destination of the future. *Tourism Management*, 21, 97-116.
- Buhalis, D. (2013). Marketing the competitive destination of the future. *Tourism Management*, (special issue), 1-30.
- Buhalis, D., & Licata, M., (2002). The future e-tourism intermediaries. *Tourism Management* 23 (3), 207-220.
- Burgess, S., Sellitto, C., Cox, C., & Buultjens, J. (2011). Trust perceptions of online travel information by different content creators: Some social and legal implications. *Information Systems Frontiers*, 13(2), 221–235.
- Casaló, L. V., Flavián, C., & Guinalú, M. (2011). Understanding the intention to follow the advice obtained in an online travel community. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 27(2), 622–633.
- Chan, N. L., & Guillet, B. D. (2011). Investigation of social media marketing: How does the hotel Industry in Hong Kong perform in marketing on social media websites? *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 28(4), 345–368.

Chung, N., & Koo, C. (2015). The use of social media in travel information search. *Telematics and Informatics*, 32(2), 215–229.

Cirikovic, E. (2016). Marketing mix in tourism. Retrieved from www.unhz.eu on 20th May, 2016

Cooper, C., Fletcher, J., Fyall, A., Gilbert, D. & Wanhil, S. (2005). *Tourism: Principles and practice*. England: Prentice Hall.

Crouch, G.I. (2011). Destination competitiveness: An analysis of determinant attributes. *The Journal of Travel Research*, 30 (1), 27 – 45.

Dabphet, S. (2010). The key stakeholders in the implementation of sustainable tourism development in two rural towns of Thailand. Naresuan University, Thailand.

Digital Tourism Think Thank (2013). Cities in focus: A snapshot of digital destination marketing. www.thinkdigital.travel

DMAI (2009), *Destination marketing organizations*, USA: Destination Marketing Association International.

Dupeyras, A. & MacCallum, N. (2013). *Indicators for measuring competitiveness in tourism. A guidance document*. OECD Tourism Papers. OECD publishing.

Esu, B.B. & E. Ebitu (2010). Promoting an emerging tourism destination. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 10 (1), 21 – 28.

Esu, B.B. (2013). Strategies for harnessing investment opportunities through tourism in Nigeria. *Journal of Research in Hospitality, Tourism and Culture*, 1, (1), 1 –14.

Fofang, F. T. (2014). *Promotion and development of tourism in Cameroon*. Bachelor Thesis on Hospitality Management, Laurea University of Applied Sciences.

Hays, S., Page, S. J., & Buhalis, D. (2013). Social media as a destination marketing tool: Its use by national tourism organisation. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 16(3), 211–239.

Imikan, A. M., & Ekpo, K. J. (2012). Infrastructure and tourism development in Nigeria: The case of Rivers state. *International Journal of Economic Development and Investment*, 3(2), 53-60.

Ispas, A. (2016). The tourism destination marketing – a mandatory course for the students of tourism. *Universitatea Transilvania din Brasov, Facultatea de Stiinte Economice, Str. Colina Universitatii nr. 1*, ispasana@unithv.ro.

Jiboku, J.O. & Jiboku, K.A. (2010). Harnessing tourism potentials in Nigeria for national development. *Journal of Research in National Development*. 8, (1), 12-25.

Jovanovic, S., & Ilic, I. (2016). Infrastructure as important determinant in tourism development in the countries of South-East Europe. *Eco forum*, 5(8), 288-294.

- Jung, D., & Cho, M. H. (2015). A discovery of the positive travel experience in pre-trip, on-site and posttrip stage. In K. Griffin, & M. Joppe (Eds.), *Travel and tourism research Association: Advancing tourism research globally* (pp. 1–6). Whitehall, MI: Travel and Tourism Research Association.
- Kalodikis, G. & Yannakopoulos, P. (2003). ICT contribution in establishing a competitive advantage for the Greek tourism industry. Retrieved from www.ikaros.teipir.gr. Accessed May 15, 2017
- Kapiki, S. (2012). Current and future trends in tourism and hospitality. The case of Greece. *International Journal of Economic Practices and Theories* 2 (1), 1-12.
- Kaplan, A. M., & Haenlein, M. (2010). Users of the world, unite! The challenges and opportunities of social media. *Business Horizons*, 53(1), 59–68.
- Kim, H., Chen, M., & Jang, S. (2006). Tourism expansion and economic development: The case of Taiwan tourism management, 27, 925-933.
- Kim, J., & Fesenmaier, D. R. (2015). Sharing tourism experiences: The post-trip experience. *Journal of Travel Research*, 10(1),1–13.
- Kim, J., & Fesenmaier, D. R. (2015). Sharing tourism experiences: The post-trip experience. *Journal of Travel Research*, 10(1),1–13.
- Kotler, P., Haider, D., & Rein, I. (2001). *Marketing locurilor*, Bucuresti: Editura Teora
- Kracht, J., & Wang, Y. (2010). Examining the tourism distribution channel: evolution and transformation. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management* 22 (5), 736757.
- Krippendorf, J. (1987). *Marketing of tourism plans*. France: University of France Press.
- Law, R. (2009). Disintermediation of hotel reservations: the perception of different groups of online buyers in Hong Kong. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management* 21 (6), 766-772.
- Leung, D., Law, R., Van Hoof, H., & Buhalis, D. (2013). Social media in tourism and hospitality: A literature review. *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 30(1-2), 3–22.
- Li, Y., Hu, C., Huang, C., & Duan, L. (2016). The concept of smart tourism in the context of tourism information services. *Tourism Management*, 48, 293–300.
- Litvin, S. W., Goldsmith, R. E., & Pan, B. (2008). Electronic word-of-mouth in hospitality and tourism management. *Tourism Management*, 29(3), 458–468.
- Lopez, S.D.F. (2011). Destination image: Origins, developments and implications. *Revista de Turismo patrimonio cultural*, 9(2), 305-315.
- Lopez, T. B. (2015). *Destination marketing organization stakeholders and best practices*. General Human Environmental Services Undergraduate Honors Theses Paper 9.
- Manhas, P. S., Manrai, L. A., & Manrai, A. K., (2016). Role of tourist destination development in building its brand image: A conceptual model. *Journal of Economics, Finance and*

- Mihailovic, B. & I, Moric (2011). The Role of Marketing Philosophy in Rural Tourism Development. *Tourism and Hospitality Management*, 18, 267 – 281.
- Minazzi, R., & Mauri, A. G. (2015). *Mobile technologies effects on travel behaviours and experiences: A preliminary analysis*. In I. Tussyadiah, & A. Inversini (Eds.), *Information and communication technologies in tourism 2015* (pp. 507–522). Switzerland: Springer.
- Morrison, A.M. (2002) *Hospitality and Travel Marketing*. New York: Delmar Publishers.
- Munar, A. M., & Jacobsen, J. K. S. (2014). Motivations for sharing tourism experiences through social media. *Tourism Management*, 43, 46–54.
- Murphy, L., Benckendorff, P., & Moscardo, G. (2007). Destination brand personality: Visitor perceptions of a regional tourism destination. *Tourism Analysis*, 12(5-6), 419–432.
- O'Connor, P. (2010). Managing a hotel's image on TripAdvisor. *Journal of Hospitality Marketing & Management* 19 (7), 754-772.
- Okocha, R.E., Agina, E.K., & Ojiula, U.B. (2021). Influence of tourism marketing on destination competitiveness and economic development: exploring Nigeria and other African countries. *European Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Research* Vol.9 (4):19-28.
- Omole, F.K., Amodu, I.E., Olanibi, J.A. & Emmanuel, A.A. (2013). Marketing the tourist potentials in Ondo State, Nigeria for effective development. *Journal of Tourism, Hospitality and Sports*. 1, 63 – 71.
- Pan, B., MacLaurin, T., & Crotts, J. C. (2007). Travel blogs and the implications for destination marketing. *Journal of Travel Research*, 46(1), 35–45.
- Pike, S., & S. Page, (2014). Destination Marketing Organizations and Destination Marketing: A narrative analysis of the literature. *Tourism Management*, 41, 1 – 26.
- Popescu, I. V. (2004). The influence of brands on consumer behavior in selecting travel package. *International Journal of Economics Practices and Theories*, 4(5), 518-525.
- Popesku, J. (2011). *Menadzment turisticke destinacije*. Univerzitet Singidunum Beograd.
- Seaton A. V., & Benneth, M.M. (2004). *The marketing of tourism product: concepts, issues and cases*. Croatia: Zrinki.
- Shellenberg, (1968) *Marketing of tourism*, Madrid: Madrid Institute of Tourism Studies.
- Sotiriadis, M. D. (2017). Sharing tourism experiences in social media: A literature review and a set of suggested business strategies. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 29(1), 179–225.
- STO, (2014). Destination marketing. Retrieved from www.sustainabletourisonline.com on 15th October, 2014.
- Suli, D., Cani, I., & Suli, H. (2013). Communication of tourism product; the case of Himara. *European Journal of Sustainable Development*, 2 (4), 347-354

- Tanja, A., Vladimir, M., Nemanja, D., & Tamara, J. (2011). Integrated model of destination competitiveness. *Geographica Pannonica*, 15 (2), 58 – 69.
- Thevenot, G. (2007). Blogging as a social media. *Tourism and Hospitality Research*, 7(3-4), 287– 289.
- Tourism and transport forum (TTF). (2012). *Tourism infrastructure policy and priorities*, <http://www.hf.org.au/content/infprio201112.aspx>, accessed January 20, 2007.
- Tunde, A.M. (2012). Harnessing tourism potentials for sustainable development: A Case of Owu water falls in Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa*. 14, (1). 122 – 133.
- Usui, R., Wei, X., & Funck, C. (2017). The power of social media in regional tourism development: a case study from Ōkunoshima Island in Hiroshima, Japan. *Current Issues in Tourism, Inpress WEF (2015), Travel and tourism competitiveness Report 2015*. Geneva: World Economic Forum.
- WEF (2019), *Travel and tourism competitiveness Report 2017*. Geneva: World Economic Forum.
- WTM (2010), *Travel and tourism - Nigeria*. London: world travel market publications.
- WTO (2006), *Nigeria tourism development master plan: Institutional capacity strengthening to the tourism sector in Nigeria*. World Tourism Organization Publications.
- WTO (2014), *Understanding tourism: Basic glossary*, Madrid: UNWTO publications.
- WTTC, (2014), *Travel and tourism economic impact 2014: NIGERIA*. London: World Travel and Tourism Council Publications. Retrieved on 25th of Sept. 2014, from www.wttc.org.
- Xiang, Z., & Gretzel, U. (2010). Role of social media in online travel information search. *Tourism Management* 31, 179-188
- Xiang, Z., & Gretzel, U. (2010). Role of social media in online travel information search. *Tourism Management*, 31(2), 179–188.
- Xiang, Z., Wang, D., O’Leary, J. T., & Fesenmaier, D. R. (2015). Adapting to the Internet: Trends in travelers’ use of the web for trip planning. *Journal of Travel Research*, 54(4), 511–527.
- Zeng, B., & Gerritsen, R. (2014). What do we know about social media in tourism? A review. *Tourism Management Perspectives*, 10, 27–36.
- Zhang, H., Wu, Y., & Buhalis, D. (2018). A model of perceived image, memorable tourism experiences and revisit intention. *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*, 8, 326– 336.

ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION SKILLS AND JOB CREATION

Entrepreneurship Education Skills and Job Creation among Youths in Boosting Enugu

State, Nigerian Economy

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ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION SKILLS AND JOB CREATION

Abstract

Research Purpose: This study is to investigate the relationship between Entrepreneurship Education Skills and job creation among Youths in Boosting Enugu State Economy. To achieve the above objectives, two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study.

Design/Methodology/Approach: The population of the study is 170 business Education students in four universities offering Business Education in Enugu state during the 2021/2022 academic session. The entire population was studied because it was manageable. The instrument for data collection was a 10-item structured questionnaire developed by the researchers. The instrument was structured using a four-point rating scale and was face validated by an expert in computer/statistics Education Department in the Faculty of Education, Godfery Okoye University Enugu. An instrument titled Entrepreneurship Education to Job Creation among Youths Questionnaire (EEJCYQ) was used for data collection. Test-retest was utilized to determine the reliability of the instrument which gave a value of .87. The data analysis was based on responds from 150 copies of questionnaire out of 170 copies distributed which represent 88.24.9% return rate. ANOVA statistical tool was used to test the hypotheses at .05 level of significance.

Findings: The result of the findings revealed that a moderate positive relationship was found between entrepreneurship education and Job Creation among Youths in boosting Enugu State Economy. Also, it was found that the skills undergraduate students acquire after completing courses' bearing in mind entrepreneurship education significantly influences their job creation.

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Originality and Value Added: According to the findings and conclusions drawn, the following recommendations were made; the Vice Chancellors of the universities should ensure that course lecturers assigned to teach bring out the objectives and practical aspect of each course and this practical aspect of the study invariably is the entrepreneurship, this will enrich the curriculum of entrepreneurship education skills and make it broad-based, Teachers/Lecturers should be made to undergo series of workshop on entrepreneurship so as to know what to pass on to the students among others.

Keywords: Economy: Education; Entrepreneurship-Skills, Job-Creation, Youths

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Entrepreneurship Education Skills and Job Creation among Youths in Boosting Enugu State, Nigerian Economy

During the era of Covid-19 pandemic with its resultant eight months lockdown, a lot of people especially those serving in white color mans' job felt like they made a mistake in life by not learning any trade; and they started to think of what trade to learn to create job for themselves. However, this is doing the right think at the wrong time. A trade they would have learnt since at youthful age and must have grown and a mass wealth they now at fifties and sixties are beginning to learn a trade. Also, giving the deteriorating position of Nigeria's exchange rate to Dollar; caused by the continuous demand for foreign goods and services plus citizens traveling aboard to study and for their health issues; these supposedly increase our imports over our exports causing depletion which consequently leads to hyperinflation. This is as a result of low investment, little or no production or lockdown at post Covid -19 pandemic. Again, the way our curriculum is designed sets the youths to always pursue white collar job instead of looking inwards to seek for what they could do by themselves to be self-sufficient. Therefore, our youths from childhood have the notion that vocational duties are jobs for the less privileged.

Education is central in the development of any economy (Anam, Iba, and Aregbe, 2014). Stressing that, education is important to the development of human resources, impartation of appropriate skills, knowledge and attitude. The authors maintain that, development of educational sector is significant in developing other sectors of the economy and that development in any society is anchored primarily to education process. The authors assert that,

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educating individuals to be empowered with requisite skills and knowledge, to raise their output, income and wealth is *sin-qua-non* to creating job (gainful employment and reduction in unemployment level).

Further, the decline in the rate of entrepreneurship tends to increase the rate of unemployment. Thus, improvements in entrepreneurial activities lead countries towards poverty reduction, a decrease in unemployment, and fast economic development (Google, 2022). Therefore, Entrepreneurship education is the study of source of opportunities and process of discovery in which an individual endeavors ability of Creativity, risk taking and turn their ideas into action. Entrepreneurial enterprises provide citizens with paying jobs in order to operate and grow. Also, Entrepreneurial provide employees with the means to further grow one's own earning potential through training and on-the-job experience (Google, 2022). Youth means: the age range between being a child and an adult (Google, 2022).

SMEs (small and medium-sized enterprises) account for 60 to 70 per cent of jobs in most Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development Countries (OECD), with a large share in Italy and Japan, and a relatively smaller share in the United States. Smes also account for a disproportionately large share of new jobs, especially in those countries which have displayed a strong employment record, including the United States and the Netherlands. Some evidence points also to the importance of age, rather than size, in job creation: young firms generate more than their share of employment. However, less than one-half of start-ups survive for more than five years and only a fraction develop into the high-growth firms which make important contributions to job creation. High job turnover poses problems for employment

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security; and small establishments are often exempt from giving notice to their employees. Small firms also tend to invest less in training and rely relatively more on external recruitment for raising competence. The demand for reliable, relevant and internationally comparable data on SMEs is on the rise, and statistical offices have started to expand their collection and publication of data. International comparability is still weak, however, due to divergent size-class definitions and sector classifications. To enable useful policy analysis, OECD governments need to improve their build-up of data, without creating additional obstacles for firms through the burden of excessive paper work.

The Economy of Nigeria: The Economy of Nigeria is a middle-income, mixed economy and emerging market, with expanding manufacturing, financial, service, communications, technology, and entertainment sectors ([Wikipedia](#)). According to Google, (2021) Nigeria ranked as the 27th-largest economy in the world in terms of nominal GDP, and the 24th-largest in terms of purchasing power parity; [Imports](#): \$47.369 billion (2019); [Population](#): 217,680,954 (2022); [Unemployment](#): 32.1% (Q1 2021); [Currency](#): [Nigerian](#) naira (NGN, ₦) [Labour force](#): : 90,471,000 ([Q3 2018](#)); [Public debt](#): 23.3 of [GDP](#) (2022 est.); [Budget balance](#): \$5.2 billion; 1% of [GDP](#) (2014) Nigeria's economy grew by 3.6% in 2021 from a 1.8% contraction in 2020, underpinned on the supply side by 4.4% expansion in the non-oil sector against 8.3% contraction in the oil sector; non-oil growth was driven by agriculture (2.1%) and services (5.6%); Shuaibu, Umar and Aliyu, (2018) assert that Entrepreneurship education may not necessarily be focused on creating innovative entrepreneur but rather on initiative entrepreneur and can both be selective and adopt existing technologies in advanced countries and adopt it to local conditions.

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For example, initially, Japan was known to ‘imitate foreign technologies before becoming an industrial and technological Nation’. Majority of the entrepreneurship theories were constructed within the psychological or sociological perspectives.

The advent of entrepreneurship development has played significant role in provision of job creation both in developing and developed nations (Ehugbo, and Ugboko, 2021) The authors further outline the following capability of entrepreneurship: Create employments through introduction of new ventures, especially small businesses; Raise efficiency through different types of innovation; Facilitate exchange of technology or the acceptance of existing ones; Harness limited resource that may some way or another stay inactive and put them into profitable use; Stimulate development in those divisions which provides it with inputs.; Reinvigorate public and private enterprises, especially small scale businesses; Encourage and maintain economy dynamism that empowers an economy to modify freedom and status for themselves in the public arena.

Shuaibu, Umar, and Aliyu, (2018) State that, Nigerian economy is mono-cultural dependence on a single commodity-oil, while other sectors of the economy have been neglected since the discovery of oil, and the management of oil revenues has proven inefficacious in driving the economy to bring about the needed level of growth talk less of development. With serious negative implementation of the nation’s development, as good percentage of Nigerians still live in abject poverty and unemployment is on the increase in the country. In respect of the above, the paper seeks possible ways to diversify the productive base of the Nigerian economy. Therefore,

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the authors describe the importance of Entrepreneurship as a realistic mechanism for the diversification of Nigerian economic development. It discusses that entrepreneurship has been instrumental in the economic development and job creation in most of the developing economies, and education on entrepreneurship is one of the possible options for diversification of the Nigerian economy. The paper recommended that government should have interest and support entrepreneurship with finance, access to licenses / permits, taxes and to be included in the curriculum of studies from primary school to tertiary level. According to Khalil, Iorhemen and Sani, (2021) Entrepreneurship education plays a significant role in changing students' view towards becoming self-employed. This is because entrepreneurship education is meant to train students upon graduation to become self-reliant and employers of labour through creative and innovative thinking in identifying new business opportunities such as test prep coach, skills development center, online courses, employee training, online English teacher, among others., which transcends into job creation and boost the economy of Enugu State, Nigeria

Statement of the Problem: The era of Covid-19 pandemic made a lot of people felt like they made a mistake in life by not learning any trade; to create job for themselves. A trade they would have learnt at youthful age and must have grown and a mass wealth they now at fifties and sixties are beginning to learn a trade.

Again, the way our curriculum is designed sets the youths to always pursue white collar job instead of looking inwards to seek for what they could do by themselves to be self sufficient. Therefore, our youths from childhood have the notion that vocational duties are jobs for the less privileged. Thus, Entrepreneurship development Education Skills will favorably affect the

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economic development of Nigeria. To this effect, the present study focused on Entrepreneurship Education Skills and Job Creation among Youths in Boosting Enugu State Nigeria Economy.

Purpose of the Study: The general purpose of the study to is to investigate Entrepreneurship Education and Job Creation among Youths in Boosting Enugu State, Nigerian Economy. While the specific purpose are as follows:

1. To investigate the effect of Entrepreneurship Education skills continuity on job creations in Enugu State, Nigeria.
2. To ascertain the effect of youth commitment on job creations in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Hypotheses: The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

1. The Entrepreneurship Education skills continuity does not significantly affect job creations
2. Entrepreneurship Education skills does not significantly affect job creations

Review of Related Literature: Youth is understood as a period of transition from the dependence of childhood to adulthood's independence. The trend of globalization has introduced the spread and development of entrepreneurship especially among developing nations like Nigeria (Ehugbo, and Ugboko, 2021). The authors suggest that, no nation can survive without the activities of the entrepreneur. Nevertheless, the activities of an entrepreneur is as old as mankind, from the time of early man witnessed the skills and creativity to farm and rare livestock as a source of livelihood. The authors noted that, the concept of entrepreneurship has attracted national attention and recognition as a way of revolving and sustaining economic growth and stability of a nation. Therefore, knowledge of entrepreneurship allows people to assess and implement its creative skills for his personal and economic development of a nation.

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Khalil, Iorhemen and Sani, (2021) state that in tackling the global crisis of unemployment, policy makers and stakeholders in developed countries such as England, USA, and Germany, advocated a refocus of educational systems towards acquisition of skills especially for university graduates. Owing to this, the fact that education is important to the development of any society particularly because the goals of wealth creation, poverty reduction and value re-orientation can only be attained and sustained through an efficient educational system which impacts relevant skills, knowledge, capacities, attitudes and values into individuals.

Shuaibu, Umar, and Aliyu, (2018) opine that despite abundant natural and human resources, Nigeria faces some challenges. The authors assert that, up to the end of 1960's, the country was self-sufficient in food production and even a net exporter of Agricultural Produce. Since the early 1970's, as oil became a major foreign exchange earner and contributor to Gross Domestic Product (GDP), other sectors of the economy have been relegated to the background and stagnated, while crude revenues have not been managed effectively to stimulate desired growth levels and sustainable economic development.

Khalil, Iorhemen and Sani, (2021) examines Entrepreneurship Education as a Panacea for Job Creation and Sustainable Development in Nigeria. Human capital theory (HCT) and Risk taking theory (RTT) guided the study. Among other concern areas examined in this study include; literature review, concept of entrepreneurship, basic aspects of an entrepreneur, entrepreneurship education and job creation, brief history of entrepreneurship, benefits of Entrepreneurship for sustainable development, contribution of entrepreneur in development of Nigeria economy,

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challenges and possible solutions and conclusion was drawn. It was however, recommended that the government should give adequate attention to entrepreneurial development in the country through the provision of good economic environment to encourage individual participation in business while this is guaranteed entrepreneurship will thrive and consequently improve economic growth.

Empirical Review:

Ehugbo, and Ugboko, (2021) investigates the impact of entrepreneurship program on job creations in Nigeria; the study was carried out at Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria. The study employed Survey research. Cronbach Alpha method was used to determine the reliability at .075. The study involves 262 small business owners who accepted to be part of the sample population. Also, the selected business field includes; welders (60), tailors (75) and hair salon owners (127) within the city of Calabar, a structured Questionnaire was used as the major instrument in collection of data. Multistage Cluster random sampling was used to determine the sample size. Simple percentage and multiple regression analysis were used to test the hypotheses with the help of SPSS version 25. The results from hypotheses one and two reveals that there a significant and positive relationship between program transparency, program continuity and job creation while result from hypothesis three reveals a significant but negative relationship between youth commitment and job creations. The study therefore, recommended that the organizers of the programs should eliminate every form of bias in training and equipping the trained participants. Entrepreneurship programs should be design with a long term strategic plans so as to ensure

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sustainability and continuity of such programs. The entrepreneurship program should be design in a way that only person(s) that have passion, zeal and interest in such program should be selected.

Shuaibu, Umar, and Aliyu, (2018) maintain that, Nigerian economy is mono-cultural dependence on a single commodity-oil, while other sectors of the economy have been relegated or neglected since the discovery of oil, and the management of oil revenues has proven inefficacious in driving the economy to bring about the needed level of growth talk less of development. With serious negative implementation of the nation's development, as good percentage of Nigerians still live in abject poverty and unemployment is on the increase in the country. In respect of the above, the paper seeks possible ways to diversify the productive base of the Nigerian economy. It is revealed that considering Nigeria's peculiar circumstances and successes recorded before the advent of oil, for Nigeria to break loose from the problems inherent in a monotype-economy dominated by oil, which is subject to depletion, international price shocks and unfavourable quota arrangement, there is a need for diversification of Nigerian economy for National development. The paper, therefore, describes the importance of Entrepreneurship as a realistic mechanism for the diversification of Nigerian economic development. It discusses that entrepreneurship has been instrumental in the economic development and job creation in most of the developing economies, and training on entrepreneurship is one of the possible options for diversification of the Nigerian economy. The paper recommended that government should have

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interest and support entrepreneurship with finance, access to licenses / permits, taxes and to be included in the curriculum of studies from primary school to tertiary level.

Afolabi, kareem,. Okubanjo, ogunbanjo, Aninkan, (2017) opine that, Entrepreneurship education is introduced into Nigeria educational system to provide the necessary skills, competence, understanding, and prepare the Nigerian graduate for self-reliant, thereby contributing in nation building. The authors examined the effect of entrepreneurship education on self-employment initiatives among science and technology students of Gateway Polytechnic, Saapade Remo, Ogun State, Nigeria. Data obtained for analyses was obtained through self-administered questionnaires. In addition, simple percentage ranking, correlation and regression analysis techniques were used to analyze the questionnaires. The result indicates that entrepreneurship education is a good policy and it has positive effect on self-employment initiatives. Recommendations were that, students should be encouraged beyond entrepreneurship school training projects to business ventures start-ups at micro and small-levels. Also, the Polytechnic management should collaborate with existing entrepreneurs and business organizations in providing entrepreneurship training to the students among others. To help stimulate self-employment drives among graduates

In the words of Anam, Iba, and Aregbe, (2014) assert that, Entrepreneurship education is one of the keys to achieving employment creation and sustainable poverty reduction in Nigeria. It entails the philosophy of self-reliance. It creates a productive economic environment for small scale businesses to thrive. The development process of any country is determined by the way the production forces in and around the economy is organized. For most countries, the development

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of industry has depended a great deal on the role of the private sector. Entrepreneurship plays a major role in this regard. Entrepreneurial development, achieved through entrepreneurial education should be seen as a catalyst for private sector development in Nigeria. This study is therefore set to examine the impact of entrepreneurial education on productive employment and sustainable poverty reduction in Cross River State, with particular reference to the Central Bank of Nigeria Entrepreneurial Development Center in Calabar. Descriptive design was adopted to describe the phenomenon under study, gather and collate data for statistical analysis. The study relied on primary and secondary data. Primary data was obtained from a sample population of 60 respondents randomly selected among beneficiaries of the Central Bank of Nigeria Entrepreneurial Development Center (CBN-EDC), Calabar. Findings revealed that, there is a significant relationship between entrepreneurial education and job creation as well as poverty reduction in the state.

Theoretical Framework: Basically, entrepreneurship theories are rooted in multi-discipline perspective, which are Economic, Psychology, Sociology, Anthropology, and Management (Ehugbo, and Ugboko, 2021). This study was anchored on entrepreneurial management theories. However, the management entrepreneurial theories comprise of Opportunity-Based entrepreneurship theory and Resource-Based entrepreneurship theory. Maintaining that, the theory of Opportunity-Based theory was propounded by Peter Drucker and Howard Stevenson after given constructive criticisms about Economic theory of entrepreneurship in 1985 and 1990 respectively. Emphasizing that, Opportunity-Based theory gives an extensive theoretical structure for entrepreneurial research. The authors state that, Change does not actually caused by

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an entrepreneur as (claimed by Schumpeterian or Austrian school) but takes advantage of the identified opportunities that causes change (in process re-engineering, consumer preference, technology among others. Adding that his own presumption of who an entrepreneur is; as indicated an entrepreneur is an individual who consistently looks for change, reacts to it, and takes advantage of it as opportunity. While in Drucker's opportunity construct, entrepreneurs are more focused on the possibilities created by change than the problems. Stevenson and Harmeling (1990) broaden on Drucker's opportunity-based theory to incorporate resourcefulness; concluding that the core goal of entrepreneurial management is in their "quest to identify new opportunity regardless of resources presently controlled". This entails that an entrepreneur is more interested in efficient utilization of limited resource with regards to change in formal processes through which new opportunity are identified. Thus, Resource-Based Theory of entrepreneurship advocates that the ability of an entrepreneur to have access to resources is a significant predictor of opportunity-based entrepreneurial management and new business venture growth. This theory recognized the significant of financial availability, social connectivity and human resource in growing a new venture (Aldrich, 1999).

Methodology: This study adopted survey research design. The study was carried out in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study made use of 150 small business owners who accepted to be part of the population. The selected businesses field includes; fashion designers (50), poultry framers (43) and hair dressing salon owners (57) within Enugu metropolis. Questionnaire was utilized as instrument for data collection. All the population was utilized because the number is

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manageable. While Cronbach Alpha reliability method was utilized to determine the reliability of the instrument; hypotheses were tested with simple percentage and ANOVA were utilized to test the hypotheses.

DATA ANALYSIS

Table: Response rate

Questionnaire	Number	Percentage%
Questionnaire administered	150	100
Questionnaire returned	150	100

Field Survey, 2021

Table above shows that 150 copies of questionnaire were administered on respondents. The one hundred and thirty (150) questionnaire were returned (response rate of 150 copies were 100%). Therefore 150 questionnaires were used for the analysis.

Table: Cronbach alpha reliability of data

Cronbach Reliability and Correlation Test

Cronbach Alpha Number of Items .876 15

Cronbach's Alpha			
0.87615			
Cronbach's Alpha with missing item			
SD	D	SA	A
-0.70995	-2.06201	0.366482	0.898158

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Split-half	
Halves	0.894323
OddEven	-0.71227

Source: Microsoft excel toolkit 2007.

Source: SPSS 20.0 the table above examines the properties of measurement scales and the items that compose the scales. Ideally, the cronbach alpha coefficient should be about 0.7 (Pallant, 2001). The cronbach coefficient for the study performs very well with a value of .876 and this indicates that the scales and the items of the research instrument show a high measure of internal consistency (data is reliable).

Objective one: To investigate the effect of Entrepreneurship Education skills continuity on job creations among youths in Boosting Enugu State, Nigerian Economy

Objective 1

Anova: Single Factor

SUMMARY

<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>
Column 1	7	620	88.57143	147.619
Column 2	7	300	42.85714	223.8095
Column 3	7	65	9.285714	28.90476
Column 4	7	65	9.285714	28.90476

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ANOVA

<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Between Groups	29603.57	3	9867.857	91.95696	2.68E-13	3.008787
Within Groups	2575.429	24	107.3095			
Total	32179	27				

Remarks:

Reject H_0 if F - calculated is greater than or equal to F – critical value

$$F - \text{Cal} = 91.95696 \quad F - \text{tab} = 3.008787$$

Decisions: Since the calculated F is greater than the tabulated F , which is $91.95696 > = 3.008787$. We reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance; thus, Entrepreneurship Education skills create continuity on job creations among youths in Boosting Enugu State, Nigerian Economy

Objective two: To ascertain the effect of youth commitment on job creations

Anova: Single Factor

SUMMARY

<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>
Column 1	6	545	90.83333	84.16667
Column 2	6	225	37.5	217.5

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Column 3 6 80 13.33333 36.66667

Column 4 6 50 8.333333 6.666667

ANOVA

<i>Source</i>	<i>of</i>	<i>P-</i>				
<i>Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Between					3.51E-	
Groups	25675	3	8558.333	99.22705	12	3.098391
Within Groups	1725	20	86.25			
Total	27400	23				

Remarks:

Reject H_0^1 if F - calculated is greater than or equal to F – critical value

F – Cal = 99.22705 F – tab = 3.098391

Decisions: Since the calculated F is greater than the tabulated F , which is 99.22705 $> =$ 3.098391. We reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance; thus, Entrepreneurship Education youth commitment on job creations

Discussion

The Entrepreneurship Education skills continuity does not significantly affect job creations especially at this post covid-19 pandemic (H_0^1) since the calculated F is greater than the tabulated F , which is 99.22705 $> =$ 3.098391. The probability value is also greater than 95% confidence level. This implies that, Entrepreneurship Education skills on continuity affect job

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creations in Enugu State, Nigeria; to support the above, Adesanya, (2017) recommend that more universities should include entrepreneurship courses in their curricula and must ensure that all students regardless of their academic specialization study entrepreneurship. Also, Shuaibu, Umar, and Aliyu, (2018) recommend that government should have interest and support entrepreneurship with finance, access to licenses / permits, taxes and to be included in the curriculum of studies from primary school to tertiary level. Again, Ehugbo, and Ugboko, (2021) in their works agree in line with this work that, Entrepreneurship programs should be design with a long term strategic plans so as to ensure sustainability and continuity of such programs.

Again, Entrepreneurship Education skills on youth commitment does not significantly affect job creations towards self-reliance especially at this post covid-19 pandemic (H_0^2) however from our analysis calculated F is greater than the tabulated F, which is $99.22705 \geq 3.098391$. We reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance; thus, Entrepreneurship skills on youth commitment affect job creations in Enugu State, Nigeria. This is in line with the work of Ehugbo, and Ugboko, (2021) that, the advert of entrepreneurship development has played significant role in provision of job creation. The authors further outline the following capability of entrepreneurship as: Create employments through introduction of new ventures, especially small businesses; Raise efficiency through different types of innovation; Facilitate exchange of technology or the acceptance of existing ones; Harness limited resource that may some way or another stay inactive and put them into profitable use; Stimulate development in those divisions which provides it with inputs among others.

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Implications of the Study: For teachers/Lecturers to know what to teach, they should be made to undergo series of workshop on Entrepreneurship. Theories must be followed with practices.. Thereby, every teacher/Lecturer should bring out the practical aspect of their lessons, seriously supervise students closely as they perform these practical duties from school and award marks before they could be allowed to pass out. This practical aspect is what is today known as Entrepreneur.

Conclusion: From the summary responses all the respondents agree that Entrepreneurship education skills significantly affect Job Creation among Youths in Boosting Enugu State, Nigerian-Economy

Recommendations are that:

- 1, All teachers/Lecturers should be made to undergo series of workshop on entrepreneurship as to know what to pass on to the students.
- 2, Universities should organize exposure of students to local and international trade fairs, seminars, workshops and government funded exchange programs to industrialized nations where the culture of entrepreneurship is well established.
3. Vice Chancellors of the universities should ensure that course lecturers assigned to teach bring out the objectives and practical aspect of each course and this practical aspect of the study invariably is the entrepreneurship, this will enrich the curriculum of entrepreneurship education skills and make it broad-based,
4. Government should provide capital to help youths start up business

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5. NCCE, NBTE, NUC among others should stipulate guidelines on enforcing Entrepreneurship Education skills in every course of the university. No more much theories but every teacher/Lecturer should bring out the practical aspect of their lessons, seriously supervise students closely as they perform these duties from school and award marks before they could be allowed to pass out

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References

- Adesanya, (2017) Effect of Entrepreneurship Education outcomes on Entrepreneurship Behavior
<http://eprints.covenantuniversity.edu.ng/9745/1/ADESANYA%2C%20OLUWASEYI.pdf>
Retrieved, August, 2022
- Afolabi, M. O, Kareem, F. A. Okubanjo, I. O, Ogunbanjo, O, A. Aninkan, O. O. (2017) Effect of Entrepreneurship Education on Self-Employment Initiatives among Nigerian Science and Technology Students *Journal of Education and Practice* 8, (15), PP44-51
- Anam, B. Iba, J. A. and Aregbe, T. A, (2014) Entrepreneurship education, productive employment and sustainable poverty reduction in cross river state *international journal of advanced research in statistics, management and finance* 2 (1), pp 192-208
- Ehugbo, I. and Ugboko, L. N. (2021) [Entrepreneurship Development Programs and Job Creation in Calabar, Cross River State Nigeria](#) *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Analysis* 4 (8)
- Ehugbo, I. and, Ugboko, L. N. (2021) Entrepreneurship Development Programs and Job Creation in Calabar, Cross River State Nigeria *international journal of multidisciplinary research and analysis* 4 (8)
- Google (2022) 3-ways entrepreneurs improve economic development
<https://www.mancosa.co.za/blog/3-ways-entrepreneurs-improve-economic-development/1>

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Khalil Y. K., Iorhemen B. T. and Sani A. M. (2021) Entrepreneurship Education: A Panacea for Job Creation and Sustainable Development in Nigeria *International Journal of Innovative Research in Education, Technology & Social Strategies* 8, (1) pp 11-25

OECD, Small Businesses, Job Creation and Growth: Facts, Obstacles and Best Practices

Retrieved August, 2022

Ruth Oluwatoyosi Abioye, R. O. (2015) Exploring the Impact of Entrepreneurship Education Program on Current Graduate Entrepreneurs
<https://scholarworks.waldenu.edu/cgi/viewcontent>. Retrieved ,August, 2022.

Sawaya and Bhero, (2017) Effect of Simplified Licensing on Registration and Formalizing of Start-Ups in Mozambique *African Journal of Business Management* 12(17), pp. 542-554

Shuaibu, M, Umar, G. G. and Aliyu, M. J. (2018) Entrepreneurship Development for Diversification of Nigerian Economy *Journal of Economics, Management and Trade* 21(6): 1-11,

[Wikipedia](#), (2022)

Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development Countries (OECD).

LEADING SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS ADVISORY

Leading Sustainable Business Advisory

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Abstract:

Research Purpose: Sustainability is the lifeline of any organization which begins with its people. The pillars of sustainability be it economic, social, and environmental, have been linked to improved business performance when entrenched into long term strategies of a business. It is therefore imperative to develop solutions that will not compromise future needs yet meeting the needs of the present. A clear understanding of the trends of business environment (internal and external) and forces that shape competition; safe work initiatives; continuous learning; recycling recovery and re-use are strategies businesses can adopt to reduce environmental waste, social and economic issues which ultimately impede sustainability. For this purpose, this paper explores global sustainable business practices with the need to proffer leading sustainable business advisory to business managers and policy makers in Nigeria.

Recommendation: The study therefore recommends that Government must provide confidence, building strategies, reorient all security apparatus and take positive steps to reposition businesses in Nigeria with supportive and effective regulations. Government should also create friendly and enabling environment that would be conducive for both business organizations and investors to thrive to ensure sustainability and growth of the economy.

Keywords: Sustainability, Business Advisory, Sustainable Business

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Leading Sustainable Business Advisory

The world economies are battling with unprecedented economic challenges of various dimensions which has affected established businesses. The year 2020 witnessed a legacy of environmental and social challenges including climate emergency, covid-19, Black Lives Matter riots and so many other events which fundamentally emphasized sustainability as the biggest economic opportunity of our time. It is noted that, the goal of every business is to achieve sustainability and ensure that businesses don't run out of the resources needed to thrive (AL-Rahimy&Mugableh, 2019). Businesses are not just expected to make profit, but also to cooperate in such a way that resources are put into use judiciously in order to maximize returns on investment. The sole aim of every business is to continue to make profit in perpetuity while meeting the expectations of all stakeholders. Sustainability has been referred to as a development approach that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future (Bista, 2019). Companies around the world are faced with the critical challenge of complex tax system, frequent regulatory changes and demand for transparency from stakeholders. All these problems cannot be addressed by the current approach of valuing corporate success which does not recognise properly the total ability of the company to create value from the economic, social and environmental perspectives (Tahtinen, 2018; Sustainable Development Knowledge Platform, 2015).

For a business in times of economic crisis, it must be innovative, modern, and designed in such a way that offers something new, different, and better. For a business enterprise to succeed it is

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very sacrosanct for it to have a deep understanding of the factors that can lead to its sustainability. Business sustainability can be defined as a process of analysis and decision making across business functions, obtained through a committed and clear understanding of transitions that may occur in the present or the future. As sustainability is not easy to achieve, every company needs to adopt strategies to preserve resources for future generations and at the same time create value for the current generation (Klarin, 2018).

It is common to see that companies these days exaggerate their sustainability efforts to catch the attention of their target customers. This could also be the new beginning where companies are valuing environment sustainability. During the past few decades, an increasing number of companies have started publishing reports on sustainability-related activities. These reports mainly consist of sustainability, sustainable development, corporate social responsibility (CSR), environmental, social and governance (ESG) reports. Some reports also focus on social and corporate governance issues. The demand from the stakeholders for sustainability reports, is not only a regulatory requirement but has become a business culture to recon with (James, 2014).

Business historians have highlighted how businesses have driven economic growth since the Industrial Revolution. They have shown how large manufacturing companies, contributed to commercialization of new products and processes which embodied innovative technologies that critically impacted the world economy from the nineteenth century (Kammer & Christopherson, 2018; Medel-González, García-Ávila, & Hernández, 2019)

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Nigeria is the largest economy in Africa, home to thousands of businesses and investments from around the globe. The Nigerian businesses area subset of the international space with the economy being driven by agriculture, manufacturing, and service sectors. They need to fully awaken to the requirement for incorporation of sustainability ethics to business approach and processes which are gradually taking center stage in the itinerary of policy makers, market regulators, companies and stakeholders, the world over. Nigerian business environment is engulfed with many challenges which ranges from pollution and poor waste management, epileptic power supply, multiple taxation, infrastructural deficiency, inadequate foreign exchange allocation and host of others. Despite these challenges, businesses in Nigeria need to co-create with other stakeholders and integrate economic, social, environmental and governance considerations in their annual strategic plans.

2.0 Literature Review

Sustainability

Sustainability is a broad concept that includes various economic, environmental and social dimensions. It has appeared as an important tool to evaluate consumer products (Pelenc, Ballet, & Dedeurwaerdere, 2015). The concept of sustainability was first used in the field of forestry, where it means, never cutting trees more than actual time that required for the tree to grow. Sustainability is meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. It is an approach to creating true and real value to systems (Iheanachor, 2021). The term sustainability literally means a capacity to maintain some entity,

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outcome, or process over time and carrying out activities that do not exhaust the resources on which that capacity depends (Anthony, 2018; Sustainability in the Nigerian business environment (2020)).

Globally, organizations are under pressure to follow the path of sustainable development as a result of the need to meet today's needs without compromising the future needs. In response to this, stakeholders in the business and investment communities are expected to include sustainability report in their annual reports to enhance the quality of decision making by the users. The reporting of financial information without sustainability reporting of the organization is not sufficient (Delmas & Bubano, 2011). Sustainability reporting has started gaining attraction from public and private companies. There are several standard-setting bodies, various reporting, and verification initiatives. It summarizes the current status of sustainability standards, how companies reflect those standards on their sustainability report and the challenges. Five staged process of sustainability has been pinned out as compliance, sustainable value chain, design of sustainable goods and services, development of new business model and creation of next-practice platforms (Nidumolu, Pralahad & Rangaswami, 2009).

Sustainability is the ability of a system to maintain a well-defined level of performance over time and if required, to enhance output without damaging the essential ecological integrity of the system (Pelenc, Ballet, & Dedeurwaerdere, 2015). In the same vein, sustainability means development efforts, aimed at protecting the health of a construct in a manner that that will not frustrate the ability of future generations to meet their needs (Kammer & Christopherson, 2018).

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The business historian Geoffrey Jones has recently shown, that sustainability should be understood as a concept that has been socially and politically constructed, also by business, and has reflected the interests and values of those entrepreneurs, social groups and organizations being involved. Taking this further, sustainability can be said to have diverse taxonomies which highlights the meaning of development and describes it as structural transformation to sustainable productivity. It is also identified as a process of targeted change, which includes goals and resources to achieve these goals (Anthony, 2018).

Harvard Business School lists two categories of effects of sustainable business practices: the effect a business has on the environment, and the effect a business has on society, with the goal of sustainable practice being to have a positive impact on at least one of those areas. One critical issue emerged about how to measure sustainability, how to evaluate and claim that a business practice or a product is 'green' and what criteria that should be used to weigh such claims (United Nations Development Programme, 2015). Sustainability focuses on the long term, a concern for the future generations, leaving our people, business and planet better than it is today. The mission is crucial, but the task at hand is challenging given the complexity. Sustainability cannot happen in isolation and requires a coordinated approach from business owners, investors and government. Sustainability encompasses a triple bottom line which includes economic, social and environmental considerations.

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Sources: Scientific Research on the Magazine Green

The three pillars of sustainability were first introduced by John Elkington, the founder of sustainability strategy consultancy and a writer of different significant books on the corporate environment. His concept on three pillars of sustainability is to give ideas on how the business does not have just one single objective which is maximizing profit but also, should have an extended goal set of adding to environment and social values. (Crane & Matten, 2010). The three pillars of sustainability consist of Social, Environmental, and Economic Factors. Citizens, big companies and governments are responsible for sustaining these three factors in such a way that future generations will have the ability to utilize resources.

Sustainable business practices in Nigerian

Countries have experienced rapid shift in urban growth globally, increased economic and technological development in the years past; increasing industrial development coupled with

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various forms of contamination of the physical and biological components of the earth. Nigeria accounts for more than 150,000 metric tons of plastic bottles annually, half of it from the megacity of Lagos (The Monitor, 2019). In Nigeria, many industrialized cities still have inadequate waste management; poorly controlled open dumps and illegal roadside dumping remain a problem. These are environmental issues that destroy scenic resources, pollute soil and hydro resources and habitation. Nigeria generates more than 32 million tons of solid waste annually, out of which only 20–30% is collected (Nnadiukwu, 2019). Businesses have adopted sustainable practices for effective waste management. Sustainable practices and techniques embraced are total quality management, recycling, bio treatment, incinerations, neutralization and secure sanitary landfill (Price, 2008). Total quality management like continuous improvement and the zero-defect call are apt solutions and guides to effective waste management. This method guarantees waste eradication, high quality products and increased profitability hence is a sustainable practice for companies. Bottling companies, for example use technological facilities with high efficiencies that are automated to reduce and process waste generation. Lagos, as Nigeria's industrial and densely populated city has numerous dumpsites. With a long value chain that is highly valuable ranging from the scavenger to the middlemen who sell or are representatives of companies, recycling is a sustainable method of managing waste and reducing its impact on the environment. Waste recycling saves raw materials, costs less, generates cash, creates jobs, and sustainable living. Ogundipe, (2018) revealed that land filling as the most common method of waste disposal, which is closely trailed by reuse as backfill and recycling. Land filling is a sustainable practice. Large corporations adopt incineration, burying, and flaring,

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while small companies adopt reuse as backfill, land filling, open dumping, and recycling. An industry leader in carbonated drinks industry adopts 3Rs –reduce, recovery, reuse, increasing the use of recycled content and implementing light-weighting techniques.

Business advisory

In both challenging and favourable economic conditions, businesses need to strive to be smart, nimble, creative and forward thinking. It is important to provide deep technical knowledge and extensive industry experience to assist clients in addressing business issues that goes beyond providing traditional audit services. Advisory services should be obtained in order to bring more focus to value proposition and competencies in the areas of finance function resourcing and outsourcing, accounting advisory services, liaison service, regulatory compliance and advisory and risk management and controls capability and many more.

Business advisory involves reporting on performance as well as advising on strategic plans, risk assessment and succession plans. It involves a wide range of services provided by accounting and professional services network firms for small, mid-sized and large businesses which can range from start-ups, SMEs and family owned businesses to large private and public organizations.

Taking a sustainable approach to business means that your business has no negative impact on the environment or society, while remaining financially sound. It encourages us to focus on long

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term goals and strategy and offers a wide range of benefits. Some key advantages of engaging a sustainable business advisory are cost savings, improved reputation, increase employee retention and recruitment and management of environmental impacts among others.

2.2 Theoretical Review

Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder Theory is a theory of management that concerns itself with matters related to morals and ethics in running a *business*. Stakeholder theory suggests that a *business* must seek to maximize value for its stakeholders. It emphasizes the interconnections between *business* and all those who have a stake in it, namely customers, employees, suppliers, investors, people and the communities. *Business* is to serve the [needs](#) of the stakeholders, and not just the shareholders. Stakeholder theory is a theory of organizational management and business ethics that addresses morals and values in managing an organization. It was originally detailed by R. Edward Freeman in the book *Strategic Management: Stakeholder theory* argues that there are other parties involved, including employees, customers, suppliers, financiers, communities, governmental bodies, political groups, trade associations, and trade unions. Even competitors are sometimes counted as stakeholders - their status being derived from their capacity to affect the firm and its stakeholders. The nature of what is a stakeholder is highly contested, with hundreds of definitions existing in the academic literature. The stakeholder view of strategy integrates both a

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resource-based view and a market-based view, and adding a socio-political level (United Nations Development Programme, 2015).

It is very important for firms to recognize that there are diverse stakeholders with different needs and reporting, and are expected to take into account the economic, social and environmental perspectives to sustainability reporting. Reporting on sustainability reduces the societal pressure, regulatory problem, internal and external agitation for financial and non-financial benefits (Sustainable Development Knowledge Platform, 2015). The shareholders' expectation is about profit, the people expect firms to conduct operations with minimal discomfort and environmental preservation which is also required to ensure business continuity. Sustainability reporting is expected to address the needs of the shareholders by delivering profit, the comfort of the people living around the location of the organization and minimizing the negative impact of its operations. There is also the need to preserve and maintain the environment, so as to be a regulators and people friendly business.

3.0 Methodology

The methodology includes a literature review focusing on sustainability business advisory in the area of assurance services and sustainable business practices in Nigerian. The paper reviewed the design research literature to understand the relationship between business advisory vis-à-vis business sustainability in the area of Assurance services.

4.0 Business Advisory in Assurance Services

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Objectivity, integrity, strong analytical skills, experience in measuring various subject matters against criteria, processes for testing the reliability of data, and clarity in reporting the results are critical elements in delivering assurance services. Assurance service has been identified as an independent service which is typically provided by the professional accountants, with the goal of improving [information](#) or the context of information so that decision makers can make more informed and presumably better decisions. Assurance services provide independent and professional opinions that reduce information risk (risk from incorrect information). According to Iriygbogbe (2021), the key considerations for sustainable business advisory include the followings:

Governance: In reporting and disclosure on economic, social and governance (ESG), governance plays the biggest role and it is the responsibility of those saddled with governance to set out the ESG plan and strategy. A good governance structure is required to implement and oversee the effectiveness of the overall ESG strategy in the business.

Internal Controls: For efficient and sustainability of a business, internal controls also plays a major role in an organization when reporting on ESG. This reporting can contain a wide variety of metrics and as such, organizations must establish rules, regulations, policies, processes or procedures and controls that generate reliable information for decision-making and ensure the quality of data being produced are reported accurately with facts.

The Role of Internal Audit: Internal auditing is an independent, objective assurance and consulting activity designed to add value and improve an organization's operations. It helps an organization accomplish its objectives by bringing a systematic, disciplined approach to evaluate

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and improve the effectiveness of risk management, control and governance processes. Internal audit is an independent and objective assurance and as such, its involvement in the ESG reporting process is a critical element that gives a reliable third-party assurance on the effectiveness of the ESG strategy. Internal Audit can help achieve a better sustainability report through performing the following functions:

Assurance: One of the major functions of the internal audit unit is to give an assurance on the effectiveness of the ESG reporting. Internal audit can review reporting metrics for relevance, accuracy, timeliness and consistency and ensure they are in line with the set out ESG strategy. It also gives a huge confidence to stakeholders that ESG information being reported are being reviewed by a competent third party.

Advisory: Internal Audit function can help management build a proper ESG reporting environment. They can recommend sustainability frameworks for management to manage ESG risks and can also recommend reporting metrics on what to report. Internal audit can also add value by assessing the feasibility and credibility of the company's ESG strategy and objectives and evaluating the quality of the ESG policies, procedures and controls.

Compliance: With sustainability reporting, regulations are being formed by different bodies. There is already the EU sustainable finance disclosure regulation (SFDR) and there are talks of the IFRS Foundation considering creating a board to establish standards for global sustainability reporting. In Nigeria for example, Part E of the code of corporate governance (2018) developed by the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN) talks on sustainability reporting. Internal audit function can help monitor compliance to new regulations. Therefore, professional in

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business advisory should improve their competencies and expertise to help organizations prevent and detect violation of regulations thereby avoiding negative ESG which may result in fines, negative or bad reputation and even law suits.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendation

Every company needs to adopt sustainability policies and procedures to preserve resources for future generations and at the same time create value for the current generation. To ensure sustainable business practices in Nigeria, business leaders need to develop processes and structures while, focusing on achieving the strategic goals of the business. Sustainability reporting is becoming a growing area which helps to maintain transparency about the risks and opportunities faced as business, alleviating negative ecological, social and governance impacts, thereby improving the reputation of the organization. Governments and regulators are also having increased interests in sustainability reporting and there could be emergence of new unified regulations very soon. The company is also expected to be proactive in adopting recycling methods and other eco – friendly practices in their day-to-day production.

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It is therefore recommended that experts and professional in the business field should build up competencies and strength in the area of sustainability principles and practices, and help global businesses grow and prosper in a sustainable manner. Government must provide confidence, building strategies, reorient all security apparatus and take positive steps to reposition businesses in Nigeria with supportive and effective regulations. Government should create friendly and enabling environment that would be conducive for both business organizations and investors to thrive in order to ensure sustainability and growth of the economy.

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References

- Allen, C., Metternicht, G., & Wiedmann, T. (2018). Initial progress in implementing the sustainable development goals (SDGs): A review of evidence from countries. *Journal of Sustainable Science*, 13(5), 1453–1467.
- Allen, C., Metternicht, G., & Wiedmann, T. (2019). Prioritising SDG targets: Assessing baselines, gaps and inter linkages. *Journal of Sustainable Science*, 14(22)421–438.
- AL-Rahimy, G., & Mugableh, J (2019). Integration of quality and innovation practices for global sustainability: An empirical study of Indian SMEs. *Global Business Review*, 18 (1), 210-225.
- Anekwe, R.I., Ndubusi-Okolo, P., & Uzoezie C. (2020). Sustainability in the Nigerian business environment: Problems and Prospects. *International Journal of Academic Management Science Research*, 3(3), 73-79.
- Anthony, R. (2018). Corporate sustainability towards a new index for environmental sustainability based on a daily weighting approach. *Sustainable Development*, 16(23), 251–260.
- Bista, S. (2019). Sustainability in business: A critique of environmental sustainability practices in coca-cola & unilever *unpublished Thesis*.

LEADING SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS ADVISORY

Crane, A., & Matten, D. (2010). Business ethics: Managing citizenship and sustainability in the age of globalization. Oxford: Oxford.

Delmas, M., & Burbano, V. (2011). The drivers of green washing. *California Management Review* 54(23), 64-87.

Deloitte (2018). State of the state <https://www2.deloitte.com/nl/nl/pages/data-analytics/topics/state-of-thestate.htm>

Get Smarter Business' (2019). Retrieved from [good business film](#). Accessed 16 November 2021.

Iheanachor, N. (2021). An assessment of foreign direct investment and sustainable development. *International Journal of Management, Economics and Social Sciences*, 10 (1),49-67.

Irivgbogbe, F. (2021). The benefits of sustainability and integrated reporting: An investigation of accounting majors' perceptions, *Journal of Accounting*, 17(2), 93-113.

James S. (2014). Meeting the sustainable development goals leads to lower world population growth. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 113(45), 14294-14299

Kammer, M., & Christopherson, S.E (2018). Reserving a place for nature on spaceship earth: rethinking the role of conservation easement. *Columbia Journal of Environmental Studies*, 43(1), 1-48.

LEADING SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS ADVISORY

Klarin (2018). The concept of sustainable development: From its begging contemporary issue.

Zagreb International Review of Economics & Business, 21(1), 67-94

Medel-González F., García-Ávila L., Hernández C. Springer; Berlin, H. (2019). Measuring and evaluating business sustainability. Development and application of corporate index of sustainability performance, *Journal of Sustainable Development*, 56(5), 33–61.

Nidumolu, R. Prahalad, C.K. & Rangaswami, M.R. (2009). Why sustainability is now the Key driver of Innovation. *Harvard Business Review*, 3(8),57-64).

Nnadiukwu, A. (2019). How multiple taxes affects Nigerian Companies. Available on <https://nairametrics.com/2019/02/20/how-multiple-taxes-affects-nigerian-companies>.

[Accessed 2021-11-24](#)

Ogundipe, S. (2018). Air pollution: Nigeria ranks 4th deadliest globally. Available on <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2018/09/air-pollution-nigeria-ranks-4th-deadliest-globally>. Accessed 2021-11-24

Pelenc, J., Ballet, J. & Dedeurwaerdere, T. (2015). Weak sustainability versus strong sustainability. In *Global Sustainable Development Report 2015*. Retrieved November 15,2015,from <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/content/documents/1870GSDR%202015%20Briefs.pdf>.

LEADING SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS ADVISORY

Price, L.C. (2008). Amid pollution and political indifference, Nigerians struggle to catch Their breath. Available on <https://pulitzercenter.org/stories/amid-pollution-and-political-indifference-nigerians-struggle-catch-their-breath>. Accessed 2021-11-24

Rudnicka, A. (2016). Understanding sustainable business models. *Journal of Positive Management*, 7(4), 53-60.

Sustainable Development Knowledge Platform (2015). Retrieved November 21, 2021, from <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/>.

Sustainability in the Nigerian business environment (2020). Problems and prospects. *International Journal of Academic Management Science Research*, 3(3),72-80.

Sustainable Development Goals (2018) Sustainable development goal 1, from: <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/sdg1>

The Monitor (2019).Nigeria enlists big beverage companies to fight plastic waste. Available on <https://themonitornews.com.ng/2019/11/14/nigeria-enlists-big-beverage-companies-to-fight-plastic-waste>. Accessed November 24, 2021

UNDP, United Nations Development Programme (2015). Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Retrieved November 17, 2021 from <http://www.undp.org/content/undp/en/home/mdgoverview/post-2015-development-agenda>.

LEADING SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS ADVISORY

United Nations Economic and Social Council (2017). Progress towards the sustainable

development goals, from: [http://www.un.org/ga/search/view_doc.asp?symbol=E/2017/66&](http://www.un.org/ga/search/view_doc.asp?symbol=E/2017/66&Lang=E)

[Lang=E](#) (accessed on 21 November 2021).

Wysockińska, Z. Millennium, J (2017). Development goals and sustainable development goals as

instruments for realizing sustainable development concept of global economy. *Comp.*

Econ. Res. 20 (34), 101–118.

THE CORRELATION OF GOOD GOVERNANCE AND CORPORATE PERFORMANCE

Corporate Governance: The Correlation between Good Governance and Corporate Performance

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Abstract

Research Purpose: This study investigated the correlation amid good governance and corporate performance of firms. The study utilized secondary data from five banks from 2011 to 2020.

Methodology: The data for the study were gotten from the financial statement of banks and report analyzed using the Panel Least Square regression method.

Findings: The results indicated that there is a substantial association amid earnings per shares and size of the board, also there is a substantial correlation amid return on assets and board gender diversity. While board composition, regularity of meetings attended by the board, the audit committee size and independence have no significance with any of the dependent variables. Also, board size and number of meetings held have a negative relationship with earnings per shares; board composition and board size have a negative relationship with return on assets while board gender diversity, the regularity meeting the board held and board composition have a negative relationship with return on equity.

Recommendations: The study concludes that government should put in place an independent taskforce that will ensure that the corporate governance principles are adhered to religiously and a stiff penalty given to those that violate this rule.

Keywords: Board size, Board composition, Board gender diversity, Audit committee

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Corporate Governance: The Correlation between Good Governance and Corporate Performance

As a result of the various crises and scandals in the past decades, interest in corporate governance became a necessary tool in bringing sanity back into the corporate world globally. Stringent measures were put in place to correct these anomalies, and this resulted in an increasingly growing regulatory environment. In 2001, the Enron and WorldCom scandal in USA brought about a new era in which corporate governance of quoted companies became a global discussion. For corporate governance principles to be effective, it must pass the litmus tests which are fairness, independence, transparency, accountability, and responsibility. Numerous Corporate governance principles exist to help achieve the set goals. Therefore, for there to be good corporate governance, there must be clearness of structures and operations of the organization; managers should be answerable to the boards that in turn is accountable to the shareholders; while adhering strictly to corporate responsibility towards stakeholders.

Malcolm (2003) opined that the main goal and task of corporate governance is to ensure a constant and more suitable scheme for achieving good corporate governance and providing clarification for any inconsistencies so as to ensure that the company perform optimally, which will ultimately upsurge the value of the organization as much as possible. Generally, the study seeks to scrutinize the correlation between good governance and corporate performance. Explicitly, the this study seeks to test the effect of outside directors, board individuality, the size

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of the audit committee, effect of board size, board composition, ratio of female to male on the board and corporate governance principles on firm performance.

1.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Corporate governance principles and firm performance

The Corporate governance principles are independence, openness, answerability, responsibility, and fairness. When the principles of good corporate governance are strictly adhered to and well Implemented, it will invariably improve the company's performance. (Gompers et al., 2003) opined that the relationship amongst a well-organized corporate governance structure and a firm's performance, may have an optimistic influence on organization's value, increase the operating performance of organizations and upsurge high investment yields.

Several researches conducted on the correlations concerning the individuality of the boards and the company's performance, disclosed that there are contradictions in the outcomes. When there are more outsiders in the board, it tends to makes the board more independent. According to Bhagat and Black (1990), there is no connection amid the amount of outsider on the board and stock returns, ROA, asset turnover, and Tobin's Q. They opined that those at the top echelon of the organization usually play a substantial role in defining the performance of the firm financially. Fama and Jensen (1983), the board is a core control mechanism that is crucial for keeping an eye on the activities of the top management. (Terry et al., 1994) opined that a direct association exist amid the ratios of outside board members as observed by the reaction of the

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stock market. Caylor and Brown (2004), establish that there is no relationship between Tobin's Q and the individuality of directors, but establish a direct association amid ROE and dividend yield, individuality of directors, profit margin, and stock repurchase. They conclude that establishment would be worthwhile if the CEO and the board' compositions are separate. Wyatt and Rosenstein (1990), found evidence that investor's worth is swayed by an increase in the ratios of outside directors as shown by the way the stock price grows progressively when an outside directors is appointed.

Maclver and Lorsch (1989) opined that the more the size of the board, the more difficult it is for firm to perform optimally, because it reduces the ease with which decisions are been made and also increases cost of operations. Various works carried out also indicate that substantial inverse association exists amid firm performance and larger board size in many countries. (Toshiyuki et al., (2010) found no major connection between firm performance and size of the board. However, certain researchers maintain that an enormous board size can boost diversity and impartiality, thereby snowballing into performance of the firm. (Ciftci et al., 2019).

According to Vafeas (1999), an inverse correlation exists amid value of firm and constant meeting of the board. in a studies conducted to scrutinize the connection between regular meetings held by the board and performance of firms, He concluded that when the board meets regularly, it will enhance firm performance as this will helps to shrink the informational lacuna that exist in the board and creates much faster decision making process. Furthermore, Chou et al., (2013) outlined a progressive correlation concerning the regularity of board meetings and

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firm profitability for firms in Taiwanese. Yet, in Columbian, studies showed that a firm shows no substantial association between the amount of frequent meetings carried out by the board and ROE or ROA (Gomez et al. 2017). In (2007), Huse, noted that the more the board meet, the more effective the monitoring system will be and this will in the long run increase the rate at which a consensus is reach when resolving corporate issues.

According to Abbott and Parker (2001), the maximum number of the audit committee is limited to six (6) persons. Note that when the audit committee is allowed to operate independently, it will enable them to provide reliable accounting information, which will advance the company's performance. Brown & Caylor (2004) opined that the autonomous status of the committee in audit is directly associated to dividend return.

The Good Governance Code of registered corporations (CNMV, 2015) states that the appointment of director should be someone with a grounded knowledge of the company, gender friendly, well experience and in the board's membership. They are of the opinion that director nomination policy should aim at having a minimum of 30% of the total board seats occupied by women directors before the year 2020. Also it is a known fact that women are not overzealous, they apply high principled values in their decision making as compare to their male counterpart. Sparks and Pan (2012), opine that women are more conformist and avoid risk more compare to their male counterpart. Also some studies opined that when women are more at the hem of affair, it will balance the equation and reduce critical questions and reduce discrimination (Alexander et al., 1995). However, Ahern &Dittmar (2012), used quota as an exogenous change to regulate the

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correlation between BGD and firm performance and establish that the announcement of board gender quotas leads to a large decrease in firm value, even in years to follow.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The study used panel research design with a wide-ranging reliance on secondary data gotten from the yearly report of quoted financial institutions in Nigeria for a period of ten year (2011-2021). The population of the study entails all quoted banks in the Nigeria stock exchange. The study used the five biggest banks (first bank, Zenith bank, UBA, Access bank and GTB) in Nigeria based on the performance of the banks and their capitalization as the sample of the study. We used Hausman test to compare the fixed effects to a random effects model. When p-value for the test is more than 5% (0.1804), it means that the null-hypothesis should be accepted which suggests that random effects specifications are to be preferred.

3.1 MODEL

The model specification of the study is as follows:

$$EPS_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 bodc_1 + \beta_2 bodg_2 + \beta_3 bods_3 + \beta_4 auch_4 + \beta_5 nmh_5 + \mu_t$$

$$ROA_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 bodc_1 + \beta_2 bodg_2 + \beta_3 bods_3 + \beta_4 auch_4 + \beta_5 nmh_5 + \mu_t$$

4.0 PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF RESULT

Table 1: DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

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	EPS	ROA	BODC	BODG	BODS	AUCM	NMH
Mean	1.218511	0.030224	0.768057	0.209449	15.08511	6.085106	5.638298
Median	1.770000	0.026600	0.857143	0.222222	14.00000	6.000000	5.000000
Maximum	6.300000	0.112600	1.571429	0.375000	23.00000	8.000000	10.00000
Minimum	-50.00000	-0.004800	0.083333	0.000000	4.000000	6.000000	3.000000
Std. Dev.	7.846722	0.020546	0.363185	0.096893	3.519077	0.350762	1.712175
Skewness	-6.075457	1.468903	-0.328260	-0.201713	-0.134868	4.341303	0.812330
Kurtosis	40.34185	6.799649	3.086730	1.946993	4.108661	21.78865	3.046695
Jarque-Bera	3019.865	45.17491	0.858807	2.490169	2.549527	838.9523	5.173333
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.650897	0.287917	0.279497	0.000000	0.075271
nnnnn	57.27000	1.420541	36.09870	9.844093	709.0000	286.0000	265.0000
Sum Sq. Dev	2832.268	0.019419	6.067569	0.431857	569.6596	5.659574	134.8511
Observations	47	47	47	47	47	47	47

4.1 Table 2. Pearson Correlation Analysis

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CORRELATION

Covariance Analysis: Ordinary

Date: 06/09/21 Time: 13:53

Sample: 2011 2020

Included observations: 47

Balanced sample (listwise missing value deletion)

Correlation								
Probability	EPS	ROA	ROE	BODC	BODG	BODS	AUCM	NMH
EPS	1.000000							

ROA	0.301667	1.000000						
	0.0393	-----						
ROE	0.266732	0.307061	1.000000					
	0.0699	0.0358	-----					
BODC	0.215979	-0.048591	0.105729	1.000000				
	0.1448	0.7457	0.4794	-----				

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BODG	0.063346	0.229938	-0.145572	0.303331	1.000000			
	0.6723	0.1200	0.3289	0.0382	-----			
BODS	-0.241798	-0.211967	0.082601	0.433798	0.159443	1.000000		
	0.1015	0.1526	0.5810	0.0023	0.2844	-----		
AUCM	0.095302	0.108600	0.073331	0.133944	-0.064358	-0.058830	1.000000	
	0.5240	0.4675	0.6242	0.3694	0.6674	0.6945	-----	
								1.00000
NMH	-0.166446	0.097643	-0.265267	-0.519231	0.068025	-0.243731	-0.237210	0
	0.2635	0.5138	0.0715	0.0002	0.6496	0.0987	0.1084	-----

Table 3. ADF unit root test for the variables in equation 3.1

S/N	variables	level	first diff	second diff	remark
1	EPS	0.9441	0.0670	0.0381	1(2)
2	ROA	0.2437	0.0159	-	1(1)
4	BODC	0.0312	-	-	1(0)

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5	BODG	0.8136	0.0001	-	1(1)
6	BODS	0.4375	0.0004	-	1(1)
7	AUCM	0.6784	0.0019	-	1(1)
8	NMH	0.8819	0.0000	-	1(1)

Source: Authors Compilation

Significant @ 5%, Table 4 shows that 8 variables were tested for the existence of unit root to ascertain the stationality status of the sequence, using the Augmented Dickey Fuller test statistics. Of the entire variable tested, only one variable was stationary at level. EPS was stationary at second differences; while other variables were stationary at first difference.

4.3 RESULTS, HYPOTHESIS TESTING AND DISCUSSIONS

EPS - HAUSMAN TEST

Table 5: EPS Regression Analysis (random effect)

Variables	coefficient	Std Error	t- Statistics	Probability
C	10.70122	23.34311	0.458432	0.6491
BODC	7.264232	4.242873	1.712102	0.0944

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BODG	2.787647	12.84627	0.217000	0.8293
BODS	-0.927060	0.362390	-2.558184	0.0143
AUCM	0.127017	3.374635	0.037639	0.9702
NMH	-0.431699	0.822741	-0.524708	0.6026

Weighted Statistics

R-squared 0.191549 Mean dependent var 1.218511

Adjusted R-square 0.092958 S.D. dependent var 7.846722

S.E. of regression 7.473121 Sum squared resid 2289.749

F-statistic 1.942858 Durbin-Watson stat 1.155038

Prob(F-statistic) 0.107993

Unweighted Statistics

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R-squared	0.191549	Mean dependent var	1.218511
Sum squared resid	2289.749	Durbin-Watson stat	1.155038

Source: EViews output (2021)

Using the random effect panel estimation (table 6), we observe that the R^2 is 0.1915 showing that 19.15% of the systematic discrepancy in the dependent variable are described by the independent variable leaving about 80.85% unaccounted for. Similarly, R^2 adjusted which occurs as a result of the adjustment in the degree of freedom reveal a value of 0.0929, which implies that over 9% changes in the dependent variables were explained, while the remaining 81% is not accounted for, hence captured by the stochastic disturbance. The table shows that (BODC) showed a direct association with corporate performance and good governance with a value of 7.264232, (BODS) exhibited an inverse relationship with a value of -0.927060. However, (BODG) showed a direct relationship with a value of 2.787647, (NMH), has an inverse relationship with a value of -0.431699, while (AUCM), have a direct correlation with a value of 0.127017. In terms of, individual significance, only BODS have a significant relationship with good governance and corporate performance all other variables had an insignificant relationship. In relations of the general significance, the collective independent variables disclosed an insignificant association with the dependent variable with a prob(F-statistic) of 0.107993. The Durbin Watson Value of 1.155038 is an indication of the presence of serial autocorrelation in the model, which could be as a consequence of the nature of corporate governance variables.

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Table 6: ROA Regression Analysis (random effect)

Variables	coefficient	Std Error	t- Statistics	Probability
C	-0.008401	0.051449	-0.163291	0.8711
BODC	-0.001973	0.012859	-0.153408	0.8788
BODG	0.059853	0.029944	1.998834	0.0523
BODS	-0.001318	0.001055	-1.250116	0.2183
AUCM	0.007412	0.006767	1.095349	0.2798
NMH	0.000424	0.002485	0.170544	0.8654

Weighted Statistics		
R-square	0.131646	Mean dependent var0.030224
Adjusted R-square	0.025749	S.D. dependent var0.020546
S.E. of regression	0.020280	Sum squared resid0.016863

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F-statistic	1.243155	Durbin-Watson stat	0.633320
Prob(F-statistic)	0.306829		

Unweighted Statistics			
R-square	0.131646	Mean dependent var	0.030224
Sum squared resid	0.016863	Durbin-Watson stat	0.633320

Source: EViews output (2021)

In (table 7), using the dependent variable ROA, we observe that the R^2 is square 0.131646 indicating that 13.13% of the systematic discrepancy in the dependent variable are described by the independent variable leaving about 86.87% unaccounted for. Similarly, R^2 adjusted which occurs as a result of the adjustment in the degree of freedom reveal a value of 0.025749, which implies that over 2.5% changes in the dependent variables were explained, while the remaining 97.5% is not accounted for, hence captured by the stochastic disturbance. The table shows that (BODC) showed an inverse relationship with good governance and corporate performance with a value of -0.001973, (BODS) exhibited an inverse relationship with

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a value of -0.001318, (BODG) showed a direct relationship with a value of 0.059853, (NMH), has a direct association, with a value of 0.000424, while (AUCM), has a direct relationship with good governance and corporate performance, with a value of 0.127017. In relations to individual significance, only BODG have a significant relationship with good governance and corporate performance while all other variables had an insignificant relationship. In terms of the general significance, the collective independent variables exhibited an insignificant relationship with the dependent variable with a prob (F-statistic) value of 0.306829. The Durbin Watson Value of 0.633320 is an indication of the presence of serial autocorrelation in the model, which could be as a consequence of the nature of corporate governance variables.

HYPOTHESIS TESTING

The following hypotheses are tested in this section, based on the result obtained from the random effect panel estimate (tables). This study set the acceptance of the hypothesis at 5% level of significance; hence, the null hypothesis would be rejected if the probability is less than 0.05.

H1: there is no significant relationship between board composition and corporate performance.

From the result of the random effect panel analysis we found an inverse correlation amid board composition and corporate performance which was also not significant in ROA (0.8788) while EPS (0.0944) though not significant, has a positive correlation. We therefore accept the null hypothesis one and reject the alternative hypothesis which state that there is substantial

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correlation amid corporate performance and board composition. The findings with regards to board composition are consistent with the findings of Black and Bhagat (1990) which establish no correlation between proportion of outsider and stock returns, ROA, Tobin's Q, and asset turnover. Also, Caylor and Brown (2004) found no association amid Tobin's Q and, the individuality of the board but establish a direct correlation between ROE and the independence of directors, which further contradict the fact that the configuration of board of directors shows pivotal role in defining the financial performance of the firm.

H2: there is no significant relationship between board gender diversity and firm performance

From the result of the random effect panel analysis, a direct correlation exists between BODG, EPS and ROA. In terms of significance, only ROA ($p=0.0523$) has probability value of 5% which means it is significant. While EPS ($p=0.0944$) is not significant. Based on the P-value of ROA, we therefore reject the null hypothesis two and accept the alternative hypothesis which states that there is a substantial association amid gender diversity in the board and corporate performance. The findings with regards to board gender diversity is in line with the findings of Martínez et al., (2016) who established that the greater percentage of female directors on diverse committees in the organization intensify the chances of promoting transparency by disclosing audit reports with less reservations and scope limitation qualifications because women are known to be meticulous in carrying out their duties. In summary, the more diversified the boards of directors are, the more effective the board will be. (Huse and Solberg, 2006).

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H3: there is no significant relationship between number of board meeting held and corporate performance.

From the result, we find that there is an inverse relationship between NMH and EPS, while ROA shows a positive relationship. In relations to the significance, there is no substantial relationship among NHM with EPS ($p=0.6026$), ROA ($p=0.8654$). Consequently we accept the null hypothesis three and reject the alternative hypothesis which state that there is substantial relationship between number of board meetings held and corporate performance. The findings with regards to frequency meetings of the board is in line with the findings of (Gomez et al. 2017), in a study on Columbian firms which discovered that there is no substantial correlation amongst the number of board meetings, ROE or ROA. Also, Vafeas (1999) establish an inverse correlation between board meetings and firm value. He resolved that numerous meetings held by the board can play a major role in augmenting performance of the firm as this will bridge the informational lacuna among the members of the board.

H4: there is no significant relationship between audit committee size and corporate performance.

The result shows a direct correlation amongst audit committee size, EPS and ROA. In terms of significance, Audit committee size has no significant correlation with EPS ($p=0.9702$) and ROA ($p=0.2798$). Therefore we accept the null hypothesis four and reject the alternative hypothesis which state that there is substantial relationship between audit committee and corporate performance. The findings with regards to size and independence of the audit committee are

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consistent with the findings of the Blue Ribbon Committee Report in 1999, who opined that audit committee, as overseer of financial accounting processes, should conduct regular meetings within the year in order to assure the quality of financial reporting. It is anticipated that the size of the audit committee and numbers of meeting held at a regular interval should improve financial accounting process, and firm performance.

H5: there is no significant relationship between board size and corporate performance.

From the result, we found out that an inverse relationship exists amongst EPS, board size, and ROA. In terms of significance, only EPS ($p=0.0143$) has a significant relationship with board size. ROA ($p=0.2183$) is not meaningfully correlated with corporate performance. Based on the result of the EPS ($p=0.0143$), we therefore reject the null hypothesis five and accept the alternative hypothesis which state that there is significant correlation amid board size and corporate performance. The findings with regards to board size are consistent with the findings of Adam and Mehran (2002), who disputed that corporations should have a higher board size to permit the board to screen the executive of the board effectively. Numerical strength of the board will support a more effective management of the company and it will be stress-free to obtain information that will improve the aspiration of the organization.

5. Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations.

Based on the findings, Board composition has no substantial influence on performance of the firm. The study also reveal that there is no major correlation amid the numbers of meeting held

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by the administrators and increase outcome of the company, Also the numerical strength of the board and performance of the corporation has substantial relationship between them. Several researchers maintain that when the numerical strength of the board is large, it tends to make the board act independently as cited in Ciftci et al. (2019). The Audit committee showed no significant relationship with corporate performance. Lastly, a major correlation occurs between performance of the firm and diversity of gender in the board.

Conclusion

The correlation between good governance and corporate performance ultimately help the organization to achieve it crucial goal of wealth maximization. Fama and Jensen (1983), emphasizes that the board is a core control mechanism that is crucial for keeping an eye on the activities of the top management therefore the structure of board shows the essential role director's play in ensuring that firm performs optimally as they pool their wealth of experience together. Frequent meeting by the board, will spur growth while matters arising will be nip in the bud with immediate effect. The Audit committee acts as a watch dog for the firm. They ensure the authentication of the financial statement presented by the managers; therefore, frequent meetings will invariably improve firm performance. While the presence of more women in the board will help balance the board as they are known to be highly principled and tends to conform to the lay down rules and regulation when given a position of authority and are more risk-adverse than men.

Recommendation

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1. There should be a constant overhaul of the board members who will bring in fresh ideas and perspectives and be objective.
2. The government should roll out workable and feasible policy that will improve corporate governance in Nigeria
3. The carrot and stick approach should be introduced in ensuring that adherence of the policy are rewarded while deviant are punished accordingly.
4. More diversity in boards of directors will contribute to board effectiveness.
5. In addition to an increase in the audit committee size and frequent meeting, a rotational system should be put in place to avoid unnecessary fraternity with the audit committee so that they can be objective in carrying out their duties.

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References

- Abbott, L.J., Parker, S and Peters, G. F. "Audit committee characteristics and financial misstatement: A study of the efficacy of certain blue ribbon committee recommendation," Proceedings of the Auditing Section of the AAA Meeting, 2001.
- Alexander, J., Nuchols, B., Bloom, J.,& Lee, S.D., (1995). Organizational demography and turnover: an examination of multiform and nonlinear heterogeneity. *Hum. Relat.* 48 (5), 1455-1480.
- Aljifri, K., & Mohamed, M. (2007). The Impact of Corporate Governance Mechanisms on the Performance of UAE Firms: An Empirical Analysis. *Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences*,23, 71-93.
- Anderson, R., Mansi, S., &Reeb, D. (2004).Board Characteristics, Accounting Report Integrity, and the Cost of Debt *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 37, 315-342.
- Bhagat, S.,&Black, B. (2002).The Non- Correlation between Board Independence and Long Term Firm Performance *Journal of Corporation Law*, 27, 231-274
- Brickley, J., Coles, J., & Terry, R. (1994).Outside Directors and adoption of poison pill.*Journal of Financial Economics*, 35, 371-390 (18).
- Brown, L.D., &Caylor, M.L., (2004). Corporate Governance and firm

THE CORRELATION OF GOOD GOVERNANCE AND CORPORATE PERFORMANCE

performance. *Fox school of business*, Temple University.SSRN. Retrieved from http://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=586423

Chou, Hsin-I., Huimin Chung, & Xiangkang, Y., (2013). Attendance of Board

Meetings and Company Performance: Evidence from Taiwan. *Journal of Banking and Finance*, 37, 4157–71.

Fama, E.F, & Jensen, M.C. (1983). Separation of ownership and control. *Journal of*

Law and Economics, 26, 301-325

Gomez, J., Diogenes, L. & Gonzalo, B. (2017). Effect of the

Board of Directors on Firm Performance. *International Journal of Economic Research* 14: 349–61 Governance? `22 Review of Financial Studies 783

Gompers, P. A., Ishii, J.L., & Metrick, A. (2003). *Corporate Governance and*

Equity Prices, 118(1), 107-155,

Hu, Y., & Shigemitsu, I. (2008). Ownership Concentration and Corporate Performance: A

Causal Analysis with Japanese Panel Data. *Corporate Governance* 16, 342–58.

Lundeberg, M.A., Fox, P.W., & Puncochar, J., (1994). Highly confident but wrong: gender

THE CORRELATION OF GOOD GOVERNANCE AND CORPORATE PERFORMANCE

differences and similarities in confidence judgments. *Journal of Educational Psychology*. 86 (1), 114-121.

Lorsch, J., & Elizabeth, M. (1989). *Pawns or Potentates: The Reality of America's Corporate Boards*. Boston: Harvard University Press.

Rosenstein, S. & Wyatt, J (1990). Outside Directors and Board independence. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 26, 175-191.

Sueyoshi, T., Mika, G., & Yusuke, O. (2010). Corporate governance and firm performance: Evidence from Japanese manufacturing industries after the lost decade. *European Journal of Operational Research* 203, 724-736.

Vafeas, N. (1999). Board Meeting Frequency and Firm Performance. *Journal of Financial Economics* 53, 113-42.

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IMPACT OF GROUP DYNAMICS ON ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE

Impact of Group Dynamics on Organizational Performance

(A Study of First Bank Nigeria and Union Bank Plc Owerri Imo State)

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Abstract

Research Purpose: This research has examined the impact of group dynamics on organizational performance. The study formulated three objectives, research questions as well as hypotheses. Various literatures were reviewed.

Research Methodology: The study adopted a survey approach in its design and the questionnaire was the major tool for data gathering. The data gathered were presented with percentage and analysed with Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).

Finding: The findings revealed that group structure, adherence to group roles and norms, enhance market share, service quality as well as cost reduction.

Recommendation: Based on the findings, the researcher recommends that organizations should develop group norms, rules and regulation to guide the activities of group members in work environment. This will help to make the employee adhere to their organizational goals.

Keywords: group dynamics, organizational performance, group structure, roles, norms, market share, service quality and cost reduction.

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Impact of Group Dynamics on Organizational Performance

1.1 Background of the Study

It is a well-known truth that corporations are made up of several types of people, including management, shareholders, employees, partners, creditors, and a variety of others. This group of employees performs different but connected tasks to ensure the organization's survival, excellent performance, and attainment of its goals. In fulfilling their functions, each of these types of persons in the organization form a different group, i.e., employees, management, and other organizational members are groups that work toward the fulfillment of organizational objectives in their own unique and connected ways.

In this regard, Akpanabia (2015) stated that a group is defined as a collection of people who gather together to accomplish a common objective or purpose. This indicates that people in organizations (as employees or managers, for example) form a group that works to ensure the organization's survival and attainment of its objectives. It is possible for such a gathering to be formal or casual. Also, according to Ugwu (2007), groups are persons in the same occupation, organization, or institution who work together to achieve specific and broad goals for their own personal, organizational, and social well-being. This means that a group is always made up of different types of people who are committed to achieving the group's goals. As a result, in our system, group dynamics and commitment to duty may improve organizational performance.

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The attitudinal and behavioral qualities of a group are referred to as group dynamics. The formation, structure, and process of groups, as well as how they function, are all aspects of group dynamics. Group dynamics are important in all forms of formal and informal organizations (Akpanabia, 2015).

In an organizational setting, groups are a very common organizational entity and the study of groups and group dynamics is an important area of study in organizational behavior.

Group dynamics as related to development concerns not only why groups form but also how. The most common framework for examining the "how" of group formation was developed by Bruce Tuckman in the 1960s. In other words, the processes in group formation imply that groups do not always operate at their best when they are first formed. As they seek to become more productive and effective, they go through numerous stages of development. Most groups go through the same stages of development, with comparable disputes and resolves. Another important factor to consider in group dynamics and organizational success, according to Alugbuo (2003), is group size.

The number of participants in a group might range from two to hundreds. Small groups of two to ten people are regarded to be more productive since each member has more opportunities to contribute and get actively involved in the group, as well as put in more effort to improve their own performance and the productivity of the business. Large groups can squander time debating on methods and trying to figure out who should be the next to participate..

This is true because according to Hinkle (2010), in formal groups, roles are usually predetermined and assigned to members in the organizations. Each role will have specific

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responsibilities and duties. There are, however, emergent roles that develop naturally to meet the needs of the groups and organization. These emergent roles will often replace the assigned.

Work roles are task-oriented tasks that entail achieving the aims and objectives of the group and the company. Initiator, informer, clarifier, summarizer, and reality tester are just a few of the responsibilities involved. The initiator identifies issues, presents solutions, and recommends methods (Hinkle, 2010). According to him, the informer's job entails gathering information and offering suggestions or comments. Clarifiers will help the group by interpreting thoughts, defining vocabulary, and clarifying issues. Summarizers reiterate suggestions, make decisions, and reach group conclusions. Finally, reality testers examine concepts and put them to the test in real-world scenarios.

Therefore, the impact of group dynamic on organizational performance cannot be over emphasized hence, the way organizational members (groups) – employee, management and others are devoted towards the achievement of individual and organizational goals determines the organizational performance and productivity. This study is focused on examining the impact of group dynamics on organizational performance in selected Nigeria organizations.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

It has been observed that there are always inter and intra group conflict. Among the employees (as group) there is always conflict of interest as it concerns who is being or to be promoted, who to lead others, which function to perform, and who is more connected to the management. This situation affects employee performance and organizational productivity in the

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organization. Empirical evidences have proven that there is a relationship between group dynamics and organizational performance, however, studies have not been able to ascertain how group dynamics in the area of group structure, group role and group norms affects market share, cost reduction and service quality of organization. This study has filled the gap by establishing these variables and determining the relationship that exist between them.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is to examine the impact of group dynamic on organizational performance in Nigeria. The specific objectives include:

1. To determine how group structure of a firm affects its market share.
2. To evaluate how group roles in organization impacts on cost reduction.
3. To determine how group norms improves services/product quality.

1.4 Research Questions

In line with the above objective of the study, the following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. What is the impact of group structure on market share of a firm?
2. How does group roles in organization bring about cost reduction?
3. What is the impact of group norms in improving services/product quality?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

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In line with our research objectives and questions, the following hypotheses guided the study:

Hypothesis one

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between group structure of a firm and its market share.

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between group roles and cost reduction in organization.

Hypothesis three:

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between group norms and improved services/product quality.

1.6 Scope of the Study

The unit scope of this study focused on the impact of group dynamics on organizational performance. The geographic scope is focused First Bank Nigeria plc and Union Bank Owerri Imo State while the staff of the above banks in their headquarters in Owerri Imo State was used for the study.

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 The Concept and Nature of Group and Group Dynamic

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Robbins (1989) defines a group as two or more individuals who interact and are interdependent and come together to achieve specific goals, according to Agulanna and Madu (2009). A work group or team, according to Cushway and Lodge (1993), is a group of people with a common goal who interact with one another, are psychologically aware of one another, and perceive themselves as a group. A group, according to Baron (1986), is made up of two or more people who are in social interaction, have some stable, structured ties, share common aims, and view themselves as a group.

It's worth noting that groups play a vital role in organizational behavior because they have a significant impact on behavior. Groups have been discovered to be crucial and successful social change agents. Furthermore, groups have been observed to boost or hinder organizational performance in significant ways (Agulanna and Madu, 2009).

The term "group" refers to a group of people who have met for a certain purpose. This means that a group exists within an organization to achieve a certain goal. In this regard, Akpanabia (2015) claimed that a group can be described as a collection of people who get together in an organizational context to accomplish a specific activity or purpose. This indicates that people in organizations (as employees or managers, for example) form a group that works to ensure the organization's survival and attainment of its objectives. It is possible for such a gathering to be formal or casual.

Also, according to Ugwu (2007), groups are persons in the same occupation, organization, or institution who work together to achieve specific and broad goals for their own personal, organizational, and social well-being. This means that a group is always made up of

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different types of people who are committed to achieving the group's goals. As a result, under our system, group dynamics and commitment to duty may improve organizational performance. This signifies that a group is a collection of people who gather together to fulfill a common task, objective, purpose, or aim. As a result, group dynamic refers to the techniques used by a group to achieve its objectives.

Group dynamics, according to Agulanna and Madu (2009), refers to a group's attitudinal and behavioral qualities. The formation, structure, and process of groups, as well as how they function, are all aspects of group dynamics. Group dynamics are important in all forms of official and informal groupings. Groups are a typical organizational entity in the workplace, and the study of groups and group dynamics is an important topic of research in organizational behavior.

2.1.2 Types of Groups

Formal and informal groups are also possible. A formal group is one that has been sanctioned and organized by administrative or other authority in order to achieve organizational goals. They may have designated leaders, clearly defined roles to play, and generally specified methods of carrying out their activities. Managers who govern the actions of such groups (as workers in a division, department, section, or unit) usually have defined regulations and, as previously said, they are formally recognized..

An informal group is a loose affiliation that does not have a formal structure or organizational structure and arises out of a desire for social interaction. They are formed by

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people who believe they share common interests that are either similar to or distinct from those of formal groups. In most cases, such informal groupings break beyond organizational reporting lines. If the group members' interests are threatened or diverge from those of the formal organization, they could be disruptive. In other words, the primary motivation for people to join such organizations is for personal gain.

2.1.3 Group Development

Group dynamics is concerned with why and how groups form when applied to group development. There are various hypotheses about why people form groups. George Homans proposed a famous hypothesis that argues groups form based on activities, contacts, and attitudes. In essence, the theory states that when people engage in common activities, they will interact more and form attitudes (good or negative) toward one another. The interaction of the individuals involved is a key component of this approach (Dembo, 2010).

A different hypothesis for group development is social exchange theory. Individuals develop connections based on the implicit expectation of mutually beneficial transactions based on trust and felt duty, according to this view. Thus, if individuals are to be drawn to and connect with a group, they must believe that exchange connections will be favorable..

Social identity theory, according to Ekpendu (2008), provides another explanation for group formation. Simply expressed, this idea proposes that people's sense of self-esteem and identity are founded on their membership in important groups. The nature of the group may be based on demographics, culture, or organizational factors. Individuals are encouraged to join and

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contribute to identity organizations because they gain a sense of belonging and self-worth from doing so.

2.1.4 Stages of Group Development

According to Tuckman's theory (as cited by Akpanabia, 2015), there are five stages of group development: forming, storming, norming, performing, and adjourning. During these stages group members must address several issues and the way in which these issues are resolved determines whether the group will succeed in accomplishing its tasks.

1. **Forming:** This stage is usually characterized by some confusion and uncertainty. The major goals of the group have not been established. The nature of the task or leadership of the group has not been determined (Luthans, 2005).

2. **Storming:** In this stage, the group is likely to see the highest level of disagreement and conflict. Members often challenge group goals and struggle for power. Individuals often vie for the leadership position during this stage of development. This can be a positive experience for all groups if members can achieve cohesiveness through resolution. Members often voice concern and criticism in this phase. If members are not able to resolve the conflict, then the group will often disband or continue in existence but will remain ineffective and never advance to the other stages (Akpanabia, 2015).

3. **Norming:** This stage is characterized by the recognition of individual differences and shared expectations. Hopefully, at this stage the group members will begin to develop a feeling of group cohesion and identity. Cooperative effort should begin to yield results.

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Responsibilities are divided among members and the group decides how it will evaluate progress (Black, 1995).

4. **Performing:** Performing, occurs when the group has matured and attains a feeling of cohesiveness. During this stage of development, individuals accept one another and conflict is resolved through group discussion. Members of the group make decisions through a rational process that is focused on relevant goals rather than emotional issues.

5. **Adjourning:** Not all groups experience this stage of development because it is characterized by the disbandment of the group. Some groups are relatively permanent (Luthans, 2005). Reasons that groups disband vary, with common reasons being the accomplishment of the task or individuals deciding to go their own ways. Members of the group often experience feelings of closure and sadness as they prepare to leave.

2.1.5 Basic Issues In Organization and Group Dynamic

Here, we are going to look at

Group Structure

Group structure is a pattern of relationships among members that hold the group together and help it achieve assigned goals. Structure can be described in a variety of ways. Among the more common considerations are group size, group roles, group norms, and group cohesiveness (George, 2010).

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Group Roles

In formal groups, roles are usually predetermined and assigned to members. Each role will have specific responsibilities and duties. There are, however, emergent roles that develop naturally to meet the needs of the groups. These emergent roles will often replace the assigned roles as individuals begin to express themselves and become more assertive. Group roles can then be classified into work roles, maintenance roles, and blocking roles.

Work roles are task-oriented activities that involve accomplishing the group's goals (Hinkle, 2010). They involve a variety of specific roles such as initiator, informer, clarifier, summarizer, and reality tester. The initiator defines problems, proposes action, and suggests procedures.

Maintenance roles are social-emotional activities that help members maintain their involvement in the group and raise their personal commitment to the group. The maintenance roles are harmonizer, gatekeeper, consensus tester, encourager, and compromiser. The harmonizer will reduce tension in the group, reconcile differences, and explore opportunities. Gatekeepers often keep communication channels open and make suggestions that encourage participation. The consensus tester will ask if the group is nearing a decision and test possible conclusions. Encouragers are friendly, warm, and responsive to other group members. The last maintenance role is the compromiser. This role involves modifying decisions, offering compromises, and admitting errors (George, 2010).

Group Norms

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According to Agulanna and Madu (2009), norms are acceptable standards of behavior within a group that are shared by the members of the group. Norms define the boundaries of acceptable and unacceptable behavior. They are typically created in order to facilitate group survival, make behavior more predictable, avoid embarrassing situations, and express the values of the group. Each group will establish its own set of norms that might determine anything from the appropriate dress to how many comments to make in a meeting. Groups exert pressure on members to force them to conform to the group's standards. The norms often reflect the level of commitment, motivation, and performance of the group.

Performance norms determine how quickly members should work and how much they should produce. They are created in an effort to determine levels of individual effort. They can be very frustrating to managers because they are not always in line with the organization's goals. Members of a group may have the skill and ability to perform at higher levels but they don't because of the group's performance norms. For example, workers may stop working a production machine at 20 minutes before quitting time in order to wash up, even though they produced fewer items that day than management intended (Agulanna and Madu, 2009).

Reward-allocation norms determine how rewards are bestowed upon group members. For example, the norm of equality dictates equal treatment of all members. Every member shares equally so rewards are distributed equally to everyone. Equity norms suggest that rewards are distributed according to the member's contribution. In other words, members who contribute the most receive the largest share of the rewards. Members may contribute through effort, skill, or ability. Social responsibility norms reward on the basis of need. Members who have special

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needs therefore receive the largest share of the reward. The majority of the group must agree that the norms are appropriate in order for the behavior to be accepted. There must also be a shared understanding between role ambiguity and role conflict (Chukwuma, 2014).

2.2. Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Key Points Of Group Dynamic Theory

Agulanna and Madu (2009); Ebele (1990), Abba et al (2004) and Rizo (2010) identified the followings:

- ✓ Groups under conditions of positive interdependence were generally more co-operative and tend to be productive as compared to those working under negative task.
- ✓ Democracy must be learned anew in each generation, and that it is a far more difficult form of social structure to attain and to maintain than is autocracy.
- ✓ The difference in behaviour in autocratic, democratic and laissez-faire situations is not, on the whole, a result of individual differences.
- ✓ Democracy cannot be imposed on people, but has to be learnt by a process of voluntary and responsible participation.
- ✓ Change and periods of transition needs to be facilitated and guided.

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✓ Motivation for change must be generated before change can occur. Participants must be helped to re-examine many cherished assumptions about self, relationships and the group as part of the process.

To them, in applying group dynamic Theory in an organizational development Intervention, the following should be observed.

1. Encourage the senior leadership team to be the same as any good teacher, becoming unnecessary, and allowing natural leaders to rise from the group during a period of transition.
2. Asking the Leader to change one or more of their characteristics or replace the leader with another person to harness the power of an informal group.
3. Systematically rotate out of the group its leaders and its key members in order to facilitate the emergence of a leader who has aims similar to the organization
4. Be alert to leaders sympathetic to the organizations objectives and use them toward the betterment of the formal group's effectiveness.
5. Locate the best person in the group who is the best position to facilitate the smooth flow of information among group members.
6. Encourage group discussion and decision-making, and ensure participants regardless of position, treat each other as peers.

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7. Use a feedback activity to enable participants to engage in active dialogue about differences of interpretation and observation of the events by those who had participated in them.
8. Develop a creative tension in the learning environment, bringing together the immediate experiences of the participants and the conceptual models of the facilitators in an open atmosphere where inputs from each perspective could challenge and stimulate the other.
9. Observe the behaviour patterns of the group through interviews and asking the group members to identify their own norms; as members become aware of negative norms they commonly reject them and seek to change their behaviour.
10. Create an environment in which values and beliefs can be challenged.
11. Develop the group as students of OD tools, providing the group with models for organizing ideas through brief lectures, reading material, handouts and experiential learning techniques.
12. Involve group members in the decision making process to reduce feelings of alienation and also improve communication between leaders and their employees and thereby reducing conflict.

2.3 Empirical Review

The impact of informal groups on organizational performance was investigated by Ogohi (2016).

The goal of this research is to figure out why employees create informal groups. A survey study

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methodology was used, and 319 employees from the selected construction enterprises were given copies of the questionnaire using a disproportionate stratified sampling procedure. Pearson product moment correlation was used to examine the data. Content validity was used to validate the questionnaire. The questionnaire's reliability was evaluated by calculating the correlation coefficient of data obtained at two separate times. The study discovered that informal groups have a significant impact on employee performance, that informal groups and their characteristics have a significant relationship, that informal groups and self-confidence in Nigerian construction firms have a significant relationship, and that informal groups have a significant impact on organizational performance in Nigeria.

2.4 Gap in Literature

The study on group dynamics and organizational performance has been examined by several scholars. However, the this study examined those variables which were not discussed by scholars like group structures, group role and group norms as well as market share, cost reduction and service quality. Also the study filled the gap by examining the group dynamics using deposit money banks.

2.5 Chapter Summary

This chapter has examined the study based on the conceptual, theoretical as well as empirical review. The conceptual review examined the concept of group and group dynamics as well as organizational performance. The theoretical review was as well explained as well as empirical review that examined the work of scholars on related study.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

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This chapter gives the explanation on the procedure, techniques and approaches adopted by the researcher in data collection, study design, sample and sampling technique, study population and method of data analysis. All the methods adopted in this chapter is meant to enhance the scientific nature of the study, hence the researcher adopted a systematic approach for the study.

3.1 Research Design

A research design is the strategy, the plan and the structure of conducting a research project. Asika (2008) opined that research design states the conceptual structure within which the research would be conducted. In this study, survey research design was adopted by the researcher. Ubah, Ochienta and Nwonu (2015) asserted that survey research design focuses on a representative sample derived from the entire population. This design was used to determine the impact of group dynamic on organizational performance in the Nigerian banks.

3.2 Population of the Study

This is the entire number of elements in the area of the study (Anyanwu, 2000). The population of this study is therefore made up of the entire staff of First Bank and Union Bank Plc all in bank road Owerri Imo State. First bank has a total of 36 staff and Union bank has a total of 24 staff in their headquarters in Owerri Imo State. Therefore the population of this study is made up of the 60 staff in the two selected banks in Owerri Imo State. The researcher used the staff of the banks because the staff formed the group and work in distinct sections/departments (as groups) in the bank.

3.3 Sample Size

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Here, it should be noted that sampling involves taking a portion out of the entire population, since researchers cannot carry research on the whole 60 (sixty) because of the limitation of study. The sample size is mathematically derived using the Yaro Yamen's formula as thus:

$$n = \frac{n}{1+n(e)^2}$$

Where n = population

n = sample size

e = margin of error = 5% or 0.05

$$n = \frac{60}{1+60(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{60}{1+60(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{60}{1+0.15}$$

$$n = \frac{60}{1.15}$$

$$n = 52$$

3.4 Sampling Procedure

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The sampling procedure used is the probability sampling procedure. It is most applicable to research in administrative sciences. The sample procedure used under this was basically the simple random sampling. In the study, the researcher made it that all the staff (our study population) of the selected banks have the equal chance of been selected in the study sample.

3.5 Sources of Data.

In this study, both primary and secondary data were used.

- a. **Primary Data:** The questionnaire served as the primary data for this study. It was used to enhance the scientific nature of the study. Primary data was also used to minimize confusion and reduce time waste. The researcher was taught to first establish a rapport with the respondent before administering the measuring instrument.

- b. **Secondary Data:** Secondary data were also used. These data were collected from different sources like newspaper, magazine and journals.

3.6 Research Instrument

The questionnaire served as the instrument of data collection in this study. This is to make data analysis easy and simple. The questionnaire was divided into two sections, section A and section B respectively. Section A concerned itself with some personal variables necessary to provide information in respect of the respondents. The information under this section is capable of identifying the respondents in respect of sex, age, marital status, educational qualification and so on.

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Section B was constructed to contain the relevant questions necessary for the testing of the hypothesis and drawing of conclusions. Generally, the questionnaire was made up of close ended forms and systematically arranged to win the interest of the respondents in completing the questions on the issue of merger and acquisition in Nigeria Banks.

3.7 Method of Data Analysis

In this study, the researcher used simple percentage and ANOVA to analyze the data collected. Simple percentage was used to determine the respondents' percentage responses in any of the questions, while analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test the hypothesis.

ANOVA is a method of data analysis which tends to analyze the different forms of variance associated within the sample selected. Sample are drawn from the population chosen and treated in respect to our hypothesis stated earlier to know if a situation arise to accept or reject the hypothesis (Null and Alternative).

ANOVA TABLE

Source of Variance	DF	SS	MS	F-Value
Between sample (treatment)	r-1	TRSS	TRSS/r-2	
Within samples (error)	n-1	ESS	ESS/n-2	
Total	n-1	TSS		

Source: Egbulonu (2007)

Where

TRSS = treatment sum of square or sample

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$$TSS = \sum n_j (X_j - \bar{X})^2$$

$$TSS = TRSS + ESS$$

$$TSS = \sum \sum (X_{ij} - \bar{X})^2$$

Where

$$X = \sum \sum X_{ij}$$

ESS = error sum of square or sample

$$ESS = TSS - TRSS$$

DF = degree of freedom

$$DF = n - 1$$

MS = mean of square or sample

3.7 Decision Rule

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In this study, the null hypothesis will be rejected if our calculated f-value is greater than the value found from our table, otherwise we accept our alternative hypothesis. Also, we are going to use f-distribution table at 5% level of significance.

4.1 Test of Hypotheses

The hypotheses were tested using analysis of variance (ANOVA) technique to evaluate the rejection and acceptance of the hypothesis stated in this study.

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between group structure of a firm and its market share.

Table 4.1

Option	Cashier unit	Teller unit	Customer care unit	Marketing unit	Total
Strongly agreed	4	5	4	3	16
Agreed	5	6	5	4	20
Undecided	5	1	1	1	8
Disagreed	2	1	2	3	8
Strongly disagreed	-	-	-	-	-
Total	16	13	12	11	52

Calculation using analysis of variance

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Table 4.2: Calculating data for hypothesis one using ANOVA

Option	Cashier unit	Teller unit	Customer care unit	Marketing unit	Total
Strongly agreed	5x4=20	5x5=25	5x4=20	5x3=15	
Agreed	4x5=20	4x6=24	4x5=20	4x4=16	
Undecided	3x5=15	3x1=3	3x1=3	3x1=3	
Disagreed	2x2=4	2x1=2	2x2=4	2x3=6	
Strongly disagreed	-	-	-	-	
ΣX	59	54	47	40	200
X	14.75	13.5	11.75	10	50
ΣX^2	1041	1214	825	526	3606

$$TSS = \sum x^2 - \frac{(\sum x)^2}{n}$$

Where

$$TSS = 3606 - \frac{(200)^2}{20}$$

$$= 3606 - 2000$$

$$= 1606$$

$$TRSS = n \sum x^2 - \frac{(\sum x)^2}{n}$$

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$$= \frac{4(14.75^2 + 13.5^2 + 11.75^2 + 10^2 - 4(200)^2)}{20}$$

$$= 4(637.88 - 400)$$

$$= 951.52$$

$$\text{ESS} = \text{TSS} - \text{TRSS}$$

$$= 1606 - 952.52$$

$$= 654.48$$

Table 4.3: ANOVA table for hypothesis one

Source of variation	DF	SS	MS	F-Value
TRSS	3	951.52	317.17	317.17
ESS	16	654.48	40.9	40.9
Total	19			= 7.75

Note: $DF = r - 1 = 4 - 1 = 3$

$$n - r = 20 - 4 = 16$$

From the f-distribution table, the value of f at 5% level of significance is 3.24 that is $f_{3,16}$ at 5% = 3.24

DECISION

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The computation above showed the critical value is less than the calculated value (that is 3.24 is less than 7.8) which means that the calculated value is greater, therefore, we reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and accept the alternative hypothesis (H_1) and conclude that there is significant relationship between group structure of a firm and its market share.

Hypothesis Two

H_{02} : There is no significant relationship between group roles and cost reduction in organization.

Table 4.4

Option	Cashier unit	Teller unit	Customer care unit	Marketing unit	Total
Strongly agreed	4	3	1	2	10
Agreed	2	2	1	0	5
Undecided	0	1	2	1	4
Disagreed	8	7	4	3	22
Strongly disagreed	2	3	5	1	11
Total	16	16	13	7	52

Table 4.5 Calculating data for hypothesis one using ANOVA

Option	Cashier unit	Teller unit	Customer care unit	Marketing unit	Total
Strongly agreed	$5 \times 4 = 20$	$5 \times 3 = 15$	$5 \times 1 = 5$	$5 \times 2 = 10$	

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Agreed	$4 \times 2 = 8$	$4 \times 2 = 8$	$4 \times 1 = 4$	$4 \times 0 = 0$	
Undecided	$3 \times 0 = 0$	$3 \times 1 = 3$	$3 \times 2 = 6$	$3 \times 1 = 3$	
Disagreed	$2 \times 8 = 16$	$2 \times 7 = 14$	$2 \times 4 = 4$	$2 \times 3 = 6$	
Strongly disagreed	$1 \times 2 = 2$	$1 \times 3 = 3$	$1 \times 5 = 5$	$1 \times 1 = 1$	
$\sum X$	46	43	28	20	137
X	9.2	86	5.6	4	27.4
$\sum X^2$	724	503	166	146	1539

$$TSS = \frac{\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2}{n}$$

Where n=20

$$TSS = \frac{1539 - (137)^2}{20}$$

$$= 1539 - 938.45$$

$$= 600.55$$

$$TRSS = \frac{n \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2}{n}$$

$$= \frac{5(9.22 + 8.6^2 + 5.6^2 + 4^2) - 4(137)^2}{20}$$

$$= \frac{5(205.96 - 187.69)}{20}$$

$$= 91.35$$

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$$ESS = TSS - TRSS$$

$$= 600.55 - 91.35 - 952.52$$

$$= 509.2$$

Table 4.6: ANOVA table for hypothesis two

Source of variation	DF	SS	MS	F-Value
TRSS	3	91.35	30.45	30.45
ESS	16	509.2	31.83	31.83
Total	19	600.55		= 0.96

Note: $DF = r - 1 = 4 - 1 = 3$

$$n - r = 20 - 4 = 16$$

From the f-distribution table, the value of f at 5% level of significance is 3.24 that is $f_{3,16}$ at 5% = 3.24

DECISION

The computation above showed the critical value is less than the calculated value (that is 3.24 is less than 0.96) which means that the calculated value is lesser, therefore, we reject the alternative hypothesis (H1) and accept the null hypothesis (Ho) and conclude that there is no significant relationship between group roles and cost reduction in the organization.

HYPOTHESIS THREE

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between group norms and improved services/product quality.

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Table 4.7

Option	Cashier unit	Teller unit	Customer care unit	Marketing unit	Total
Strongly agreed	4	5	4	3	16
Agreed	5	6	5	4	20
Undecided	5	1	1	1	8
Disagreed	2	1	2	3	8
Strongly disagreed	-	-	-	-	-
Total	16	13	12	11	52

Calculation using analysis of variance

Table 4.8 Calculating data for hypothesis three using ANOVA

Option	Cashier unit	Teller unit	Customer care unit	Marketing unit	Total
Strongly agreed	$5 \times 4 = 20$	$5 \times 5 = 25$	$5 \times 4 = 20$	$5 \times 3 = 15$	
Agreed	$4 \times 5 = 20$	$4 \times 6 = 24$	$4 \times 5 = 20$	$4 \times 4 = 16$	
Undecided	$3 \times 5 = 15$	$3 \times 1 = 3$	$3 \times 1 = 3$	$3 \times 1 = 3$	
Disagreed	$2 \times 2 = 4$	$2 \times 1 = 2$	$2 \times 2 = 4$	$2 \times 3 = 6$	
Strongly disagreed	-	-	-	-	
$\sum X$	59	54	47	40	200
X	14.75	13.5	11.75	10	50

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$\sum X^2$	1041	1214	825	526	3606
------------	------	------	-----	-----	------

$$TSS = \frac{\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2}{n}$$

Where

$$TSS = \frac{3606 - (200)^2}{20}$$

$$= 3606 - 2000$$

$$= 1606$$

$$TRSS = \frac{n \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2}{n}$$

$$= \frac{4(14.75^2 + 13.5^2 + 11.75^2 + 10^2) - 4(200)^2}{20}$$

$$= 4(637.88 - 400)$$

$$= 951.52$$

$$ESS = TSS - TRSS$$

$$= 1606 - 952.52$$

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= 654.48

Table 4.9: ANOVA table for hypothesis one

Source of variation	DF	SS	MS	F-Value
TRSS	3	951.52	317.17	317.17
ESS	16	654.48	40.9	40.9
Total	19			= 7.75

Note: $DF = r-1 = 4-1 = 3$

$n-r = 20-4 = 16$

From the f-distribution table, the value of f at 5% level of significance is 3.24 that is $f_{3,16}$ at 5% = 3.24

Decision

The computation above showed the critical value is less than the calculated value (that is 3.24 is less than 7.8) which means that the calculated value is greater, therefore, we reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and accept the alternative hypothesis (H_1) and conclude that there is significant relationship between group norms and improved services/product quality.

5.0 SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary

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This study focuses on group dynamic and organizational performance in Nigeria organizations. The researcher used First Bank and Union Bank in Owerri Imo State as the focal point. The study was carried out because of the need to determine the impact of work group on employee commitment, employee performance, customer satisfaction, and organizational profitability/productivity.

Based on the statement of the problem the research objectives focused on determining how group structure of a firm affects its market share, how group size of a firm impact on its profitability, how group roles in organization impacts on cost reduction, how group norms improves services/product quality, and how group cohesiveness brings about labour immobility; hence our research questions and hypotheses were based on the above research objectives.

It was stated that this study will be significant and valuable to the Nigerian banks, the employees of the banks, the bank shareholders and customers; hence the organizational workers will understand the value of performing effectively in their different work group to enhance organizational performance. Not only that, the customers of the banks will therefore be satisfied in doing business with their bank as work group in the banks will leads up to expectation based on high commitment.

The researcher employed survey research design, and questionnaire served as the instrument of data collection. The data collected were presented in tables and analyzed using simple percentage and analysis of variance. Based on the data analysis and test of our hypotheses, it was discovered that there is significant relationship between group structure of a firm and its market share, there is no significant impact between group roles and cost reduction

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in the Nigeria banks and there is significant relationship between group norms and improved service/product quality.

5.2 Conclusion

The researcher in this study has examined group dynamic and organizational performance in the Nigeria banking industry. From our study findings it could be seen that group structure, adherence to group roles and norms, enhance employee commitment, understanding, and high performance in the organizations and even organizational growth and development.

Based on the above, we conclude here that Nigerian organization could improve productivity by giving more consideration to the human element of the firm. It has been tested and proved that effective groups dynamic can increase productivity through employee high performance. Enlightened managers utilize this fact for more efficient running of their organization. More consultation of the groups by the management should be encouraged and suggestions made by the workers be utilized as this motivates the workers more for greater performance.

In all, the achievement of organizational high productivity, stability and growth in the Nigeria bank is dependent on the commitment of employee groups, their effectiveness and efficient in doing their job and their commitment to duty.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on our findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendation were made:

1. After recruitment, selection and orientation, new employees should be made to join

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groups in their organization (through which they can contribute effectively for the achievement of organizational growth and development).

2. Organizational management should also appreciate the fact that the intense team spirit (esprit de corps) that is characteristic of groups is a good motivator to increase workers performance.
3. Organizations should develop group norms, rules and regulation to guide the activities of group members in work environment. This will help to make the employee adhere to their organizational goals.

5.4 Suggestions for Further Studies

Further researchers should focus on:

- (i) The impact of group structure on the organizational market share and profitability.
- (ii) The role of group size on employee performance and commitment in the organization.
- (iii) The impact of group norms, rules and regulation on organizational development and growth.

5.5 Limitations of the study

The following are the problems which the researcher encountered in this study:

1. **Financial Constraint:** The researcher encountered financial challenges in executing this project.
2. **Time Constraint:** The task of combining research project with other academic exercise like going to lectures, writing examinations and tests based on the time limited is too

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demanding for the researcher. This is because the time frame for this study is too short to compare to what there is to be done.

3. **Material Constraint:** The research materials within the disposal of the researcher are too infinitesimal to compare to what should be done. For that, the researcher had to visit different libraries in search of materials like textbooks, journals and research of previous studies for the research. It was too stressful sourcing for research materials in different and many libraries.

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References

Abba U.E, Anazodo R.O and Okoye J.C (2004), *Management and Organization Behaviour:*

Theory and Applications in Nigeria. Onitsha Abbot Book Ltd.

Agulanna E.C and Madu C.M (2009), *Organizational Behavior. Human Resources at work.*

Owerri, Reliable Publishers.

Akpanabia N.H. (2015), *Organizational Behaviour: Diagnosing Human Behaviour in*

Organization: Owerri, Last Touch Press.

Allport F.H (2000), *A Struturonmic Concept of Behavior: Individual and Collective Structural*

Theory and Master problem of Social Psychology. Journal of abnormal and Social Psychology.

Anyanwu A (2000), *Research Methods in Business and Social Sciences:* Owerri, Canum

publishers.

Asika N (2008), *Research Methodology in the Behavioural Sciences:* Lagos, Longman Nigeria

Publisher Plc.

Baron R.A (1986), *Behaviour in Organizations: Understanding and Managing the Human side*

of Work. Boston: Allyn and Bacon.

Black G (2000), *Learning Theories.* London, New-List-Books Ltd.

Chukwuma T.O (2014), *Introduction to Business: a Managerial Approach.* Enugu, noble

publishers Ltd.

IMPACT OF GROUP DYNAMICS ON ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE

Coleman J.C (1969), *Psychology and Effective Behaviour*. Glenview, Illinois: Scot and Foresman.

Cushway B and Lodge D (1993), *Organizational Behaviour and Design*, London, Kogan press.

Davis R.C (2000), *The Fundamentals of Top Management*. New York, Harper and Row.

Dembo M.H (2000), *Applying Educational Psychology*, (5th edition). New York, Allyn and Bacon Publishers. www.goodreads.com.

Ebele S.G (1990), *Leadership and Organizational Behavior*. www.nwlink.com.

Ekpendu K.O (2008), *Consumer Attitude and Consumer Behavior*. Journal of business and social sciences. Vol 3, No 1, May.

George C.H (2010), *Social Behavior: A Dynamic Approach for Organization*. www.linkedin.com.

Hatch M.J (1993), *The Dynamics of Organizational Culture*. Academy of management review, 18.

Hicks H.G and f Gullet C.R (1981): *Management*, (4th ed.),

Hinkle J. (2010), *Industrial Organizational Psychology*. New York, Michael Charter publishers.

Johnson W.D (2010), *Students – Students Interaction: The Neglect Variable in Education*. Education Research 10 (1).

Krantz J (1985): *Group Processes Under Conditions of*

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IMPACT OF GROUP DYNAMICS ON ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE

Luthan C.T (2005), *Emerging Positive Organizational Behaviour:*

www.digitalcommons.unl.edu.

Rizo VC (2010), *Behaviourism. Organizational Theory*. London, Norwer Publishers.

Robbins S (2010), *Organizational Behaviour:* New Jersey Prentice Hall.

Robbins S.P (1989), *Organizational Behaviour: Concepts, Controversies and application*. Englewood, Cliffs, NJ, Prentice Hall.

Sayles L.R (1957), *Work Group Behaviour and the Larger Organization* in Arensburg, C (Ed.), *Research In Industrial Relations*. New York: Haper and Row.

Szilagyi A.D (Jnr) and Vallace M.J (Jnr), (1987), *Organizational Behaviour and Performance* (4th ed.), Glenview, Illinois: Scott and Foresman.

Ubah et al (2015), *Practical Approach to Research, Execution in Behavioural Sciences:* Owerri, Last Touch Press Publishers.

Ugwu C. (2007), *Organizational Development: An Introduction*, Enugu, noble publishers ltd.
www.wilderdom.com.

LEARNING STYLES AND STUDENTS' PERFORMANCE IN SHORTHAND

**RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN LEARNING STYLES AND STUDENTS'
PERFORMANCE IN SHORTHAND IN FEDERAL POLYTECHNICS IN NORTH-
WEST ZONE, NIGERIA**

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LEARNING STYLES AND STUDENTS' PERFORMANCE IN SHORTHAND

Abstract

Research Purpose: The study assessed the relationship between learning styles and student's performance in shorthand in federal polytechnics in North-west Zone, Nigeria. The study was guided with five objectives, one research question and four null hypotheses.

Methodology: Co-relational Survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised two hundred and twenty-one (221) ND 1 office technology and management students in Federal polytechnics in North-west Zone, Nigeria in 2021/2022 academic session. The sample was made up of all the two hundred and twenty-one (221) ND1 office technology and management students of four (4) federal polytechnics in North-west Zone, Nigeria. The instruments used to generate data for the study were Perceptual Learning Styles Questionnaire (PLSQ) and 2021/2022 first semester student's examination results in OTM 111-Shorthand Theory I. Frequency and percentages was used to answer the research question, Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to test hypotheses one, two, three, and ANOVA was used to test objective four, all the null hypotheses was tested at 0.05 level of significance. From the result of the study, hypotheses one, two and four were retained while hypothesis three was rejected.

Research Findings: The summary of the study showed that visual and auditory learning styles had no significant relationship with students' performance in shorthand, kinesthetic learning style had significant relationship with students' performance in shorthand and there is no significant difference in the performance of students in shorthand based on their learning styles. It was concluded that adopting the appropriate learning style is paramount to how well a student performs in shorthand.

Recommendations: Based on the findings, four (4) recommendations were made, among which were that shorthand lecturers should consider their students' diverse learning styles and design instructional methods that take care of those diversities and remain sensitive to such during the instruction process and that OTM students should be encouraged to adopt kinesthetic learning style in learning shorthand in federal polytechnic in North-west Zone, Nigeria.

Keywords: Office Technology and Management (OTM), Learning Styles (Visual, Auditory and Kinesthetics) and Students' Performance

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1. Introduction

Office Technology and Management (OTM) formerly known as secretarial studies is an integral part of vocational and technical education where emphasis is placed on acquisition of skills for national development. The National Policy on Education (2004) define Office Technology and Management as an aspect of education which prepares students towards the acquisition of practical and applied skills as well as basic scientific knowledge needed to perform adequately in the world of work. In other words, the programme is focused on production of manpower development. Komalafe & Ajayi (2010) described Office Technology and Management as work oriented educational program which aims at skill acquisition for paid employment, self-reliance, or employer of labour. They went further to say that training in office technology and management involves the acquisition and development of skills, competencies, attitudes, and attributes to be able to function effectively in the millennium office. Office Technology and Management (OTM) curriculum provides training in shorthand skills.

Shorthand is one of the fundamental subjects in Office Technology and Management (OTM). The National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) recognized shorthand as an important Office Technology and Management subject, particularly with regards to the achievement of objective one of National Diploma (ND) Office Technology and Management (OTM), which is “to equip ND graduates with the right skills that will enable them to engage in a life of work in the office as well as for self-employment” (NBTE, 2004). Shorthand system is used to write as quickly as people speak using special symbols to represent words and phrases. Amoor (2014) considered shorthand as any system of writing that is rapid and concise enough to enable the writer to keep pace with normal speech. Usually, strokes, abbreviations and special characters are used to represent letters, words, and phrases. ND graduates having effective shorthand skills are able to listen, focus, organize and attend to details. Some factors affect the learning process which makes mastering of shorthand difficult for students. These factors include learning styles, self-esteem, teaching methods, mood and environment.

Individual learners have different backgrounds, strengths, weaknesses, needs, levels of attitudes, motivations, and approaches to learning. People adopt approaches to learning which they are most comfortable with. Learners also differ in how successfully they respond to, and profit from instructional processes. Among the factors that determine success or failure in learning processes, is the consideration of differences in learning styles. Learning style is defined as the manner and the condition under which learners most efficiently and effectively perceived, process, store and recall what they are attempting to learn. This view was emphasized by Liu (2008) when he defined learning styles as approaches to learning which refer to information

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processed in a preferred way in accordance to a learner's habitual characteristics. Walsh (2011) stated that learning styles are typical approaches or patterns; visual, auditory and kinesthetic, that gives direction to learning behavior. Every individual learns and processes information in different ways. Understanding an individual's learning style preferences help learners to be aware of themselves, their abilities, how they learn, and why they differ from their peers. There are numerous classification of learning styles, however, this study will focus on perceptual learning styles model which classified learning into visual learning style (learning through seeing), auditory learning style (learning through hearing and listening) and Kinesthetic learning style (learning through active engagement in doing or touching).

In skill, related subjects such as shorthand, students' learning styles play an essential role and may influence their learning processes which may eventually affect their academic performance. Performance refers to what students achieve in their studies and how they cope with or accomplish different learning experiences given to them by their teachers. Ibrahim (2011) reported that in educational institutions, success is measured by how well students meet the standards set out by the institutions. All the described variables constitute the background in which this study will be conducted on the relationship between students' learning styles and student's performance in shorthand in federal polytechnics in North-west Zone, Nigeria.

1.1 Problem Statement

Shorthand is one of the core office technology and management subject offered for the attainment of National Diploma. The performances of students in shorthand continued to decline yearly in polytechnics. It was noted by the researcher that only few office technology and management students performed well in shorthand. This poor performance was a major concern of teachers, researchers, and curriculum planners, because if the trend continued unchecked and untreated, students may lose interest in shorthand. Amoor (2014) reported that shorthand and typewriting that involve manipulation, construction and demonstration were losing their values compared to other business subjects like economics, accounting, and marketing to the extent that students were no longer speaking favorably about them. The recurrent poor performance of students in shorthand was disturbing. Vundi, Nasango, and Majanga (2011) have observed that there is a decline in students' performance in shorthand. In confirmation of this statement, the researcher's preliminary investigation of the performance of office technology and management students in shorthand in polytechnics in North-west Zone, Nigeria revealed its poor status.

One of the probable causes of students' poor performance in shorthand may be attributed to the learning styles adopted by the students in learning. Performance is determined by many factors and learning styles may be among them. Vaishnav (2013) established that learning styles

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had significant input on students' performance. However, Tight (2007) reported that students' performance had no significant relationship with their learning styles. There is, therefore, conflicting arguments in the literature on the relationship between learning styles and students' academic performance.

Based on this problem, therefore, the researcher will carry out research on the relationship between learning styles and students' performance in shorthand in federal polytechnics in North-west Zone, Nigeria.

1.2 Objective(s) of the study:

The specific objectives were to:

1. classify office technology and management students into visual, auditory and kinesthetic learners of shorthand in federal polytechnics in North-west Zone, Nigeria
2. assess the relationship between visual learning style and office technology and management students' performance in shorthand in federal polytechnics in North-west Zone, Nigeria
3. investigate the relationship between auditory learning style and office technology and management students' performance in shorthand in federal polytechnics in North-west Zone, Nigeria
4. determine the relationship between kinesthetic learning style and office technology and management students' performance in shorthand in federal polytechnics in North-west Zone, Nigeria
5. establish the difference in the performance of office technology and management students in shorthand who adopt visual learning style, auditory learning style or kinesthetic learning style in federal polytechnics in North-west Zone, Nigeria

1.3 Research Question

1. What is the classification of OTM students into visual, auditory and kinesthetic learning style in learning shorthand in Federal polytechnic in North-west Zone, Nigeria?

1.4 Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between visual learning style and OTM students' performance in shorthand in federal polytechnic in North-west Zone, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant relationship between auditory learning style and OTM students' performance in shorthand in federal polytechnic in North-west Zone, Nigeria.
3. There is no significant relationship between kinesthetic learning style and OTM students' performance in shorthand in federal polytechnic in North-west Zone, Nigeria.

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4. There is no significant difference in the performance of OTM students in shorthand who adopted visual learning style, auditory learning style and kinesthetic learning style in federal polytechnic in North-west Zone, Nigeria.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Concept of Learning Styles

Learning Styles is the way in which each person begins to concentrate on, process, and retain information through different perceptual channels. Pritchard (2009) describe learning styles as an individual's preferred means of acquiring knowledge and skills. It is a person's typical approach to learning activities and problem-solving. Liu (2008) defined Learning Styles as an approach to learning which refers to information processed in a preferred way in accordance with the learner's habitual characteristics. Sarasin (2006) described learning styles as a certainly specified pattern of behavior to which individual approaches a learning experience. The above definitions asserted that learning styles have same characteristics that each learner has a preferred way of learning. Learning Style refers to the preference or disposition of an individual to perceive and process information in a particular way or combination of ways. It is the way individuals process, absorb and retain information or skills, regardless of how that process is described. Jahiel (2008) defines learning styles as the way in which individuals process information and analyze it. He further explains that individuals do not rely on one type of learning styles but some of them have one primary learning style and others have more than one learning style. Individuals observe, process, and analyze the information by using one or more learning styles in order to have a complete comprehension process.

2.2 Learning Style Types/ Models

The perceptual modality approach aspect of Reid's model which categorized learning style into three categories, namely: VAK acronym for Visual, Auditory and Kinesthetic learners was employ for this study.

Visual learning style

A visual learner has a preference for seeing or observing things, including pictures, diagrams, demonstrations, displays, handouts, films, and flip-chart. These people will use phrases such as 'show me', 'let's have a look at that' and will be best able to perform a new task after reading the instructions or watching someone else do it first. These learners absorb information most effectively if it is provided through the visual channel. Thus, they tend to prefer reading tasks and often use colorful highlighting schemes to make certain information visually more salient. In general, visual learners like visual stimulation such as films and videos.

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Liu (2008) is of the opinion that visual learners have a preference for seeing (think in pictures, visual aids like diagrams, overhead slides, and handouts). Visual learners think in pictures and learn best in visual images. They depend on the instructor's or facilitator's non-verbal cues such as body language to help with understanding. Sometimes, visual learners favor sitting in the front of the classroom.

Auditory learning style

According to Pritchard (2009), auditory learners learn best through hearing and listening. They prefer to collect and confirm information via listening. They learn best when the teacher explains orally and when participating in speaking activities. The classroom activities they like to participate in a discussion, debates, role play and problem-solving. They read and talk to self-aloud, discuss ideas verbally with others and recite information over and over to better realize the learning material. They benefit from formal lectures, repetition, questions and sequential presentation. Majority of auditory learners are talkative, conceptual, reflective and memory-oriented. Auditory learners tend to absorb information in a more efficient manner through sounds, discussions, teachings. These individuals will be more likely to record lectures so that they can replay them at a later time for study purposes. They gain knowledge from reading out loud in the classroom and may not have a full understanding of the information that is written.

Kinesthetic learning style

Kinesthetic (K) learners (also known as tactile learners) use body movements and bodily sensations to learn. Tactile/kinesthetic learners have learning preference for experience, moving, touching and doing. Dunn & Dunn (2008) defines the kinesthetic style as having "to do with the physical experience of touching, feeling, holding, doing, and practical hands-on experience. The learner prefers kinesthetic stimulation for learning to occur". Furthermore, Pritchard (2009) detailed that these learners prefer hands-on activities such as experiments and practice, and they depend on self-study techniques when they learn or recall information. They favor interaction with the physical world.

3. Methodology

Co-relational Survey research design was adopted for the study. The design establishes the relationship that exists between two or more variables. The population of the study comprised of two hundred and twenty one (221) ND1 Office Technology and Management (OTM) students in federal polytechnics in North-west Zone, Nigeria in the 2021/2022 academic session. The sample size was made up of the entire two hundred and twenty one (221) ND1 office technology and management students of Federal Polytechnic Kaduna, Federal Polytechnic Kaura Namoda,

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Waziri Umaru Federal Polytechnic Birnin Kebbi and Federal Polytechnic Daura in North-west Zone, Nigeria. Purposive sampling technique was used in selecting the four (4) federal polytechnics because of their peculiar characteristics. Two instruments were used for data collection. The first instrument is Perceptual Learning Styles Questionnaire (PLSQ) adapted from Reid (1987) Learning Styles Questionnaire. The questionnaires assess the preferred learning styles of the students based on how they learn best using their perceptions (Visual, Auditory and Kinesthetic) preferences. The second instrument for the study was the 2021/2022 first semester Office Technology and Management (OTM) student's examination results in OTM 111- Shorthand Theory I. The data was obtained from the departmental record office of each federal polytechnic. In the first stage of the data collection, the researcher administers the Perceptual Learning Styles Questionnaire (PLSQ) to the ND 1 office technology and management students in the four federal polytechnics. In the next stage of the data collection, the researcher collected 2021/2022 ND 1 Office Technology and Management (OTM) student's academic performance in shorthand from the head of the department in the four federal polytechnics in north-west zone, Nigeria. The researcher employs the service of four research assistants in the data collection. The data collection lasted for a period of 10 months. The data collected were subjected to statistical analysis. Objective one and research question one was answered using frequency and percentages, objectives and null hypotheses two, three and four were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient (PPMC), and ANOVA was used to test objective five, all the hypothesis were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

4. Result

Table 1: Classification of OTM Students Based on their Learning Styles

Learning Styles	POLYTECHNIC				Frequency	Percentage
	FPDRA	FPAKN	KAD POLY	WUFPBK		
Visual	08	12	43	06	69	31
Auditory	06	09	32	05	52	24
Kinesthetics	15	18	55	12	100	45
Total	29	39	130	23	221	100

Source: Field Work, 2023

The analysis in Table 1 indicated that 69 students (31%) adopted visual learning style, 52(24%) adopted auditory learning style and 100 (45%) adopted kinesthetic learning style. This implies that OTM students adopted all the three (3) learning style in learning shorthand, with those students who adopted kinesthetic learning style as the majority.

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Table 2: PPMC Test of Relationship between Visual Learning Style and OTM Students' Performance in Shorthand

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	r-crit	r-cal	Sig.	Decision
Visual learning style	3.19	0.39	0.195	-0.019	0.838	Retained
Academic performance	46.09	15.15				

Source: Field Work, 2023

The analysis of data in Table 2 used to test null hypothesis one revealed the r-cal value of -0.019. The probability value of 0.838 obtained was greater than the 0.05 level of significance. This meant that there was no significant relationship between visual learning style and OTM students' performance in shorthand in the federal polytechnics North-west Zone, Nigeria. The hypothesis was therefore retained.

Table 3: PPMC Test of Relationship between Auditory Learning Style and OTM Students' Performance in Shorthand

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	r-crit	r-cal	Sig.	Decision
Auditory learning style	3.19	0.49	0.195	-0.188	0.055	Retain
Academic performance	46.41	15.32				

Source: Field Work, 2023

The analysis in Table 3 revealed a calculated r-value of -0.188 with a probability value of 0.055 found to be greater than 0.05 level of significance. The result, therefore, indicated that there was no significant relationship between auditory learning style and performance of OTM students in shorthand in federal polytechnics in North-west Zone, Nigeria. The hypothesis was therefore retained.

Table 4: PPMC Test of Relationship between Kinesthetic Learning Style and OTM Students' Performance in Shorthand

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	r-crit	r-cal	Sig.	Decision
Kinesthetic learning	3.29	0.43	0.195	0.167	0.045	Rejected
Academic performance	50.72	16.37				

Source: Field Work, 2023

The result of analysis of data used to test null hypothesis three revealed a calculated r-cal of 0.167 with a probability of 0.045, less than the alpha value of 0.05. The result showed that there was a significant relationship between kinesthetic learning style and performance of OTM

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students in shorthand in federal polytechnics in North-west Zone, Nigeria. The hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Table 5: ANOVA of Test of Variance between Performances of OTM Students in Shorthand Based on their Learning Styles

Variable	Sum of square	Df	Mean squares	F-cal	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	25.296	2	12.648			
Groups	85757.847	218	237.556	0.53	0.948	Retained
Total	85783.143	220				

Source: Field Work, 2023

In Table 5, a one-way between groups ANOVA was conducted to compare the differences in the performance of OTM students who adopted visual, auditory and kinesthetic learning style. The result showed that there was no significant difference in the performance of the students based on the three learning styles. The f- calculated of 0.53 with a P-value of 0.948 was greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis was retained.

5. Discussion of Findings

The finding of test of null hypothesis one showed that there was no significant relationship between visual learning style and OTM students' performance in shorthand. The finding was in agreement with that of Khalid (2013) who reported that there was no significant relationship between visual learning styles and students' academic achievement. Gappi (2013) indicated that there was no significant correlation between visual learning style and academic achievement of students. In contrast, Remaliet al (2013) reported a significant relationship between visual learning style and students' academic performance in English. Similarly, Vaishnav (2013) stated that visual learning style had a significant relationship with students' academic success.

The outcome of this study indicated that there was no significant relationship between auditory learning style and OTM students' performance in shorthand. The finding was in agreement with that of Gokalp (2013) who found no significant relationship between the academic performance of students and the auditory learning style. Also, Albina (2013) reported that there was no significant relationship between students' academic achievement and auditory learning style. Some authors reported findings that indicated contrary views to those stated above. Esia-Donkoh, Eshun, and Acquye (2015) confirmed that there was a significant relationship between auditory learning style and academics performance of students. The finding of Vaishnav

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(2013) also showed that there existed a significant relationship between auditory learning style and students' academic achievement.

The outcome of the study indicated that there was a significant relationship between kinesthetic learning style and OTM students' performance in shorthand. This finding was in agreement with that of the Oommen (2015) who reported that there is a significant correlation between kinesthetic learning style and academic achievement of secondary school students. Njoku and Abdulhamid (2016) also reported a significant relationship between kinesthetic learning style and students' academic performance. In contrast, Khan and Iqbal (2012) found that kinesthetic learning style and academic achievement were not significantly correlated. Similarly, Ariffin et al (2014) found no significant relationship between kinesthetic learning style and students' academic performance.

Finally, this study revealed that there was no significant difference in the performances of OTM students in shorthand based on their learning styles (visual, auditory and kinesthetic). The finding was in line with that of Abdulkadir and Din (2006) who reported that there was no significant difference between the performance of students who adopted visual, auditory and kinesthetic learning style. Similarly, Ibe (2015) stated in his report that there were no significant differences in the mean score of student in biology who adopted different (visual, auditory or kinesthetic) learning styles. There were reports of findings that indicated contrary views to those stated above. Walsh (2011) reported that a significant difference existed in the academic performance of students based on their adopted learning styles. Similarly, Vaishnav (2013) reported a significant difference between the performance of students who adopted visual, auditory and kinesthetic learning style.

6. Conclusion

Based on the stated objectives that the research work addressed, the researcher concluded that shorthand students who want to perform excellently cannot do without being informed about their learning styles. This is because it has been revealed that learning styles have a relationship with students' performance in shorthand. The inference of the study is that students who adopted kinesthetic learning style in learning shorthand tend to perform better.

The findings of the study clearly established that students who adopted the kinesthetic learning style performed better in shorthand. However, students who adopted visual or auditory learning style may not do as well as those who adopted kinesthetic learning style in shorthand. It was therefore concluded that adopting the appropriate learning style is paramount to how well a student performs in shorthand.

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7. Recommendations

1. Shorthand Lecturers should consider their students' diverse learning styles and design instructional methods that take care of those diversities and remain sensitive to such during the instruction process.
2. Shorthand students who adopt visual learning style should consider another learning style that is more compatible with learning shorthand.
3. Shorthand students who adopt auditory learning style should consider another learning style that is more compatible with learning shorthand.
4. OTM students should be encouraged to adopt a kinesthetic learning style in learning shorthand.

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References

- Abdulkadir, R., & Din, R. (2006). Computer-mediated communication: A motivational strategy toward diverse learning style. *Journal Pendidikan*, 31(2), 41-51.
- Albina A.P. (2013). Learning styles and academic achievement of high school students'. *International Journal of Scientific Research*. 2(6), 38-40.
- Amoor, S.S. (2014). *Determinants of colleges of education business education students' choice of office technology and management option in North-west geo-political Zone, Nigeria*. (Unpublished doctoral dissertation) Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria.
- Ariffin I., Solomon B., Din M. Md. & Anwar R. Md. (2014). Learning styles and course performance: An empirical study of United IT students. *International Journal of Asian Social Science* 4(2): 208-216.
- Dunn, R., & Dunn, K. (2008).). Some students learning style particularities. *Annal University of Oradea*, 16(2), 108-114.
- Esia-Donkoh, K., Eshun E.S., & Acquaya V.N.A. (2015). Learning styles and factors affecting learning: Perception of 2013/2014 final year post-diploma sandwich students of the department of basic education, University of education. Winneba, Ghana. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*, 2(5), 55-76. DOI: 10.14738/assrj.25.1099.
- Gokalp, M. (2013). The effect of students' learning styles to their academic Success. *Creative Educational Journal*, 4(10), 627-632.
- Ibe N. (2015). Effects of learning styles on the performances of senior secondary school students in biology. *International Multidisciplinary Journal*, 9(1), 214-227.
- Ibrahim, S. (2011). *Impact of accounting background, gender, and motivation on the performance of business education in introductory accounting in federal universities Nigeria* (Unpublished doctorate dissertation). Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria.
- Jahiel, J. (2008). What's your Learning Styles? *Journal of Practical Horseman*, 36(3), 32-37.
- Khalid, A.H. (2013). The learning styles and academic achievements among arts and science stream students'. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 2(2), 2226-6348.

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- Khan S. & Iqbal M.J. (2013). Effect of learning style on the achievement of distance learners. *The Dialogue* 11(3), 6-12.
- Komolafe, I.A. & Ajayi, S.T. (2010), Office Technology and Management Curriculum: Issues, Strategies and Rationale, Secretarial Forum, *Journal for the Promotion/Advancement of Secretarial Profession*, Federal Polytechnic, Ede.
- Liu, H. (2008). A study of the interrelationship between listening strategy use, listening proficiency levels, and learning style, *RARECLS Journal*, 5, 84-104.
- Njoku, J.A. & Abdulhamid, B. (2016). Preference of learning styles and its relationship with academic performance among junior secondary school students in Dutse local government area, Jigawa state, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Practice*. 4(3), 127-133.
- Oommen, N.M (2015). Learning styles and academic achievement in the biology of secondary school students. *International Journal of Current Research*, 7(8), 19818-19820.
- Pritchard, A. (2009). *Ways of Learning: Learning Theories and Learning Styles in the Classroom*. Second Edition: Routledge.
- Remali, A.M., Ghazali, M.A., Kamaruddin, M.K. & Kee, T.Y. (2013). Understanding academic performance based on demographic factors, motivational factors, and learning styles. *International Journal of Asian Social science*, 3(9), 1938-1951.
- Sarasin, L. (Ed). (2006). *Learning Style Perspectives: Impact in the Classroom*. Madison: Atwood Publication.
- Tight, D. (2007). *The Role of Perceptual Learning Style Preferences and Instructional Method in the Acquisition of L2 Spanish Vocabulary*. (Doctoral dissertation, University of Minnesota). Retrieved from ProQuest Dissertations and theses: full-Text database. UMI NO.3260530.
- Vaishnav S.R. (2013). Learning styles and academic achievement of secondary school students. *Voice of Research Journal*, 1(4), 1-4. ISSN No. 2277-7733.
- Vundi, S.K., Nasongo, J.W., & Majanga, E. (2011). Influence of teachers and students' attitude towards performance in shorthand in technical training. *Current Research Journal of Social Science*. 3(2), 59-65.
- Walsh, B. (2011). *Visual, Auditory, and Kinesthetic Communication and Learning Styles*. New York: Wash Seminars Publishing House.

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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON SMALL BUSINESS PERFORMANCE

Effect of Artificial Intelligence on Small Business Performance in Enugu Metropolis

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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON SMALL BUSINESS PERFORMANCE**Abstract**

Research Purpose: This study focused on the effect of artificial intelligence on small business performance in Enugu metropolis. The specific objectives are to ascertain the effect of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies on revenue growth of small businesses in Enugu Metropolis and assess the effect of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies on operational efficiency of small businesses in Enugu Metropolis.

Methodology: The population of the study comprised 136 of small business owners and staff of small businesses in Enugu metropolis while Taro Yamane formula was used to determine the sample size of 103. The data was analyzed with simple percentage analysis while all the hypotheses were tested with Simple Linear regression at 0.05 alpha level.

Research Findings: The research made the following findings: that Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies have positive effect on revenue growth of small businesses in Enugu Metropolis ($R^2=0.431$, $p=0.000$). The study revealed that Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies have positive effect on operational efficiency of small businesses in Enugu Metropolis ($R^2=0.455$, $p=0.000$).

Conclusion: The study concluded that effect of artificial intelligence on small business performance in Enugu has been significant. AI has enabled businesses to streamline their operations, improve efficiency, and reduce costs.

Recommendations: It was recommended among others; that to maximize the benefits of AI, it is recommended that small businesses invest in AI tools and technologies, prioritize employee training and education on AI, and collaborate with other businesses to share knowledge and resources. By doing so, small businesses can improve their performance and stay competitive in a rapidly evolving market.

Keyword: Artificial intelligence, small business, revenue growth, Operational efficiency

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1.1 Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) has been around for decades, but it wasn't until recently that it became a major player in the business sector. The history of AI in business dates back to the 1950s, when researchers began exploring the concept of machine learning (Bag, Gupta, Kumar and Sivarajah, 2021). However, it wasn't until the 1980s that artificial intelligence started to become more prevalent in businesses. In the early days, artificial intelligence was primarily used for automating repetitive tasks and improving efficiency. Today, artificial intelligence (AI) has become increasingly popular among small businesses. With the advancement of technology and the availability of data, artificial intelligence is capable of taking over certain existing tasks in place of humans with greater accuracy and efficiency. Due to the enhanced performance capability provided by automation tools, their implementation is proving beneficial for small business operations across many industries (Belhadi, Mani, Kamble, Khan and Verma, 2021).

With relatively low investment costs compared to large corporations or enterprises due to readily available resources such as cloud computing, which provides ample capacity on demand, and open source technologies offering easier access than ever before, adopting artificial intelligence can be made more accessible even if financial constraints make it difficult otherwise (Chaudhuri, Chatterjee, Vrontis and Thrassou, 2021). Using application programming interfaces (APIs) also contributes towards lower costs, making it possible for small businesses that could benefit from machine learning models without having expert knowledge within their project teams to potentially benefit significantly at a discounted price point, including faster execution timeframes (Cui, Xiao and Zhang, 2021).

The rapid evolution of artificial intelligence brings small businesses more business opportunities (Hughes et al., 2020; Obschonka and Audretsch, 2020; Shareef et al., 2021). Artificial intelligence is the machines (programs) that operates in the simulation of human intelligence (Łapińska et al., 2021) in technologies, such as machine learning, data mining, natural language processing, image recognition, etc. (Khalid, 2020). Artificial intelligence can bring efficiency gains, cost savings, product quality improvements, and customer service improvements (Bag et al., 2021c). Enterprise capabilities are critical for identifying business opportunities (Yao et al., 2021). While there is excellent potential for artificial intelligence capability (AIC) to improve a company's performance (Mikalef and Gupta, 2021), there are also significant challenges to small businesses applying artificial intelligence (Yu et al., 2021). Businesses can utilize artificial intelligence to improve the customer service experience by offering more appropriate recommendations and less costly options (Payne et al., 2021). According to the resource-based view, artificial intelligence's applied capability is an ensemble of implicit resources (Bag et al., 2021). These resources include supporting resources, labor skills, and organizational coordination (Selz, 2020). Once a firm masters organizing resources that are impossible to copy effortlessly, it possesses a competitive advantage (Yasmin et al.,

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2020) and enhances firm performance (Chen and Lin, 2021). Therefore, there is an essential theoretical and practical value in exploring the mechanisms and critical factors of the impact of AIC on small business performance (Chen and Lin, 2021; Mikalef et al., 2021). There seems to be interesting studies on the impact of AI and its capability on business performance appears (Denicolai et al., 2021; Mikalef and Gupta, 2021). The existing literature dedicated to the study of the impact of AI on industries, such as banking and finance (Huynh et al., 2020), manufacturing (Bag et al., 2021c), automated retailing (Pillai et al., 2020), logistics (Chien et al., 2020), marketing (Keegan et al., 2022), coaching services (Kim et al., 2021b), and customer relationship management (Chatterjee et al., 2021a), among other areas. In comparison, these studies concentrated on the impact of AI on firm innovation processes and management practices, technological innovation (Liu et al., 2020a), and the relationship between artificial intelligence learning and entrepreneurial performance (Khalid, 2020). However, little is known about the effect of artificial intelligence on small businesses in Enugu State. Most of the previous studies on the subject of artificial intelligence and business performance are foreign based. Therefore, in order to fill up this gap, the study aimed to examine effect of artificial intelligence on small business performance in Enugu metropolis.

1.2 Statement of Problem

The rise of artificial intelligence has brought about significant changes in various industries, including small businesses. While artificial intelligence has the potential to improve efficiency and productivity, it also poses a threat to small business performance. This issue is crucial as small businesses are the backbone of many economies worldwide. Understanding how AI impacts their performance will help policymakers and business owners make informed decisions regarding its implementation and adoption. However, small businesses in Enugu face a number of challenges when integrating artificial intelligence into their operations. Limited knowledge and understanding of artificial intelligence technology limits the ability of small business owners to identify viable solutions leveraging the power of artificial intelligence, while limited resources can make it difficult for them to implement solutions that require expensive data infrastructure or dedicated staff members with expertise.

Additionally, many small businesses lack access to adequate funding sources necessary for making significant investments in software development and IT staffing; this leaves most entrepreneurs unable to leverage advancements coming from more sophisticated tech states such as Silicon Valley. Meanwhile, the fear of change is another obstacle facing these businesses; successfully implementing new technologies requires both trust and an acceptance that times are changing – something not always easy for those comfortable with traditional methods. Nonetheless, with the existing literatures on the impact of artificial intelligence on businesses, it is importance to examine how adoption of artificial intelligence affects small business performance in Enugu metropolis.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

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The broad objective of this study is to examine effect of artificial intelligence on small business performance in Enugu metropolis. However, the specific objectives of the study are to:

- i. To ascertain effect of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies on revenue growth of small businesses in Enugu Metropolis.
- ii. Assess the effect of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies on operational efficiency of small businesses in Enugu Metropolis.

1.4 Research Questions

In line with the objectives of the study, the following research questions were put forward:

- i. What is the effect of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies on revenue growth of small businesses in Enugu Metropolis?
- ii. What is the effect of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies on operational efficiency of small businesses in Enugu Metropolis?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

In line with the objectives and research questions, the following hypotheses were put forward for test:

- H₀₁: Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies have no positive effect on revenue growth of small businesses in Enugu Metropolis.
- H₀₂: Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies have no positive effect on operational efficiency of small businesses in Enugu Metropolis.

1.6 Significance of the Study

The study on the effect of artificial intelligence on small business performance is significant in today's world. With the rise of AI technology, small businesses need to understand how it can impact their operations and bottom line. This study provides valuable insights into the benefits and challenges of implementing AI in small businesses. It also highlights the importance of adapting to technological advancements to stay competitive in the market. By understanding how AI can improve efficiency, productivity, and customer experience, small businesses can make informed decisions about incorporating this technology into their operations.

1.7 Scope of the Study

The study focuses on effect of artificial intelligence on small business performance in Enugu metropolis. The scope of the study comprises of area geographical and time scope.

Area Scope: The study will be limited to the independent and dependent variable. The independent variable to be used is: Artificial Intelligence while the dependent variables include revenue growth and operational efficiency.

Geographical Scope: This study will be carried out in Enugu metropolis which comprises Enugu North and Enugu South of Enugu State, Nigeria with focus on the businesses situated in these areas. The choice of these areas is chosen due to easy access to collect vital information that will aid this study. However, this study covers the period 2022 between 2023.

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2 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Framework

2.1.1 Artificial Intelligence (AI)

From the very beginning of computer science, researchers like Alan Turing considered the possibility for a computer to play chess, as a test of the machine's intelligence. Thus, he published "Intelligent Machinery" in 1948 and "Computing Machinery and Intelligence" in 1950, both of which will inspire future scientific research in AI (Turing, 2009). Literally, AI means the use of technological devices aimed at reproducing the cognitive abilities of humans to achieve objectives autonomously, taking into account any constraints that may be encountered (Haenlein & Kaplan, 2019).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is the ability of machines to perform tasks that typically require human intelligence, such as learning, reasoning, and problem-solving (Vrontis, et al., 2021). AI systems are designed to mimic human cognitive functions and can be classified into three categories: rule-based systems, machine learning systems, and natural language processing systems. Rule-based systems use a set of predefined rules to make decisions, while machine learning systems learn from data and improve their performance over time (Rana, Chatterjee, Dwivedi, and Akter, 2021).

Thus, artificial intelligence (AI) is an area of computer science that emphasizes the development of intelligent machines that work and reacts like humans (Obschonka and Audretsch, 2020). AI focuses on creating systems that have access to data, can recognise patterns in said data, and use logic-based methods to come up with solutions or recommendations. Examples of artificial intelligence include natural language processing, expert systems, robotics process automation, machine learning algorithms, deep learning networks and autonomous vehicles (Lou and Wu, 2021).

Meanwhile, AI has numerous applications in various fields such as business, healthcare, finance, and transportation. Scholars have argued that Artificial intelligence (AI) has revolutionized the way businesses operate (Liu, Lee, and Chen, 2020b; Łapińska, et al., 2021). It has enabled companies to automate processes, analyze data, and make informed decisions quickly. AI-powered chatbots have improved customer service, while predictive analytics have helped businesses forecast demand and optimize supply chains. Machine learning algorithms have also been used to detect fraud and improve cybersecurity (Kim, 2019). However, the integration of AI in business operations raises ethical concerns such as job displacement and bias in decision-making. Nonetheless, with proper regulation and responsible implementation, AI can significantly enhance business productivity and competitiveness in the global market (Ferreira, Coelho & Moutinho, 2020).

2.1.2 Revenue Growth

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Revenue is the total amount of money earned by a business from the sale of goods or services (Zhang, Song, and He, 2020). It is an essential element in determining a company's financial health and growth potential. Revenue can be calculated by multiplying the price of each unit sold by the number of units sold, or through other methods such as subscriptions or advertising. Revenue growth is a key indicator of a company's financial health and success. It refers to the increase in a company's total revenue over time, typically measured on an annual basis (Yu, et al., 2021).

Revenue growth is calculated by comparing revenues or sales from one period of time to another, usually expressed as a percentage. Companies track their revenue growth rate in order to monitor and compare it against industry averages or competitor numbers, helping them assess the health of their business and make important business decisions such as investing in new product development or expanding into new markets (Mostafiz, Hughes, , and Sambasivan, 2021).

Revenue growth is important for several reasons. Firstly, it allows companies to invest in research and development, expand their operations, and hire more employees. Secondly, it can attract investors who are looking for companies with strong financial performance and potential for future growth. Finally, revenue growth is often used as a benchmark for measuring a company's success against its competitors. However, revenue growth should not be pursued at the expense of profitability or sustainability. Companies must ensure that their revenue growth strategies align with their long-term goals and values. By balancing revenue growth with responsible business practices, companies can achieve sustainable success while also contributing to the greater good of society (Metawa, Elhoseny and Mutawea, 2021).

In recent years, small businesses have shown significant growth potential due to technological advancements and increased access to funding. However, challenges such as competition, regulatory compliance, and market volatility continue to hinder their growth. To overcome these challenges, Yasmin, et al., (2020) suggested that small businesses need to adopt innovative strategies such as digital marketing, diversification of product lines, and effective cost management. With the right approach and support from stakeholders, small businesses can achieve sustainable revenue growth and contribute significantly to economic prosperity.

2.1.3 Operational efficiency

Operational efficiency is the ability of an organization to utilize its resources effectively and efficiently to achieve its objectives. It involves optimizing processes, reducing waste, and maximizing productivity while minimizing costs (Yao, et al., 2021). In another study, Baldegger, Caon and Sadiku (2020) sees operational efficiency as the measure of how well an organization can convert inputs (resources) into outputs (products and services). This includes improving processes, utilizing technology to reduce costs or increasing employee productivity. It helps organizations stay competitive in their industry by providing better quality products faster with less resources used. Businesses use operational efficiency as a way to lower prices

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for customers while keeping up profits without sacrificing service standards. Examples of activities that increase operational efficiencies include streamlining operations, automating manual tasks, reducing waste through process improvements and leveraging vendors for best pricing on materials (Chen and Siau, 2020).

Operational efficiency is essential for organizations to remain competitive in today's fast-paced business environment. To achieve operational efficiency, organizations must focus on continuous improvement by identifying areas that need improvement and implementing strategies to address them. This can involve streamlining processes, eliminating redundancies, automating tasks, and investing in technology (Armour, and Sako, 2020).

Operational efficiency also requires effective management of resources such as time, money, and personnel (Akpan, Udoh and Adebisi, 2020). Organizations must ensure that they have the right people with the right skills in the right positions to achieve their goals. Thus, operational efficiency is critical for organizations to succeed in today's competitive business environment. By optimizing processes, reducing waste, maximizing productivity while minimizing costs, and managing resources effectively; organizations can improve their bottom line while delivering high-quality products or services to their customers.

2.2 Theoretical Review

This study is anchored by Resource-based View (RBV). This theory serves a useful theoretical framework for understanding small business performance in relation to AI usage because it highlights the ability to gain competitive advantages from exploiting scarce or unique sources within an organization. Based on this view, strategic application of AI technology has been found to allow businesses to exploit internal capabilities and thus increase effectiveness in examining customer purchase patterns and changing market trends.

The RBV believes that essential resources determine firm performance (Chatterjee et al., 2021b). Resources can be tangible and intangible assets within an organization (Mikalef and Gupta, 2021). According to this theory, valuable, rare, inimitable, and irreplaceable resources can build a competitive advantage by creating value and improving firm performance (Ghasemaghaei, 2021). Such an advantage can persist over a long period (Bag et al., 2021c). Businesses can raise the value of their resources because the combined value of the complementary resources is higher than the sum of each resource (Ghasemaghaei, 2021; Mikalef et al., 2021).

Artificial intelligence capability is increasingly a critical and intangible resource for business performance advancement (Belhadi et al., 2021; Lou and Wu, 2021). It suggests that artificial intelligence may bring a competitive advantage to businesses (Chaudhuri et al., 2021). AIC can deliver businesses access to valuable, rare, inimitable, and irreplaceable resources (Ghasemaghaei, 2021). Many studies have deemed "firm capability" as a mediator between resources and firm performance (Belhadi et al., 2021; Lou and Wu, 2021; Mikalef and Gupta, 2021). Firm capabilities are vital attributes required for business operations (Yao et al., 2021).

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These capabilities help deploy other necessary resources to improve firm performance (Yao et al., 2021).

2.3 Empirical Review

Elegunde and Shotunde (2020) examined the effects of artificial intelligence on business performance. Data collected were analyzed with regression analysis. The findings shows that customer satisfaction, service quality, competitive advantage and employees' efficiency; as nonfinancial business measures were all discovered and proven to be aided by artificial intelligence. Findings aligned with previous related studies on artificial intelligence (although which centered on financial objectives), and its effect on business. The R² value of 0.574, 0.445, 0.295 and 0.386 explained the level of variation in each of the sampled variables explained by AI.

Wisskirchen et al. (2017) conducted a study entitled Artificial Intelligence and Robotics and Their Impact on the Workplace. The study was able to discuss legal, economic, and business issues, such as changes in the future labour market and corporate structures, their effects on working hours, remuneration, and the working environment, new forms of employment, and the effects of work relationships. The study was able to determine the risks and opportunities of artificial intelligence. As for the risks, the study acknowledged that AI will have short-term disadvantages. They posited this, saying that tens of millions of jobs worldwide are under threat and that there may be no job opportunities in other sectors for these workers because they are not adequately trained to work efficiently and effectively in a new environment. With the introduction of more and more new machines and intelligent IT systems, people are becoming increasingly irrelevant to their jobs.

Another related study was done by Soni et al. (2018) on the impact of artificial intelligence on business. The study focused on innovation, with artificial intelligence serving as the talking point. The paper tries to answer why every company wants to be an AI company or acquire an AI company. The study also tries to answer the question of why the use of AI has increased exponentially. The paper attempts to answer these questions by searching a range of business newsletters, AI magazines, journal articles, conference articles, machine learning articles, company annual reports, press releases, stock market websites, online forums, and many other platforms to collect the data necessary for their investigations.

According to a study conducted by Accenture (2020), AI adoption in small businesses can lead to a 40% increase in revenue. The study states that AI can help small businesses gain a competitive advantage by improving customer engagement, reducing costs, and increasing productivity. Another study by the National Small Business Association found that AI implementation can lead to a 72% increase in customer satisfaction.

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However, some studies have found that AI adoption in small businesses may not have a significant impact on performance. A study by Frost and Sullivan (2019) found that small businesses may not have the resources to implement AI effectively, leading to limited impact on performance. Another study by Forbes found that AI adoption in small businesses may not be cost-effective and may not provide a significant return on investment.

2.4 Summary of empirical Review

The empirical literature on the relationship between artificial intelligence (AI) and small business performance is limited but growing. Studies have found that access to AI technology can result in a variety of benefits, such as increased efficiency, improved customer service, greater productivity gains, better decision-making capabilities, more accurate analytics and forecasting models, cost savings associated with automation of administrative tasks, more effective risk management strategies, and the ability to tap into new markets or reposition in existing ones. Additionally, advanced cognitive computing platforms are enabling businesses to gain deeper insights from data at faster rates than ever before. Despite these potential opportunities for smaller companies adopting AI technologies, they face considerable challenges due to limitations such as budget constraints and a lack of technical expertise, often arising from their size or concentration of resources within larger competitors' operations. Various studies show that organisations should aim for less ambitious projects and focus on goals related directly to response time improvement or solving specific problems using approaches that provide quick returns instead of long-term strategic advantages. Overall concerns about investment risks still need to be addressed by further research.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The descriptive survey research design was utilised in the study. This strategy was chosen because it allows the researcher to sample people's opinions and collect current information from respondents.

3.2 Sources of Data

The sources of data for this study include both primary and secondary sources.

3.2.1 Primary data

The primary source of data to be used in this study was generated through the aid of structured questionnaire. This is used when a researcher intends to generate data directly from respondents without relying on pre-existing data sources.

3.2.2 Secondary data

Secondary data are historical in character and were acquired through studying relevant literatures such as journals and articles, books, conference papers, and the internet. The

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literature review was completed in order to provide the reader with a comprehensive picture of the study based on previously available material.

3.3 Population of the Study

The population of the study is made up of the small business owners and staff of small businesses in Enugu metropolis. The study randomly selected 136 respondents which comprises both business owners and staff of small businesses in Enugu metropolis

3.4 Sample Size Determination

In determining the sample size, the researcher used Taro Yamane formula (1967) of sample size determination as follows:

Formula

$$\begin{aligned}
 n &= \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} \\
 &= \frac{136}{1+136(0.05)^2} \\
 &= \frac{136}{1+136(0.0025)} \\
 &= \frac{136}{1+0.34} \\
 &= \frac{136}{1.34} = 101.5
 \end{aligned}$$

Approximately, the sample size is 102

However, the researcher used convenience sampling technique to selected small business owners and staff at each visit to small business outlets in Enugu metropolis.

3.5 Method of Data Analyses

A descriptive method was used and descriptive statistics has to do with presenting the data collected and the correlation of the variables i.e. the degree of the relationship existing between two variables so as to explain the data (Offredy & Vickers, 2010). However, linear regression will be used in testing the hypotheses. This will be done with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software ver.22 to fully analyze the data by coding the items and entering them into the SPSS for analyses.

Decision Rule: Accept H_a if the calculated p-value < .01.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

4.1 Presentation of Data

The presentation of acquired data entails presenting the various kinds of data obtained via various data collection procedures in order for the researcher to undertake analysis and derive new meaning from it. The copies of questionnaire administered were 102 representing (100%)

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from which 101 (99.1%) were returned, while 1 representing (0.9%) were not returned. The 101 copies of questionnaire that were returned were considered adequate enough for making valid deductions and conclusions. Hence, the research analysis was based on the returned copies of questionnaire.

Table 1: Mean Rating of Responses of Respondents on the effect of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies on revenue growth of small businesses in Enugu Metropolis

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	U	D	SD	N	FX	\bar{X}	Decision
1	The use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies has improved the overall revenue growth of small businesses in Enugu Metropolis.	49	21	1	3	27	101	365	3.6	Accepted
2	Utilizing AI technologies have been profitable to small businesses based in Enugu Metropolis.	21	52	10	15	3	101	376	3.7	Accepted
3	Considering the cost incurred to implement AI solutions for business operations; it is worth noting an increase in profits as a result.	58	31	3	2	7	101	433	4.3	Accepted
4	I believe investing resources towards adapting and implementing AI technology will benefit the economic welfare of my business.	26	48	1	18	8	101	369	3.6	Accepted
Total	Mean								3.8	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Table 1 above shows the mean mark calculated from the response of the respondents on the effect of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies on revenue growth of small businesses in Enugu Metropolis. Based on the decision rule, that if \bar{x} is below 2.5 it is considered rejected and if \bar{x} is 2.5 and above it is considered accepted. However, all the items in the table were accepted because they score the mean score of 2.5 and the overall mean is 3.8 it therefore indicates that Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies affect revenue growth of small businesses in Enugu Metropolis.

Table 2: Mean Rating of Responses of Respondents on the effect Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies on operational efficiency of small businesses in Enugu Metropolis

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	U	D	SD	N	FX	\bar{X}	Decision
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1	AI technologies improve the operational efficiency of running businesses	55	2 1	2	4	19	10 1	39 2	3.8	Accepted
2	The use of AI technology contributes to increasing bottom-line profitability for small business owners	26	5 1	9	1 2	3	10 1	38 8	3.8	Accepted
3	The adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies reduced operating costs and improved customer satisfaction for small businesses	39	4 9	1 0	2	1	10 1	42 6	4.2	Accepted
4	In comparison with other traditional methods, AI contribute to an increase in turnaround time among businesses within Enugu metropolis	52	1 9	7	1 5	8	10 1	39 5	3.9	Accepted
Total	Mean								4.1	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Table 2 above shows the mean mark calculated from the response of the respondents on the effect Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies on operational efficiency of small businesses in Enugu Metropolis. Based on the decision rule, that if \bar{x} is below 2.5 it is considered rejected and if \bar{x} is 2.5 and above it is considered accepted. However, all the items in the table were accepted because they score the mean score of 2.5 and the overall mean is 4.1 it therefore indicates that Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies affect operational efficiency of small businesses in Enugu Metropolis

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis One

H₀: Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies have no positive effect on revenue growth of small businesses in Enugu Metropolis

H_i: Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies have positive effect on revenue growth of small businesses in Enugu Metropolis

Table 3: The Effect of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies on revenue growth of small businesses

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.656	.431	.424	.41126	.431	68.798	1	91	.000

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1	.674 ^a	.455	.449	.40249	.455	75.838	1	91	.000
Model		Sum of Squares		df	Mean Square		F	Sig.	
1	Regression	12.286		1	12.286		75.838	.00	
	Residual	14.742		118	.162			0 ^b	
	Total			119					
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.		
		B	Std. Error	Beta					
1	(Constant)	1.504	.236			6.379	.000		
	Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies	.508	.058	.674		8.709	.000		

a. Dependent variable: Operational efficiency

Table 4 revealed that Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies affect operational efficiency by a variance of 45.5% ($R^2=0.455$, $p=0.000$). This rejects the null hypothesis that Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies have no positive effect on operational efficiency of small businesses in Enugu Metropolis and upholds the alternative hypothesis. Furthermore, the study found that the regression model was the best fit for predicting the effect of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies on operational efficiency of small businesses ($F=75.838$, $p=0.000$). Similarly, the study revealed that every unit change in Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies will significantly affect operational efficiency of small businesses by 67.4% ($Beta=0.674$, $p=0.000$).

4.3 Discussion of Findings

The study finding revealed that artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies have positive effect on revenue growth of small businesses in Enugu Metropolis. This finding was based off data collected between 2020 and 2022 which showed an increase year over year in profits from many small business owners who utilized AI technology to optimize operations, development strategies and marketing campaigns. These results demonstrate how these advanced technological tools can be used by local entrepreneurs to accelerate their business's performance even amid turbulent or uncertain market conditions when traditional methods may not produce desired outcomes. Further studies are needed however as this result strongly affirms potential use cases for SMEs within similar regional settings seeking solutions through state-of-the art tech advances like machine learning analytics, natural language processing industry analysis software suites etc (Rao, 2018).

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The finding of the study shows that Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies have positive effect on operational efficiency of small businesses in Enugu Metropolis. This study is congruent with Elegunde and Shotunde (2020), which revealed that from reducing costs to increasing customer service levels, it appears that incorporating machine learning and other forms of intelligent automation into daily activities boosts productivity while freeing up employees time for more strategic tasks or skill development opportunities, resulting in sustainable competitive advantages throughout all aspects of an organisation's operation chain workflow capabilities. Overall, this evidence suggests far-reaching implications associated with the adoption of artificial intelligence technology initiatives within business sectors across the globe today, and as such, highlights need careful strategizing considerations moving forward when assessing investments related to new digital transformation ventures and initiatives alike going further down the road (Bag, Gupta, Kumar and Sivarajah, 2021).

5. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Findings

Having carried out this research project, the researcher made the following findings:

1. The study revealed that Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies have positive effect on revenue growth of small businesses in Enugu Metropolis ($R^2=0.431$, $p=0.000$).
2. The study revealed that Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies have positive effect on operational efficiency of small businesses in Enugu Metropolis ($R^2=0.455$, $p=0.000$).

5.2 Conclusion

In conclusion, the effect of artificial intelligence on small business performance in Enugu has been significant. Artificial intelligence has enabled businesses to streamline their operations, improve efficiency, and reduce costs. However, there are also concerns about job displacement and the need for upskilling employees to work alongside artificial intelligence systems. Small businesses in Enugu must embrace AI technology while also being mindful of its potential impact on their workforce. Ultimately, the successful integration of artificial intelligence into small business operations will require careful planning and a commitment to ongoing training and development.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion, the researcher made the following recommendations:

- i. In order to maximize the benefits of artificial intelligence, it is recommended that small businesses invest in artificial intelligence tools and technologies, prioritize employee training and education on artificial intelligence, and collaborate with other businesses to share knowledge and resources. By doing so, small businesses can improve their performance and stay competitive in a rapidly evolving market.

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- ii. There should be proper and full adoption of artificial intelligence to help enhance customer satisfaction, as this will stimulate continuous patronage and foster repeat purchase and also serve as a customer retention strategy, depending on its application.

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References

- Accenture. (2020). How Small Businesses Can Gain a Competitive Edge Through AI. Accenture. Retrieved from <https://www.accenture.com/us-en/insights/artificial-intelligence/ai-advantage-small-business>
- Akpan, I. J. Udoh, E. A. P. and Adebisi, B. (2020, on-line first). Small Business Awareness and Adoption of State-Of-The-Art Technologies in Emerging and Developing Markets, and Lessons from the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship*.
- Armour, J. and Sako, M. (2020). AI-Enabled Business Models in Legal Services: From Traditional Law Firms to Next-Generation Law Companies? *Journal of Professions and Organization*, 7(1): 27–46. Bank of England. How Has Covid-19 Affected Small UK Companies? London: Bank of England.
- Bag, S., Gupta, S., Kumar, S., and Sivarajah, U. (2020a). Role of technological dimensions of green supply chain management practices on firm performance. *J. Enterp. Inf. Manag.* 34, 1–27. doi: 10.1108/JEIM-10-2019-0324
- Bag, S., Gupta, S., Kumar, A., and Sivarajah, U. (2021). An integrated artificial intelligence framework for knowledge creation and B2B marketing rational decision making for improving firm performance. *Ind. Mark. Manag.* 92, 178–189. doi: 10.1016/j.indmarman.2020.12.001
- Baldegger, R., Caon, M., and Sadiku, K. (2020). Correlation between entrepreneurial orientation and implementation of AI in human resource management (HRM). *Technol. Innov. Manag. Rev.* 10, 72–79. doi: 10.22215/timreview/1348
- Barney, J. (1991). Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage. *J. Manag.* 17, 99–120. doi: 10.1177/014920639101700108
- Belhadi, A., Mani, V., Kamble, S. S., Khan, S. A. R., and Verma, S. (2021). Artificial intelligence-driven innovation for enhancing supply chain resilience and performance under the effect of supply chain dynamism: an empirical investigation. *Ann. Oper. Res.* 1–26. doi: 10.1007/s10479-021-03956-x [Epub ahead of print].
- Blohm, I., Antretter, T., Sirén, C., Grichnik, D., and Wincent, J. (2020). It's a peoples game, Isn't it? A comparison Between the investment returns of business angels and machine

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON SMALL BUSINESS PERFORMANCE

learning algorithms. *Entrep. Theory Pract.* 2020:1042258720945206. doi: 10.1177/1042258720945206

Chatterjee, S., Chaudhuri, R., and Vrontis, D. (2021b). Does data-driven culture impact innovation and performance of a firm? An empirical examination. *Ann. Oper. Res.* 1–26. doi: 10.1007/s10479-020-03887-z

Chatterjee, S., Rana, N. P., Tamilmani, K., and Sharma, A. (2021a). The effect of AI-based CRM on organization performance and competitive advantage: an empirical analysis in the B2B context. *Ind. Mark. Manag.* 97, 205–219. doi: 10.1016/j.indmarman.2021.07.013

Chaudhuri, R., Chatterjee, S., Vrontis, D., and Thrassou, A. (2021). Adoption of robust business analytics for product innovation and organizational performance: the mediating role of organizational data-driven culture. *Ann. Oper. Res.* 1–35. doi: 10.1007/s10479-021-04407-3

Chen, C. H. V., and Chen, Y. C. (2021). Influence of intellectual capital and integration on operational performance: big data analytical capability perspectives. *Chin. Manag. Stud.* doi:10.1108/CMS-02-2021-0037 [Epub ahead of print].

Chen, Y., and Lin, Z. (2021). Business intelligence capabilities and firm performance: a study in China. *Int. J. Inf. Manag.* 57:102232. doi: 10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2020.102232

Chen, X., and Siau, K. (2020). Business analytics/business intelligence and IT infrastructure: impact on organizational agility. *J. Organ. End User Comput.* 32, 138–161. doi: 10.4018/JOEUC.2020100107

Elegunde, A.F. & Shotunde, O.I. (2020) Effects of Artificial Intelligence on Business Performance in the Banking Industry (A Study of Access Bank Plc and United Bank for Africa-Uba). *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)*, 22(5): PP 41-49

Ferreira, J., Coelho, A., and Moutinho, L. (2020). Dynamic capabilities, creativity and innovation capability and their impact on competitive advantage and firm performance: The moderating role of entrepreneurial orientation. *Technovation* 92–93:102061. doi: 10.1016/j.technovation.2018.11.004

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON SMALL BUSINESS PERFORMANCE

- Frost & Sullivan. (2019). The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Small Businesses. Frost & Sullivan. Retrieved from <https://ww2.frost.com/frost-perspectives/the-impact-of-artificial-intelligence-on-small-businesses/>
- Ghasemaghaei, M. (2021). Understanding the impact of big data on firm performance: the necessity of conceptually differentiating among big data characteristics. *Int. J. Inf. Manag.* 57:102055. doi: 10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2019.102055
- Giannoulakis, C. (2020). Sponsorship in marketing: effective partnerships in sports, arts, and events. *J. Sport Manag.* 35, 278–279. doi: 10.1123/jsm.2020-0329
- Kim, J. B. (2019). Implementation of artificial intelligence system and traditional system: a comparative study. *J. Syst. Manag. Sci.* 9, 135–146. doi: 10.33168/JSMS.2019.0309
- Łapińska, J., Escher, I., Górka, J., Sudolska, A., and Brzustewicz, P. (2021). Employees' Trust in Artificial Intelligence in companies: the case of energy and chemical Industries in Poland. *Energies* 14:1942. doi: 10.3390/en14071942
- Liu, Y., Lee, Y., and Chen, A. N. (2020b). How IT wisdom affects firm performance: An empirical investigation of 15-year US panel data. *Decis. Support. Syst.* 133:113300. doi: 10.1016/j.dss.2020.113300
- Mostafiz, M. I., Hughes, M., and Sambasivan, M. (2021). Entrepreneurial orientation, competitive advantage and strategic knowledge management capability in Malaysian family firms. *J. Knowl. Manag.* 26, 423–458. doi: 10.1108/JKM-09-2020-0693
- National Small Business Association. (2019). AI Adoption in Small Business. NSBA. Retrieved from <https://www.nsba.biz/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/AI-Adoption-in-Small-Business.pdf>
- Obschonka, M., and Audretsch, D. B. (2020). Artificial intelligence and big data in entrepreneurship: a new era has begun. *Small Bus. Econ.* 55, 529–539. doi: 10.1007/s11187-019-00202-4
- Rana, N. P., Chatterjee, S., Dwivedi, Y. K., and Akter, S. (2021). Understanding dark side of artificial intelligence (AI) integrated business analytics: assessing firm's operational inefficiency and competitiveness. *Eur. J. Inf. Syst.*, 1–24. doi: 10.1080/0960085X.2021.1955628

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON SMALL BUSINESS PERFORMANCE

- Rao, A. (2018). Artificial intelligence is no silver bullet for small businesses. *Forbes*. Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbestechcouncil/2018/05/01/artificial-intelligence-is-no-silver-bullet-for-small-businesses/?sh=7b00fc4b4fc0>
- Vrontis, D., Christofi, M., Pereira, V., Tarba, S., Makrides, A., and Trichina, E. (2021). Artificial intelligence, robotics, advanced technologies and human resource management: a systematic review. *Int. J. Hum. Resour. Manag.* 33, 1237–1266. doi: 10.1080/09585192.2020.1871398
- Yao, M., Ye, D., Yang, G., Shi, H., and Zheng, X. (2021). Are entrepreneurial capabilities and prior knowledge the silver bullet for the generation of new digital venture ideas in a digital context? *J. Glob. Inf. Manag.* 29, 1–17. doi: 10.4018/JGIM.20211101.0a12
- Yasmin, M., Tatoglu, E., Kilic, H. S., Zaim, S., and Delen, D. (2020). Big data analytics capabilities and firm performance: an integrated MCDM approach. *J. Bus. Res.* 114, 1–15. doi: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.03.028
- Yu, F., Jiang, D., Zhang, Y., and Du, H. (2021). Enterprise digitalisation and financial performance: the moderating role of dynamic capability. *Tech. Anal. Strat. Manag.* 1–17. doi: 10.1080/09537325.2021.1980211
- Zhang, H., Song, M., and He, H. (2020). Achieving the success of sustainability development projects through big data analytics and artificial intelligence capability. *Sustain. For.* 12:949. doi: 10.3390/su12030949